

Climate-Adapted Conservation Strategy for Southern California Montane Forests

**DRAFT STRATEGY
JULY 2024**

CLIMATE-ADAPTED CONSERVATION STRATEGY FOR SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA MONTANE FORESTS

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PREFERRED CITATION

S. Hennessy, M. Jennings, N. Molinari, C. Magee, A. Pairis, and H. Safford. 2024. Climate-Adapted Conservation Strategy for Southern Montane Forests. 131 pp.

COVER PHOTO

Prescribed fire on the Descanso Ranger District of the Cleveland National Forest, Dana Barre

Acknowledgements

We thank Carolyn Enquist (Ecosystem Mission Area, U.S. Geological Survey) for her support as a member of the project leader group and primary funding collaborator. She and Hugh Safford had the vision that made this project possible. Jeff Heys (Wildfire Crisis Strategy Landscape Manager for Southern California, USDA Forest Service) also served on the project leader group throughout. We thank Althea Walker, Director of Community Resilience at Climate Science Alliance, for Tribal coordination and support. Diane Terry, Director of Communications at Climate Science Alliance, supported project design and outreach.

We would like to acknowledge the time and contributions of the Southern Montane Forests Advisory Group listed below:

Matthew Bokach	San Gabriel Mountains National Monument, Angeles National Forest
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Participants of the Tribal Working Group, in association with Climate Science Alliance, contributed input and review at several points throughout the project. In addition, Northern Institute of Applied Climate Science, California Climate Hub, and USFS Region 5 Ecology Program welcomed our use of their products and publications and supported our efforts to further develop them for Southern California.

The following subject matter experts provided input and technical review at different points in the development of this conservation strategy: Charles Barnes, Steve Bear, Matthew Bokach, Jean Brennan, Christy Brigham, Dan Cayan, Lance Criley, Frank Davis, Stephen Fillmore, Janet Franklin, Emily Fudge, Heidi George, Lacey Hankin, Stacy Hishinuma, Bethany Kyre, John Lovio, Toni Lyn Morelli, Tina Mozelewski, Monica Pina, Joeline Tamm, Jim Thorne, Ian Turner, Andrew Weinhart, and Kirsten Winter.

Executive Summary

Montane forests (forests above c. 3600 ft/1200 m elevation) are restricted to “sky islands” of mountain habitat in the Transverse and Peninsular mountain ranges of Southern California. Ongoing major threats to ecosystem integrity include rapid climate warming; persistent, long-term droughts; the highest ozone pollution levels in the nation; altered fire regimes that result in uncharacteristic wildfire; rapid habitat loss due to urban development; and damaging invasive species. Furthermore, the suppression of Indigenous landscape stewardship and fire practices since colonization and the exclusion of Indigenous science has contributed to present-day issues associated with ecological health, climate resilience, and community fire risk in California. Without proactive management focused on forest health, much of southern California’s montane forests may be lost in coming decades to these compounding threats.

Vision and Scope

This conservation strategy seeks to conserve montane forest ecosystems in the Southern California sky islands and to sustain the ecosystem services and benefits they provide.

The conservation strategy applies to all higher elevation forested lands across the region, regardless of ownership, promoting an all-lands approach. The major disturbances that are driving forest loss cross ownership boundaries, and successful management of forest resilience to these stressors requires partnership across boundary lines. The strategy includes conifer and hardwood forest types, and also focuses on the ecological and social factors that distinguish Southern California. It provides recommendations for climate-adapted management with a focus on investment and management actions in key landscapes.

Region-specific characteristics of montane forests

Montane forests in Southern California are regionally distinct in structure and composition. In addition to drought- and fire-tolerant yellow pine species (*Pinus ponderosa* and *P. jeffreyi*), mixed conifer species such as white fir (*Abies concolor*), incense cedar (*Calocedrus decurrens*), and Coulter pine (*Pinus coulteri*) occur with patchy distribution. There are also forest types with more limited extent that occupy unique habitats such as subalpine at higher elevations, pinyon pines along desert edges, as well as patches of the regional endemic, Bigcone Douglas-fir (*Pseudotsuga macrocarpa*), which provides valuable wildlife habitat. Hardwood associates such as black oak (*Quercus kelloggii*) and several species of live oaks are found at most elevations. These forests are not considered timber-producing, and in contrast with the rest of California, National Forest lands in southern California do not have timber production targets. Shrub cover varies from absent to dense, the latter where tree cover is low and especially after disturbance.

The montane forests of southern California have less geophysical connectivity than the Sierra Nevada and Cascade mountain ranges. With a few exceptions, montane forest occurs in disjunct patches separated by lower, warmer elevations often vegetated with chaparral and live oaks. The boundary between montane forest and chaparral generally lies in closer proximity to forest stands than elsewhere. This proximity plays a critical role in fire spread in southern California, given that these two vegetation types are adapted to very different fire regimes. Chaparral burns at high intensity over large areas, especially during Santa Ana wind conditions, while montane forest is generally fire-adapted to carry

flames at lower intensities. In montane forest, the historic fire regime maintained a characteristically short fire return interval and fire intensity and severity were generally low, with estimates of high severity fire effects constituting less than 10% of the burned area.

As elsewhere in California, fire exclusion and selective logging over the last century increased the density of shade-tolerant and relatively fire-intolerant species. Currently the proportion of high severity effects during wildfires has increased, and decades of fuel accumulation prevents the safe reintroduction of fire in many locations without initial understory thinning.

Purpose of the strategy

This Conservation Strategy has been designed as a roadmap for increasing the resilience, sustainability, and persistence of southern California's montane forests. By identifying climate-informed implementation actions, this strategy will support planning and management efforts to enhance forest health and resilience and safeguard the local communities that live in and benefit from these forests. The strategy is also intended to build a community of practice by promoting collaborative action and fostering the development of partnerships to improve forest resilience.

Created with collaborative input

To better understand the specific challenges to increasing the resilience of southern California's montane forests, we asked forest management practitioners—including planners, fire managers, foresters, ecologists, Tribes, and more—about their experiences through a peer-reviewed questionnaire. The information gathered from the questionnaire has informed and shaped the development of the conservation plan and the adaptation strategies highlighted in the plan.

Use of the strategy

Leaning into the diversity of these lands and wide range of ownerships, this strategy focuses on supporting the processes of planning and implementation rather than attempting to apply a uniform set of prescriptive management strategies to all lands. This approach supports region-wide efforts to increase the pace and scale of the work to restore forest structure (primarily through understory thinning and prescribed fire) and prioritizes key portions of the landscape where these actions are effective and ecologically beneficial.

Integrating climate adaptation strategies into forest management planning and practice is also critical for successfully responding to changing conditions, and for ensuring effective use of management staff and funding. Management that incorporates climate adaptation responds to observed impacts or prepares for projected future change, rather than responding to conditions that no longer exist or are not likely to persist. The process of incorporating climate adaptation is best accomplished by considering climate impacts throughout the planning, implementation, and evaluation cycle, so that both decision-making processes and management actions may be adjusted along the way.

This Conservation Strategy recommends, supports, and facilitates the use of three processes by managers:

1. Prioritize Forest Resilience Projects at Landscape-Scale. The first component of the conservation strategy is a customized decision framework for supporting landscape-scale project delineation and prioritization. Prioritization is a major component of both Federal and State efforts to increase the pace and scale of treatments. The Southern Montane Forests Framework is climate-adapted and aligned with the best-available science in Southern California. Conducting landscape-scale prioritization planning will help managers to maintain flexibility and enable rapid management response during unpredictable funding cycles.

2. Adapt for Climate Stressors at Project Level. This strategy recommends increased use of the Adaptation Workbook approach for project-scale planning (Janowiak et al. 2022). A regionally relevant Adaptation Menu (based on the CA Climate Hub's Forest Adaptation Strategies Menu, Swanston et al. 2020) is the second component of the strategy, provided to guide managers through their options for forest management after project delineation and prioritization (Appendix B). This Menu summarizes the best management tactics for Southern California's forests. In many cases the most important types of management for resilience to stressors will not be unfamiliar. Reintroducing fire and reducing understory density will frequently be the most important management needed. However, the menu should also be used to consider more transformative alternatives in locations experiencing high levels of exposure to climate and disturbances.

3. Consider Context in Reforestation. The third component of the strategy is focused on post-fire landscapes. After fire, the Postfire Restoration Framework (Meyer et al. 2021) can assist in the identification of a portfolio of priority sites and restoration projects. The framework can be applied to any postfire landscape of interest and allows flexibility with respect to management priorities and goals. The framework emphasizes analysis of the burned area within both climate and habitat contexts. The context of anticipated future climate conditions puts necessary sideboards on reforestation projects. Often, the best approach will be to prioritize planting in locations of climate refugia and slower warming over more exposed locations. The habitat-focused context includes consideration of ecological attributes such as regional native biodiversity and habitat connectivity. This approach prioritizes the reforestation of mature native forest stands, with their higher species and structural diversity, over simpler and younger plantation stands.

The framework also emphasizes long-term ecosystem integrity and function through incorporation of natural range of variability (NRV) into the analysis flow. In fire-adapted forests, where the process of fire plays a central role in maintaining forest condition, locations where fire effects are positive should be considered separately from the locations where fire effects were outside the natural range of variability.

The processes and tools recommended by this conservation strategy are largely well-documented with manuals and case studies. However, the intent is not to ask managers to “start from scratch” using unfamiliar protocols and processes. The authors of this conservation strategy are experienced in using these processes through workshop engagements with a variety of audiences, including collaborative partnership groups. In many cases, the authors of this strategy will be available to guide use of the Southern Montane Forests Framework, the adaptation workbook and menu, and the postfire restoration strategy.

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Introduction to the Strategy

Southern California (defined here as the portion of the State falling south of 35°30'0" N latitude and west of 116° longitude, roughly from Morro Bay south) is one of the most biodiverse regions in the United States. The region is characterized by high habitat heterogeneity, strong topographic and climatic gradients, and a suite of active ecological and geological processes such as wildfires, earthquakes, mountain uplift, floods, and debris flows. The region is also characterized by a large and growing human population (24 million people, or c. 8% of the U.S. total) and the level of regional threat to plants and animals, their habitats and the ecosystem services they provide is unparalleled in the U.S. Federal and State sensitive, threatened, and endangered species number in the hundreds. Specific threats include rapid climate warming; persistent, long-term droughts; the highest ozone pollution levels in the nation; altered fire regimes that result in uncharacteristic wildfire; rapid habitat loss due to urban development; and an expanding list of damaging invasive species.

Montane forests (forests above c. 3600 ft/1200 m elevation) are restricted to “sky islands” of mountain habitat found in the Peninsular and Transverse Ranges, with most of the montane forest area found in the San Jacinto, San Bernardino, and San Gabriel Mountains. As in the Sierra Nevada, southern California montane forests are dominated by a mix of conifers (mostly pines, firs, and incense cedar) and hardwood (mostly oak) species (Minnich 2007). Montane forests protect the upper watersheds of all the region’s major rivers and provide numerous ecosystem services, including carbon sequestration, soil conservation, erosion and sedimentation reduction, provision of plant and wildlife habitat and migration corridors, shading and cooling of surface waters, recreational opportunities, and aesthetic and spiritual amenities. These watersheds also provide about 40% of the water used for human, agricultural, and industrial purposes in southern California (USDA 2020).

Southern California’s mountains within the Peninsular and Transverse Ranges are the ancestral homelands of the Kumeyaay, Payómkawichum [Luiseño], Acjachemen, Kúupangaxwicheem [Cupeño], Cahuilla, Serrano, Tongva, Tataviam, and Chumash peoples, who are the original stewards of these lands. Post-Euro-American settlement, public management of the montane regions of southern California’s upper watersheds began in the late 1800s, when some of the nation’s first Federal Forest Reserves were created to protect forest and soil resources and reduce downstream flooding and sedimentation. Most montane forests in southern California are managed by the U.S. Forest Service (total area = c. 470,000 acres), with a smaller portion managed by California State Parks (c. 37,000 acres total) and a handful of other organizations, including counties, cities, and Tribes. Private holdings of montane forest in southern California total about 152,000 acres. The sky island forests have figured prominently among both national- and regional-scale assessments of critical landscape components for conservation (USFS 10-Year Wildfire Crisis Strategy 2021, Belote et al. 2017, Belote et al. 2021, Stephenson and Calcarone 1999). Within the region, Stephenson and Calcarone (1999) assessed National Forest lands and highlighted ongoing major threats to ecosystem integrity (changing fire regimes, hydrological alterations, invasive species, forest pest and pathogens, heavy recreational use, air pollution, and private land development). Since the assessment, these threats have intensified, in addition to rapid climate warming. Conservation of montane forests in southern California into the future is contingent on updating our understanding of the vulnerabilities and challenges facing these forests and integrating these considerations into management practices at a landscape scale.

Vision

The vision for successful forest conservation in the region is based on a foundation of diverse and inclusive collaborations to conserve southern California’s sky islands and sustain the ecosystem services and benefits they provide. Without proactive management focused on forest health, much of southern California’s montane forests may be lost in coming decades to the compounding threats of climate change, fire, insects, disease, and air pollution.

This conservation strategy applies to all higher elevation forested lands across the region, regardless of ownership. The major disturbances that are driving forest loss cross ownership boundaries, and successful management of forest resilience to these stressors requires partnership across boundary lines. The strategy includes conifer and hardwood forest types, incorporating both the ecological and social factors that distinguish southern California. It provides recommendations for climate-adapted management investments and management actions in key landscapes.

Alignment

The strategy focuses on a regional scale, leveraging forest and climate expertise to develop recommendations specific to Southern California’s montane forests. These recommendations can assist with strategic prioritization for landscape-scale implementation. We are aligned with State initiatives and strategies focused on resilience, such as the [California Wildfire and Forest Resilience Action Plan](#) (2021) and the [Strategic Plan for Expanding the Use of Beneficial Fire](#) (2022), as well as conservation, such as the State’s 30x30 initiative and the federal [America the Beautiful](#) campaign. At the Federal level, we are also aligned with the U.S. Forest Service’s [10-year Wildfire Crisis Strategy](#) (2022) and [Shared Stewardship Strategy](#) (2020). In 2023, Southern California was designated a USFS Wildfire Crisis Strategy Landscape. The landscape project is called the Southern California Fireshed Risk Reduction Strategy and brings additional focus and resources to this region.

Southern Montane Forests

Yellow pine and mixed conifer (collectively “YPMC”) forests are the predominant forest types in California (Barbour et al. 2007). The drought- and fire- tolerant “yellow pines” (*Pinus ponderosa* and *P. jeffreyi*) generally formed the backbone of most YPMC forests before Euro-American settlement, but selective logging and fire exclusion over the last century or more have greatly increased the density of shade-tolerant and relatively fire-intolerant species statewide (Safford and Stevens 2017). In southern California, ponderosa pine is the dominant yellow pine up to about 5200 ft in elevation, where it is replaced by Jeffrey pine; Jeffrey is also the dominant yellow pine on the drier north and east sides of the major mountain ranges (Keeley 2006, Minnich 2007). At mesic sites such as lower slopes, northern aspects, and higher elevations, white fir (*Abies concolor*) and incense cedar (*Calocedrens decurrens*) are important associates in YPMC stands, often with a component of sugar pine (*P. lambertiana*) (Keeley 2006). Canyon live oak (*Quercus chrysolepis*) and black oak (*Quercus kelloggii*) are YPMC hardwood associates at most elevations, and shrub cover varies from absent to dense, the latter where tree cover is low and especially after disturbance (Minnich 2007). In pre-settlement YPMC forests, spatial patterns were heterogeneous and overall tree densities were relatively low, with most of the total basal area in

larger trees (Safford and Stevens 2017). Survey data from the San Bernardino Mountains in the 1930s described an open forest structure, with a mix of age classes but a preponderance of larger trees (diameter at breast height > 26 cm, Minnich et al. 1995).

Prior to Euro-American settlement (“pre-EAS”), YPMC forests experienced frequent fires from lightning and human ignitions (Bendix and Hartnett, 2018), with Indigenous forest stewardship practices relying heavily on the use of fire (Anderson, 2005). Characteristic of the YPMC fire regime was a short fire return interval (generally <15 years) and predominantly low fire intensity and severity (North et al. 2016, Safford et al. 2021). Studies of reference forests in Baja California, historical stand data, and simulation modeling suggest that high severity fire effects constituted <10% of the burn area (Mallek et al. 2013, Rivera-Huerta et al. 2016, Stephens et al. 2008). While pockets of high severity fire occasionally opened larger gaps in the forest canopy, the preponderance of low to moderate fire severity created an overall fine-grained heterogeneous structure with mostly small canopy openings (Safford and Stevens 2017). Modern fire regimes in YPMC forests in California are drastically changed from the pre-EAS condition. Fire frequency has been greatly reduced, which has led to increased fuels and more severe fires when burning does occur (Safford et al. 2021).

Subalpine forests occur above about 8200 ft in southern California and are dominated by lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta*), with limber pine (*Pinus flexilis*) in localized occurrences on the higher mountains above 8500 ft (Minnich 2007). The red fir (*Abies magnifica*) belt found between YPMC and subalpine forests in the rest of California is absent in southern California. Pre-EAS subalpine forests supported fire regimes characterized by infrequent, high severity crown fires that torched lodgepole stands, leaving many standing dead boles behind. Fire return intervals were greater than 100 years, and the ignition source was often lightning. After fire, snags gradually fell and large patches of burned forest recovered through growth of new even-aged stands (Minnich 1988).

Montane forest types in this region also include mixed evergreen forests. In a southern California version of mixed evergreen, Bigcone Douglas-fir (*Pseudotsuga macrocarpa*) occurs with canyon live oak in fragmented groves in steep canyons, predominately on north-facing slopes, talus, and cliff faces between 3,300 and 7,200 ft (Sawyer et al. 1977, Minnich 2007). Lower elevation stands are surrounded by chaparral, and at higher elevations they intergrade with mixed-conifer forest (Lombardo et al. 2009, Minnich 2007). Bigcone Douglas-fir is one of the few western conifers that can resprout along the bole and branches after fire, but tree survival is minimal after high severity burning (Minnich 1977). On dry rocky slopes and ridgelines, Coulter pine (*Pinus coulteri*) mixes with canyon live oak and chamise (*Adenostema fasciculatum*) chaparral. More continuous stands of Coulter pine occur in mesic headwaters on the desert side of the mountains.

The fire regime of mixed evergreen forests is strongly influenced by topography and proximity to chaparral. Chaparral supports a fire regime with a long fire return interval (35-100+ years) but high-severity fire. The mixed evergreen species of canyon live oak and Coulter pine both associate with denser stands of chaparral and will regenerate quickly and vigorously after high-severity fire (Borchert 1985, Keely and Zedler 1998, Minnich 1979, Minnich 1988). Bigcone Douglas-fir requires a long fire-free period for regeneration (saplings do not bear cones until they are at least 40-50 years old) and mature Bigcone is generally associated with sparse chaparral cover (McDonald 1990). It also relies on mesic canyons and dissected cliff faces as refugia from high-severity fire (Minnich 1980).

Region-specific characteristics of montane forests

Southern California experiences the highest interannual variability in precipitation in the United States. Atmospheric river events are a major source of moisture, and half of annual precipitation typically comes in only 5-10 days during the winter and spring. While precipitation may fall in the form of snow at montane elevations, in general snowpack accumulation and timing of snowmelt are less significant than in other parts of the state. In addition, Santa Ana winds drive major fire events beginning in October each year, which overlaps with the end of dry and warm “fire season” conditions. These wind events peak in December and occur intermittently into May. Existing fuels and vegetation models do not always accurately reflect the fire dynamics that occur during these wind events.

The region’s forests are not timber-producing. Currently, National Forest lands in Southern California do not have timber production targets, in contrast with Forest lands in the rest of the State. There are also no private lands owned by timber companies that are used for commercial harvest. Before establishment of the National Forest system, logging had localized impacts, but once the National Forests were created, intensive logging on Federally-owned forest lands ended. When mechanical thinning occurs, it is generally designed to accomplish forest health and community safety objectives (reduce stand densities and fire hazard) while limiting collateral damages to natural and cultural resources. After the major forest mortality event of 2002-2005, federal, state, and local entities cooperated to remove large volumes of dead trees. However, there were and remain few outlets for wood utilization in the region (e.g. sawmills or biomass facilities) and shipping costs are high. Frequently the primary end use is for personal firewood supplies. Onsite options include whole-tree chipping, pile burning, or use of an air curtain burner, but these are best suited for smaller volumes than are currently needed across the region.

The montane forests of Southern California have lower geophysical connectivity than the Sierra/Cascades. With the exception of the central portion of the San Bernardino Mountains, montane forest occurs in disjunct patches separated by lower, warmer elevations often vegetated with chaparral and live oaks. The boundary between montane forest and chaparral generally lies in closer proximity to forest stands in Southern California than elsewhere. This proximity plays a critical role in fire spread in Southern California, given that these two vegetation communities are adapted to very different fire regimes. Chaparral burns at high intensity over large areas, especially during Santa Ana wind conditions, while montane forest is generally fire-adapted to carry flames at lower intensities. However, with increases in human-caused ignition sources and ongoing land-use change, greater numbers of fires are being started along roadsides or in the wildland urban interface (WUI), and excessively dense montane forest stands are primed to burn at stand-replacing intensities after a century of fire exclusion. The likelihood of large fires crossing from chaparral into vulnerable forest stands is therefore currently very high.

There is less biological connectivity for gene flow as well among Southern California forest stands. For example, Ponderosa pine in Southern California has been found to be more similar genetically to southwestern (Nevada, New Mexico) populations than Sierra Nevada populations (Potter et al 2013). The sources for seeds with climate-appropriate genetics differ from the rest of California. Seed sources from higher latitudes across California may not be adapted to local climate conditions, and sources from lower latitudes require international cooperation. The southern U.S. border with Mexico complicates efforts to expand sources of genetic material.

Will montane sky island forest persist?

In the 20 years since the publication of the SCMFA, the condition of montane forests in Southern California has markedly declined. Minimum temperatures have increased by 3-5°F at many stations since the early 20th century (Molinari et al. 2016, Sawyer et al. 2014), and ozone has continued to exceed national standards (US EPA 2021). Coupled with the highest interannual variability in precipitation in the United States and high forest densities due to fire suppression, these trends are leading to major physiological stress in Southern California YPMC forests.

Two major conifer mortality events have occurred in Southern California in the past 20 years. The first was triggered by drought between 1999 and 2003, followed by one of the most severe outbreaks of western pine beetle up to that time (Minnich 2007, Minnich et al. 2016, Kolb et al. 2016, Fettig 2019). A study in 2003 showed that bark beetles were more active in locations with greater pollution levels (Jones and Paine, 2004). USFS Aerial Detection Surveys measured conifer mortality between 2002-2005 of approximately 2.8 million trees across the four National Forests in Southern California. These losses appear to have impacted the prevalence of larger trees in the community; by the 2000s, contemporary large tree density was less than 30% of densities measured in the Transverse and Peninsular ranges in the 1930s (McIntyre et al. 2015). There is also some evidence of upslope shifts in conifer distribution in the San Jacinto Mountains and San Diego County as a result of lower elevation tree mortality during the 1999-2003 drought, which likely correlates with enhanced drought stress at lower elevations (Fellows and Goulden 2012, Freeman et al. 2017).

The second drought extended from 2012 to 2016 (Asner et al. 2016) and triggered a major forest die-off event in the Sierra Nevada Mountains, especially impacting low-elevation ponderosa pine (Fettig et al 2019, Restaino et al. 2019, Stephenson and Das 2020). Forests in Southern California were much less affected, with the Aerial Detection Surveys estimating conifer mortality between 2010-2019 at 1.4 million trees. It is notable that YPMC forests in the Sierra de San Pedro Mártir in northern Baja California, which were not logged and have only experienced a few decades of fire suppression, suffered little to no enhanced mortality during these drought events, probably due to much lower tree densities and better forest health than their US counterparts (Dunbar-Irwin and Safford 2016, Murphy et al. 2021).

Throughout the 2000s, severe wildfires (e.g. Cedar, Grand Prix, and Old Fires 2003, Butler 2 Fire 2007, Day Fire 2008, Station Fire 2009, Mountain Fire 2013, Lake Fire 2015, Bobcat and Apple Fires 2020) have burned large areas of montane forest in Southern California (Nigro and Molinari 2019), and conifer forest did not regenerate in the early years following severe fire in some burned areas (Franklin et al. 2006, Franklin and Bergman 2011, Goforth et al. 2008, Safford and Vallejo 2019). One extensive global survey of recent cases of drought- and fire-induced forest mortality across many biomes found self-replacement of the dominant tree species in only 21% of cases (Batllori et al. 2020). A compositional shift from conifer species towards oaks appears to have begun in Southern California (measured as shifts in basal area; McIntyre et al. 2015), but ongoing invasion by the Goldspotted Oak Borer beetle (*Agrilus auroguttatus*) is killing large numbers of oaks in Southern California and complicating our ability to project future forest trajectories. While mortality in oak woodlands was not consistently measured prior to about 2006, detection became more urgent due to the spreading effects of Goldspotted Oak Borer (GSOB). Between 2010-2019, USFS aerial surveys recorded approximately 74,000 dead oaks (including both evergreen and deciduous species) across Southern California.

Analysis of satellite imagery has shown that as of 2021, approximately 14% of the conifer forest and oak woodland cover that existed in 1985 has been lost in Southern California, the highest relative loss measured across California (Wang et al. 2022). Wang et al. (2022) attributed the losses in this region to severe wildfires and regeneration failure. Unfortunately, model accuracy for detecting forest die-off due to drought was lower than that for fire, harvest, and regrowth, and may have been underestimated. To date, though, this is the most comprehensive estimate of forest loss available. These events lead to questions such as, what constitutes “persistence” of montane forests? What if conifers are no longer the dominant tree type? If oaks become the dominant, will we still have a montane forest?

Interacting threats to montane forests in Southern California

Fire Exclusion

Discussion of current and future threats to montane forest persistence begins with current forest condition, which has been shaped on forest lands by over 100 years of fire exclusion, including suppression of wildfires and forced cessation of fire use by Native Americans and rural populations. In Southern California, where large urban and agricultural populations developed earlier than in the rest of the state, concerns about fire-related hazards such as mudflows into agricultural fields and decreased summer water supply for irrigation drove both the establishment of the first Forest Reserves in the United States and early efforts to manage them (Cermak 2005). Even in the earliest years of the original National Forest Reserves (precursor to the US Forest Service lands), fire control was a core part of the forest ranger’s responsibilities (Cermak 2005).

A regional survey of fire scar dendrochronology indicates that prior to fire exclusion, mean fire return interval ranged between 2.0-13.3 years (Skinner et al. 2006). With fire exclusion, fire return intervals (FRI) increased. In a recent study in Southern California, half of YPMC stands on Forest Service lands had experienced no fire in the past 100 years (Nigro and Molinari 2019). In the same study area, mean FRI had increased more than four-fold over presettlement levels by 2016 (Nigro and Molinari 2019). For forest stands included in this review, comparison of current FRI against reference presettlement FRIs shows that 95% of acres classified as dry mixed conifer and 98% of acres classified as yellow pine are considered highly departed from presettlement fire return intervals (Table 1). Nearly all (98%) acres of oak woodland also fall in the highly-departed category, as do 88% of moist mixed conifer acres.

TABLE 1. Forest area included in this review, characterized by the current (2021) degree of departure from reference presettlement fire return intervals (USFS Regional Ecology Program).

Presettlement Fire Regime	Direction and degree of change						Acres by PFR
	Too much fire			Not enough fire			
	High	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	High	
Bigcone Douglas-fir	-	3%	22%	37%	30%	9%	69,163
California juniper	-	17%	48%	35%	-	-	48
Dry mixed conifer	-	-	-	-	5%	95%	74,358
Lodgepole pine	-	-	-	-	-	100%	6
Mixed evergreen	-	1%	16%	26%	27%	30%	172,057
Moist mixed conifer	-	-	-	-	12%	88%	105,056
Oak woodland	-	-	-	-	2%	98%	2,253
Pinyon juniper	6%	23%	-	71%	-	-	13,750
Subalpine forest	7%	24%	-	68%	-	-	446
Yellow pine	-	-	-	-	2%	98%	129,371
% Total Acres	0%	1%	8%	14%	15%	61%	566,508

Fire exclusion has subsequently been identified as the primary cause of contemporary changes to YPMC composition and structure (Minnich et al. 1995). For example, in the San Bernardino Mountains, Minnich et al. (1995) found strong compositional shifts towards white fir and incense cedar over a 60-year period. Stand densities increased, with small diameter size classes increasing three to ten-fold. Mesic mixed stands of ponderosa pine showed the greatest changes in composition and density, which included declines in larger ponderosa size classes (Minnich et al. 1995). These regional trends are similar to those documented in YPMC throughout California (McIntyre et al. 2015, McKelvey and Johnson 1992, Safford and Stevens 2017).

Wildfire is occurring on a much greater scale than the management activities (mechanical thinning and prescribed fire) to bring forests back within the historic NRV. Within the extent of montane forest affected by fire in the past 5 years (2016-2020), 88% of the dry mixed conifer acres and 91% of yellow pine acres

were in highly departed condition when they experienced wildfire. 93% of oak woodland was also in highly departed condition when it experienced wildfire. It is also worth noting that nearly 30% of acres classified as contiguous Bigcone Douglas-fir have burned in the past 5 years. The species occurs both in contiguous stands and as an incidental associate of mixed evergreen communities, of which nearly 15% of classified acres have burned in the past 5 years. This regionally endemic forest type is experiencing wildfire rapidly, largely before management activities occur. While Bigcone Douglas-fir is resilient to lower-severity fire, stands have been lost to severe fire.

Taken together, these changes translate to increased fire risk in YPMC forests. Increased stand densities provide additional fuels for fire, and result in higher vertical and horizontal fuel continuity (Safford and Stevens 2017). Increasing fire risk has resulted in increasing fire sizes in Southern California conifer forest since 1910 (Nigro and Molinari 2019). Accumulated fuels also contribute to greater fire severity (Steel et al. 2015, 2018; Safford and Stevens 2017, Miller and Safford 2012). In Southern California conifer forests, increases in mean and maximum high severity patch size have been documented for the period 1984-2016, as well as an increase in the mean proportion of high severity area per fire (Nigro and Molinari 2019). The situation in the reference forests of the Sierra de San Pedro Mártir (SSPM) in Baja California is very different. Fire severity and mean annual area burned at high severity have not changed over time in the SSPM, although a slight upward trend in high severity patch size may be driven by accumulating fuels caused by current fire suppression policies in Mexico (Rivera et al. 2016)

As a point of reference, surveys in the San Jacinto, San Bernardino, and San Gabriel Mountains at the turn of the twentieth century (1899-1900) reported that all forest areas showed evidence of multiple burns, but that damage to most areas was low (Leiberg 1900). Leiberg suggested that fire severity was low because of limited levels of litter and undergrowth, while concurrently reporting high severity fire effects in surveys of chaparral plots. In recent years, several observers have concluded that the fuel-driven shift in fire behavior in YPMC amounts to a shift from a fire regime of frequent, mostly low-intensity fire (fire return interval of 0-35 years) to infrequent, high-intensity fire (e.g. from LANDFIRE fire regime Type I to Type III or IV, depending on the site (Steel et al. 2015, Safford and Stevens 2017, Safford et al. 2021). Regimes III and IV are both characterized by a fire return interval of 35-100+ years, but differ in terms of the degree of high severity (“stand-replacing”) fire (Schmidt et al. 2002). Some forest types are adapted to stand-replacing fire, but YPMC conifer species are not adapted for regeneration after high severity fire (e.g., they lack serotinous cones, long-lived soil seedbank, and ability to resprout). Postfire regeneration is then at risk due to factors such as distant tree seed sources, subsequent reburning, and unfavorable conditions for seedling survival (Coop 2020). In YPMC, high severity fire effects over large land areas can delay or prevent postfire forest recovery (Franklin et al. 2006, Goforth et al. 2008, Safford and Vallejo 2019).

The current status of extremely high fire risk in YPMC forests is largely a legacy of a century of fire exclusion from the forests. The Land Management Plans for the National Forests in Southern California require full suppression of all wildland fires. Moreover, current forest conditions and fuel loading levels do not enable wildland fire use, due to the potential for catastrophic fire damage to communities and infrastructure. Fire suppression reduces the immediate likelihood of severe fire effects and losses, but also allows both fuel loads and the long-term likelihood of severe fire effects to continue increasing (Moreira et al. 2020). Prescribed fire is utilized by managers, but has been difficult to deploy on a scale sufficient to reverse the trends of long-term fire suppression. In many locations, it has been a slow process to gain social license from adjacent communities in support of prescribed fire.

Because forest density has a major influence on forest health and physiological stress, continued fire exclusion consequently exacerbates the negative effects of climate warming, air pollution, insect outbreaks, and pathogens on Southern California forests, as covered in the following sections.

Climate Stressors

Ongoing changes in climate are strongly linked to anthropogenic carbon emissions (Bedsworth et al. 2018). Trends in temperature are tracked by global climate models (GCMs), large-scale simulation models calibrated on historical climate data. GCMs employ potential climate pathways resulting from a range of possible emissions scenarios (called Representative Concentration Pathways - RCP, or Shared Socioeconomic Pathways - SSP) through the twenty-first century to determine greenhouse gas concentration trends used in simulations of future climate dynamics. Ensemble analysis of similar climate models gives an indication of the reliability of projections and forms the basis of future climate summaries such as those created for California's Fourth Climate Change Assessment (Pierce et al. 2018).

Some of the most frequently cited climate models for California are still based on extreme emissions scenarios, as in the RCP 8.5 scenario, which projects current emissions trends into the future with no mitigation. This pathway is associated with statewide increases in average temperatures by 7-9° F by the end of the present century (Pierce et al. 2018). Other frequently cited pathways, such as RCP 4.5, account for reduced emissions levels achieved through policy, changes in energy sources or technologies, or other mitigation. The RCP 4.5 scenario is associated with somewhat lower average temperature increases of 4-6° F, demonstrating what we could achieve through emissions mitigation (Pierce et al. 2018). The current trajectory falls in between these two pathways. While an updated suite of models are in the process of adoption for the 5th California Climate Assessment, the RCP 8.5 model pathway still adequately models projections for temperature and precipitation through about 2050; the pathways diverge more strongly after 2050. The updated suite of models will more accurately predict conditions for century end.

The further we proceed into the 21st century, trends in climate are projected to depart more strongly from historical averages. This holds true for the montane elevations of Southern California. Regional modeling efforts provide more precise downscaled projections for climate conditions within the current distribution of montane forests and provide additional detail on seasonal or periodic events such as heat waves, atmospheric river (AR) storms, and drought. as detailed in the following sections.

Temperature

In the past century, Southern California has warmed more rapidly than other regions of California in terms of both minimum and maximum temperatures (Cordero 2011). California overall has already experienced an average temperature increase of 0.4 °F (0.22° C) per decade since 1918 (Cordero 2011). Southern California has experienced the largest increase in drought stress (measured via climatic water deficit) in the state (Rapacciuolo et al., 2014). In the past 60 years, warming has been concentrated in lower-elevation inland locations experiencing rapid urban development (climate warming is enhanced in these areas by urban heat-island effects; Sequera 2015). However, projections show that for currently forested montane locations above 3600 ft (1200 m), maximum temperatures are projected to increase by mid-century on average by 4.5 (range 3.4 – 5.2)° F if mitigation is very successful (RCP 4.5), or more likely by 5.8 (4.5 – 6.5)° F (RCP 8.5, Cal Adapt tool, Pierce et al. 2018). By the end of the century, maximum temperatures in montane forests could increase on average from 6.0° F (RCP 4.5) to 9.0° F (RCP 8.5).

Increasing trends are also seen for minimum temperatures, which are also important in forested systems. In the region, warming temperatures are also expected to be associated with more intense heat waves (Jennings et al. 2018).

Precipitation Variability

Looking ahead, there continues to be a high level of uncertainty regarding the overall direction of precipitation change across California as a whole. GCMs indicate mid-latitude precipitation increases along with subtropical precipitation decreases. The boundary between the two patterns is expected to fall somewhere within the latitudes encompassed by California (Swain et al. 2018, Neelin et al. 2013). Recently, several modeling efforts have reported that precipitation may increase across much of California (Berg and Hall, 2015, Neelin et al. 2013, Wang et al. 2017, Yoon et al. 2015). Even if Southern California falls south of the boundary and into the region of project subtropical decreases, regionally downscaled models have indicated that decreased precipitation frequency could be offset by an increase in daily precipitation intensity (Pierce et al 2013). By the second half of the century, less frequent precipitation may cause increasingly frequent extreme dry conditions during the winter “wet season” (Berg and Hall 2015).

The future precipitation regime is likely to be more variable than historic baseline, and more dependent on extreme storm events (Pierce et al. 2013, Polade et al. 2017). This is significant, because Southern California already supports the highest interannual variability in precipitation in the United States, with half of annual precipitation typically coming in only 5-10 days of precipitation events (Dettinger et al. 2011). Increases in water cycle extremes will often be associated with Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events (El Niño/La Niña, Yoon et al. 2015). Recent projections indicate that a greater than threefold increase in frequency of extreme precipitation events is possible (Swain et al 2018).

Uncertainty regarding the direction of precipitation trends is also partly due to the strong influence of atmospheric river storms. Across California, a significant portion of annual precipitation (20-50%) comes from atmospheric rivers (AR) (Dettinger 2011). Individual storms make important contributions to overall annual precipitation across the state. In mountainous regions, atmospheric rivers interact with sharp elevational gradients, and strong orographic lift is a major driver of precipitation (Dettinger 2011). Dettinger (2011) noted that GCMs may not represent AR effects with precision.

The consequences of increasing precipitation volatility played out recently during a rapid swing between prolonged drought conditions (2012-16) and an unusually high number of atmospheric rivers during the winter of 2016-17, which caused major flood damage (Wang et al 2017). Both natural and human systems were challenged by the rapid shift between drought and flooding, a situation that is anticipated to occur more frequently in the future.

Drought

Drought results not just from low precipitation, but the combination of both warm and dry conditions (Diffenbaugh et al. 2015). The Southern California climate is characterized by very high interannual variability in precipitation, and single- and multi-year droughts are regular occurrences (Dettinger et al. 2011, Du et al. 2020). Regional changes occurring as a result of anthropogenic climate forcing, such as the likely shift towards less regular precipitation during the winter “wet season”, are likely to include increased occurrence and frequency of droughts. Drought occurrence and frequency are linked to global-scale cycling, such as periodic shifts in sea surface temperature anomalies in both the Pacific and Atlantic

Oceans (McCabe et al. 2004, Du et al. 2020). However, anthropogenic climate warming also influences the probability of co-occurring warm and dry conditions (Diffenbaugh et al. 2015).

Increases in temperature from anthropogenic warming will increase evaporative demand on a global scale, under even moderate emissions scenarios (Zhao and Dai, 2015). Globally, higher evaporative demand will increase drought levels by creating more frequent and persistent dry conditions (Naumann et al 2018, Prudhomme et al 2014). Over much of California, the moisture deficit is projected to increase, with consequences such as decreased soil moisture and higher baseline forest mortality (van Mantgem et al. 2009, Pierce et al. 2018). Importantly, forest water stress and tree susceptibility to mortality driven by fire, insects and disease, carbon starvation and xylem cavitation are all also higher where forest densities are high (Young et al. 2017, Restaino et al. 2019). While there is variability in the magnitude of evaporative change that is projected, the trend of increasing drought levels is consistent across models (Scheff and Frierson 2014, Zhao and Dai 2015).

Historical analysis indicates that drought has increased globally over many land areas since 1950, and more widespread, severe droughts are projected to occur in the next 30-90 years (Dai et al. 2013). Beyond these expected changes, much discussion is occurring around predictions of droughts more extreme than those found in the historical record. These are referred to as “global-change-type droughts” or “hotter droughts” and are expected to have major impacts on forests (Millar and Stephenson 2015). For example, a record-setting drought occurred in California between 2012-2016, with the most extreme measured historical values for lowest 12-month precipitation, highest annual temperature, and other drought indicators (Asner et al. 2016, Diffenbaugh et al. 2015). Paleoclimate data also suggest that the 2012-2016 event was the deepest drought in more than 1000 years in the central part of the State (Lund et al. 2018)

Analyses of forest drought stress indices project that for forests in the southwestern U.S., average drought stress is likely to be higher by 2050 than in the previous 1000 years (Williams et al 2013). Further out, some projections include severe extended drought in the American Southwest by the second half of this century (Cook et al. 2015). The concern around “hotter droughts” is that they may drive forest mortality beyond existing biological controls and resilience thresholds and lead to permanent forest loss (Millar and Stephenson 2015, Raffa et al. 2008).

Drought is a major driver of forest mortality (Dale et al. 2001). Allen et al. (2010) summarized 88 well-documented episodes of drought-induced tree mortality across the globe that occurred from 1970 to 2009, and an increasing percentage of published forest research is focused on drought mortality (Allen et al. 2010). The balance of evidence shows that forests are increasingly vulnerable to drought-induced mortality under warming temperatures (Allen et al. 2015).

The physiological mechanisms of tree mortality have been an active area of research for decades (Choat et al. 2018), with findings that tree mortality from drought is consistently associated with substantial loss of hydraulic function through cavitation, with carbon starvation playing a role in some cases (Adams et al. 2017, Anderegg et al 2016). The hydraulic systems of many tree species are closely adapted to the current environment, with narrow safety margins between average hydraulic condition and failure thresholds (Choat et al. 2012). It follows that phenotypic plasticity is important to resilience, and some degree of plasticity in traits is needed to maintain populations as site conditions change (Choat et al. 2018). For ponderosa pine, post-drought recovery has been shown to vary by site longitude, elevation,

and soil moisture, with this variability in recovery suggesting a limited degree of plasticity in responding to drought (Gazol et al. 2017).

The ability to predict forest mortality events is slowly improving, based on approaches that incorporate species-specific hydraulic measures, measures of forest structure, and climate variables (Venturas et al. 2021). Tree mortality has also been quantitatively associated with water stress, measured in terms of climatic water deficit (CWD, defined as cumulative evaporative demand that exceeds available water), and forest density, as trees in denser forests face increased competition for available water. During the California drought of 2012-2016, tree mortality increased by an order of magnitude over baseline levels and was associated with the combination of dry conditions and dense forest stands (Young et al. 2017). In that drought event, mortality of large ponderosa on dry sites was pronounced (Koontz et al. 2021). Water stress (CWD) has subsequently been implicated in historic (20th century) changes in forest structure and function across California (McIntyre et al. 2015).

Snowpack

Future snowfall and snowpack changes have been modeled for the Southern California mountains (Sun et al. 2016). Relative to a baseline period (1981-2000), ensemble-mean winter snowfall is projected to be 70% of the baseline by midcentury (2041-60), and further fall to 50% of baseline by end of century (2081-2100). Increased early snowmelt will further decrease snowpack levels throughout the winter season. By 2060, earlier spring snowmelt is projected to shift the first snowpack-free date 1-3 weeks earlier relative to baseline, especially at lower and middle montane elevations (Sun et al. 2016). Notably, earlier snow-free days were not projected for the highest elevations. Lower levels of water storage in snowpack translate to decreased soil moisture, as winter water runoff increases and the springtime period for snow to slowly melt and be absorbed into the soil ends early.

Ozone and Other Atmospheric Pollution

Nitrogen deposition and ozone pollution from fossil fuel combustion constitute another threat to Southern California forests. Ozone pollution impacts were first documented in the San Bernardino Mountains in the 1950s (Ohmart 1980). Since then, regional monitoring indicates a pollution gradient that runs from west (most pollution) to east (less pollution) along the Transverse Range (Fenn et al., 2008, Grulke et al. 2009). For example, empirical measures of annual N deposition in the San Bernardino Mtns from the early 2000s ranged from 6.1 to 71.1 kg of nitrogen over one hectare per year, increasing from east to west (Fenn et al. 2008). Pollution load analyses show that in mixed conifer forest, the leaching of pollution into streams (reducing water quality) and decreases in fine root biomass both occur at approximately 17 kg of nitrogen over one hectare per year, while impacts to sensitive species in the community, such as lichens, begin at 3.1 kg of nitrogen over one hectare per year (Fenn 2008, 2010).

Ozone and N pollution impact many aspects of tree health and regional forest decline. N deposition can enhance productivity, thereby accelerating stand densification and fuels accumulation, as well as invasion by annual grasses and herbs (Allen et al. 2007, Fog 1988). Fertilization effects from N deposition favor shoot over root growth allocation (Haynes and Gower, 1995, Gower et al. 1995). Decreased root biomass has been measured at more polluted sites (Grulke et al. 1998). In conifer forests, N deposition also stimulates new foliar growth and premature needle loss, resulting in higher leaf turnover (Grulke et al. 2009). On the forest floor, ozone and N deposition increase the amount of leaf and branch litter and retard litter decomposition rates. Annual litter accumulation at more polluted montane forest sites in the

San Bernardino Mountains was 50-125% greater than at similar, but less polluted sites (Grulke et al. 2009). This has obvious feedbacks into fire hazard and risk.

Additionally, ozone pollution can magnify drought effects. Ozone damages foliar tissues, which require repair (Matyssek and Sandermann, 2003) and draw on the tree's carbohydrate stores. Elevated ozone also interferes with photosynthesis and transpiration, making the tradeoff between CO₂ uptake and water loss through leaf stomata less efficient. Water loss through the canopy increases, but with less fine root mass to replace the ongoing water loss, the level of drought stress increases (Grulke et al. 2009).

Increasing the level of hydraulic stress experienced by trees living close to environmental limits, or perhaps already experiencing cavitation damage due to external drought conditions, may further boost forest mortality rates. Considering all of the demonstrated and potential feedbacks, ozone and nitrogen deposition should be considered important contributing factors to forest decline in Southern California.

Insect and Fungal Agents

Montane forest communities support various insect and fungal species that act as disturbance agents (Raffa et al. 2008). Bark beetles are major insect agents affecting conifers in Southern California montane forests and include but are not limited to western, Jeffrey, and mountain pine beetles (*Dendroctonus brevicomis*, *D. jeffreyi*, and *D. ponderosae*), and pine engraver beetles (*Ips* spp.), as well as fir engraver beetles (especially *Scolytus ventralis*) (Minnich 2007). Their disturbance effects in forests may be widespread or host-specific, with variable duration and severity (Krawchuck et al 2020). In a healthy forest ecosystem, bark beetles target stressed and dying trees; providing important functions such as mycorrhizal associations, symbiotic endophytes, removing decadent trees, opening up closed overstory canopies, recycling nutrients into soil, and contributing to heterogeneity in forest stands. Bark beetles have a widespread association with fungi that act as either nutrient sources for developing larvae or as antagonists to host defenses. Some fungal associates are symbiotic and carried in specialized structures called mycangia, such as blackstain fungi (*Leptographium wagneri*) that lead to black stain root diseases (Minnich 2007, Minnich et al. 2016, Bennett et al. 2021). Other fungal associates such as blue stain fungi (*Ophiostoma* and *Grosmannia* spp.) can be carried on the body surface of bark beetles and aid in overcoming tree defenses (Lieutier 2002). Other important fungal agents include annosus (*Heterobasidion irregulare* and *H. occidentale* on conifer and fir/spruce respectively), *Armillaria* species that infect the root system of both conifers and hardwood, but especially oak in Southern California (Baumgartner & Rizzo, 2001; Downer & Lacan, 2020). Outbreaks of insect and fungal disturbance agents are limited by coevolved biological controls at a range of spatial scales, such as host defenses, predators and competitors, and host depletion (Raffa et al. 2008). Interactions between many fungal and insect agents are important but generally imperfectly understood (Held et al., 2021).

Bark beetles are one of the most damaging biotic threats to conifer forests, and the mechanisms of bark beetle attack and tree defenses are highly developed in response to each other (Lieutier, 2002). During a bark beetle attack, trees need to divert resources from physiological processes such as photosynthesis and growth and reallocate energy to pre-existing and inducible defenses (Lieutier 2002). Due to an impressive chemical communication system, bark beetles can attack en masse to exhaust the energy reserves of host tree through the physical damage of gallery excavation and the inoculation of fungal pathogens (Lieutier 2002, Raffa et al. 2001). When mass aggregations happen, bark beetle populations can grow exponentially and allow them to overcome the defenses of healthy trees, leading to outbreaks. Generally, most trees have sufficient vigor to repel beetle attacks so that forest-level impacts remain low.

Under drought conditions and increased temperatures, trees must put more energy towards survival, lessening defense capabilities (Herms 1992; Raffa et al. 2005, Raffa et al. 2008; Ghosh et al. 2022) against insect and fungal disturbance agents. Water-stressed trees in particular have lower energy reserves and diminished production of secondary defense compounds (Anderegg et al 2015, Raffa et al 2008). Further studies reveal that the more severe the drought, the greater the bark beetle associated mortality (Creeden et al. 2014, Kolb et al. 2016) as a result of weakened trees and increased fungal growth (Bentz et al. 2010). An example of the impacts of prolonged drought occurred after the hot, multi-year drought that lasted from 2012 to 2016. Over 100 million trees were lost due to bark beetle activity that most severely impacted the central and southern Sierra Nevada in 2015-2016 (Fettig et al. 2019). The widespread occurrence of several major bark beetle outbreak events across western North America in the past 20 years suggests that anthropogenic impacts on climate such as increased temperatures and changing precipitation regimes may be exceeding natural controls (Kolb et al. 2016) leading to an increase of landscape level beetle caused mortality (Bentz et al. 2010). Furthermore, as climate warming progresses, upward elevational and latitudinal shifts of insect populations beyond current geographic climatic barriers are anticipated (Bentz et al. 2016). For example, mountain pine beetles are expanding into Southern California (Bentz et al. 2010). While tree mortality has beneficial ecological effects at moderate levels, the increased potential for climate driven susceptibility to insects and diseases places them among the threat factors of greatest concern.

Invasive species

Nonnative Insects - Gold spotted oak borer

Starting in the early 2000s, oak mortality was detected in San Diego County in an expanding area centered on the Laguna and Cuyamaca Mountains. While mortality was originally attributed to drought, in 2008 it was connected to a non-native woodboring beetle, the Goldspotted Oak Borer (*Agrilus auroguttatus*, Coleman and Seybold 2008). By that time the area of affected oaks had grown to approximately 16,000 acres (USDA Forest Service, Pacific Southwest Region, Forest Health Monitoring, 2009). Extensive efforts followed to definitively establish species status (Hespenheide and Bellamy 2009, Hespenheide et al. 2011, Coleman et al. 2012b), and to identify the origin population in the mountains of southeast Arizona, which are approximately 415 miles distant from the apparent introduction site (Lopez et al 2014). The mechanism of introduction was presumed to be through the transportation of firewood into the region, identifying GSOB as an intracontinental invasive species (Coleman and Seybold 2011). At the present time, 20 years after the estimated initial introduction, the affected area has spread beyond San Diego County to include Los Angeles, Orange, Riverside, and San Bernardino Counties (California Forest Pest Council 2023).

In contrast to disease agents that may weaken individual trees but are not primary agents of mortality, GSOB causes mortality even in the absence of other insect and fungal agents. Larvae tunnel through the vascular tissues of the tree disrupting the translocation of water, leading to dieback and eventual mortality (Coleman and Seybold 2016). In the crown, premature dieback and crown thinning worsens progressively, although trees may survive for 6-10 years before mortality occurs (Hishinuma et al. 2011; Hishinuma, personal communication).

Greater injury effects in the introduced range compared to the GSOB home range suggest that the affected species in Southern California are naïve hosts (Coleman and Seybold 2011) with no evolved defenses against the insect. GSOB is found in several oak species but causes 80-90% mortality in the

regional red oak species (coast live oak, *Quercus agrifolia*, California black oak, *Q. kelloggii*). Intermediate (~60%) mortality occurs in *Q. chrysolepis*, a goldencup oak. Infestation— but not mortality— has been observed in white oaks (*Q. engelmannii*) (Coleman et al 2012a).

Larger tree size (greater than 5 in diameter at breast height) is a key susceptibility factor, and trees above 15 in dbh are at high risk (Coleman and Seybold 2016). Drought stress does not increase the risk of infestation (Coleman et al. 2011). Although the deep root systems of old growth oaks minimize their drought exposure relative to adjacent, smaller oaks, old growth oaks are particularly susceptible to GSOB injury (Coleman et al. 2011).

The most common locations of new infestations are areas where firewood is stored and/or burned; areas such as campgrounds, recreational areas, and communities where firewood is a predominant source of supplemental heat. For this reason, the movement of firewood from infested areas to uninfested areas must be strongly discouraged. Chemical treatments of both systemic and contact insecticides have proven effective at protecting uninfested and lightly infested trees in infested areas and areas adjacent to infested areas (Coleman et al. 2016; Coleman et al. 2017); however, these treatments require annual tree-by-tree application. Forest scientists are very concerned with how infestation dynamics are likely to play out once GSOB spreads northwards into the extensive hardwood belts of the Sierra Nevada and Coast Ranges. The combination of naïve and vulnerable red oak hosts along with beetle preference for larger trees raises the possibility of widespread mortality in California's old growth oaks.

Nonnative Plant Species

Postfire conditions are suitable for nonnative species introduction and establishment. Nonnative grasses and forbs occur after fire in localized locations, often as a result of anthropogenic disturbance. At montane elevations, the primary annual grass species of concern is cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*), with localized areas of invasion. In recent years, there have also been anecdotal observations of riggut brome (*Bromus diandrus*) occurring at higher elevations than expected. Lacking persistent seedbanks, these species need the opening of a fire disturbance to spread and reduced competition from native species to increase (Franklin 2010). Invasive forb species such as tecolote (*Centaurea melitensis*) and mustards (e.g. *Sisymbrium sp.*), follow the annual grasses. While nonnative cover increases over the first 2-4 years, cover is likely to decrease in subsequent years due to competition with recovering native species (Franklin 2010, Keeley et al 1981). These species provide flashy fuels that have the potential to interfere with historic fire regimes by increasing the continuity of surface fuels (Fusco et al. 2019).

Regarding the widespread introduction of exotic annual grasses and forbs such as *Bromus sp.*, *Avena sp.*, and others, historical records are spottier for montane areas compared to lower elevations. While it is well documented that introduced species were dominant in grasslands at lower elevations by the early 19th century (D'Antonio et al. 2007), the timing of invasion and subsequent dominance has been more variable in montane areas. Local disturbance patterns, including the timing of development, logging, and other human pressures influence whether invasives have successfully established in the understory.

The Need for a Regional Strategy

The Scope of the Problem

How much fuel treatment is needed? The California Spotted Owl Conservation Strategy (USDA 2019) sums up the current estimates for landscape-scale forest treatment:

“Treating more than 20 percent of the landscape with strategic treatments can reduce modeled fire size and behavior (Collins and Skinner 2014), but effectively influencing ecosystem function, especially where treatment patterns are limited by management constraints, requires restoring, treating, or both more than 40 percent of the area at the landscape scale (Lydersen et al. 2017). At a mid-scale (1,000s to 10,000s of acres), roughly 25 to 60 percent of the area may need to be treated to influence fire severity (Lydersen et al. 2017), and at a patch/stand scale, more treatment may be necessary to influence fire severity (50 to 75 percent at the scale of 500 acres; Lydersen et al. 2017). Even more treatment for restoration may be required under future climate regimes (Westerling et al. 2016).”

While this CASPO strategy did not include Southern California, similar values are expected. Given an estimated 660,000 acres of montane forest in Southern California, this would translate to an approximate target of 132,000 acres of fuel treatments to reduce fire size and behavior. More comprehensive restoration of ecosystem function, such as landscape-scale restoration of the frequent fire regime, would translate to an approximate target of 264,000 acres overall. The location of these treatments will depend on biophysical factors such as elevation and topographical position as well as existing plant community types. Restoration of more open and heterogeneous forest structure will need to focus on established forest areas within the montane region and be mindful of the different management requirements of community types within or adjacent to the montane forest region including montane chaparral, pinyon-juniper woodland, meadows, and riparian and aquatic ecosystems.

Challenges and Barriers to Implementation

It is important to acknowledge that the current pace and scale of forest treatments is likely not sufficient to achieve forest persistence or community preparedness at the landscape scale across Southern California’s forests. This is due to a combination of factors, including policies, priorities, a well-established culture of fire suppression (Schultz et al. 2019), a need for greater community engagement and buy-in, and a lack of adequate workforce and economic opportunities to carry out the work at the necessary scale. Accordingly, achieving resilience in the region’s forested systems means adapting both our ecological and social systems, including policies, processes, and management. Therefore, taking stock of both the opportunities and barriers to collaborative action are an important first step to effective conservation action.

To better understand the specific challenges to increasing the resilience of Southern California’s montane forests, we asked forest management practitioners— including planners, fire managers, foresters, ecologists, and more— about their experiences through a peer-reviewed questionnaire. A draft of the questionnaire was reviewed by a social scientist who provided feedback and it went through the review and approval process by San Diego State University’s Institutional Review Board (IRB). We also conducted cognitive interviews with three individuals to refine the questionnaire prior to broad distribution

across the region. The information gathered from the questionnaire has informed and shaped the development of the conservation plan and the adaptation strategies highlighted in the plan.

Representatives from across the region and from a range of organizations completed the questionnaire, providing 63 responses (Figure 1). The majority of respondents had a background in fire and fuels management (n=37), forestry (n=32), ecology or biology (n=24), and planning (n=16). The vast majority had experience with project planning (n=49) and implementation (n=50). Most practitioners who completed the questionnaire also had experience in project monitoring, fund acquisition, contracting, advising, or other aspects of regulatory compliance. We asked respondents about the types of projects they had experience with and most had worked on fuels reduction (n=54), forest health (n=48), restoration or reforestation (n=41), and/or prescribed fire (n=14) projects.

FIGURE 1. Geographic (left panel) and organizational (right panel) breakdowns of practitioner questionnaire respondents. Percentages are out of a total of 63 responses.

To understand how to best integrate strategies into the conservation plan that would help address challenges and barriers to action, we asked practitioners to identify the top three factors that posed the biggest challenges to completing planning and implementation of forest management projects in Southern California. Staff capacity, regulatory compliance, and funding availability were identified as top challenges for both planning and implementation (Figure 2). Competing organizational priorities or leadership support were identified as an additional challenge for project planning. In response to an open-ended question about the greatest needs practitioners face in trying to advance forest treatments, respondents offered input such as: “Time, Talent, Treasury”; cross-agency coordination, cooperation, and partnerships; streamlining of regulatory processes; pathways to train and maintain staff and contractor workforce; and increased public education and support.

FIGURE 2. Top challenges in forest project planning (top panel) and implementation (bottom panel) identified by practitioners responding to the questionnaire on forest management experiences. Respondents were able to select up to three challenges.

Challenges in Designated Wilderness

FIGURE 3. San Gorgonio Wilderness in 2024, four years after the Apple Fire.

Prior to 2020, the San Gorgonio Wilderness supported old growth montane forest. The wilderness was severely burned in the Apple Fire, one of several large fires in Southern California during the 2020 fire season (Figure 3). The photo was taken in 2024, looking towards the south face of Mount San Gorgonio, the highest peak in Southern California (11,503 ft.) The existing wilderness boundary encompasses both the south and north faces of Mt. San Gorgonio. Unfortunately, the north face of the mountain also previously experienced high-severity fire, during the 2015 Lake Fire. Within the wilderness area, postfire regeneration surveys in large high severity burn patches revealed no seedling recruitment eight years following the Lake Fire. In the case of the Apple Fire, managers were somewhat relieved to note a linear stand of surviving trees (visible in the photo); these may serve to reseed downslope portions of the wilderness. However, large portions of the prefire conifer forest currently lack signs of natural tree regeneration and may simply reset to shrub-dominated vegetation communities.

Across Southern California, designated wilderness areas contain 578 square miles (370,000 acres) of montane forest. Of that forest area, nearly 60% has burned since 2005, much of it at high severity due to overly dense forest structure and compounding factors such as extreme weather conditions. In addition, most of the remaining forest area (~28%) has not experienced fire in more than 80 years, since the early 1940s. This remaining unburned montane forest has an elevated vulnerability to high severity fire. Management in designated wilderness is subject to restrictions on mechanized equipment and limited or no road access, limiting both pre-fire management (such as thinning and prescribed fire) and postfire restoration. The need for more active management in wilderness, in terms of reforestation and restoration of the natural fire regime, has been the topic of much discussion recently ([Center for Public Lands Story Map](#)):

- Reintroduction of Fire into Wilderness. Constraints on the reintroduction of fire into wilderness resemble those outlined for montane forest more generally. The Land Management Plans for the National Forests in Southern California require full suppression of all wildland fires. Due to current forest conditions and fuel loading levels, the potential for catastrophic fire damage to

communities and infrastructure is high. Managers have interest in deploying prescribed fire, but it is rarely used in designated wilderness. A 2023 effort by Center for Public Lands at Western Colorado University leveraged manager input to identify barriers and opportunities for fire management in wilderness. The resulting product resembles a “menu” of management options with 21 opportunities to overcome barriers to prescribed fire in wilderness, organized under eight themes (Center for Public Lands 2023). The menu format is similar in style and use to the menu of climate-adapted management options in Appendix B of this strategy.

- Postfire reforestation in wilderness has not been conducted to date in California. Wilderness is left to recover without intervention, although the likelihood of successful forest regeneration remains low when a large proportion of the forest area experiences high severity fire. Most conifer species produce heavy seeds with limited potential for dispersal. When the size of high severity patches is large, the surviving trees may not maintain dominance in the recovering plant community, and also may not be able to generate the quantity of viable seed needed to support robust regeneration.

Actions intended to either recover from, or prevent, the impacts of a fire in wilderness need to be assessed in terms of their net impact to wilderness character. Most administrative actions in wilderness are reasonably interpreted as trammeling (manipulating the natural environment), and might involve the introduction of development (e.g., use of motorized equipment), both of which are generally prohibited in wilderness areas. However, if managers can make an argument that the impacts to wilderness character of trammeling and/or development are offset or even exceeded by the *enhancement* of the Natural character of the wilderness (one of 5 components of wilderness character specified by the Wilderness Act), then the administrative action can be authorized. This argument is articulated in a document called a Minimum Requirements Analysis Framework (MRAF). Factors such as historic vegetation types, historic fire return interval, and preventing the introduction and spread of invasive species are all contributors to the Natural character of a wilderness area. Administrative actions meant to enhance or protect these or similar natural factors could potentially be authorized as long as the related impacts from trammeling and/or introducing development into the wilderness were short-term, indiscernible, and/or limited in scope.

Thoughtful development of strong supporting rationale is needed to enable the implementation of active management such as prescribed fire and reforestation in wilderness. Landres et al (2020) developed a framework based on a list of unbiased questions (scientific, legal, and ethical) to support project-level planning and analysis. This type of approach supports case-by-case evaluation of specific wilderness situations and formulation of management approaches consistent with the intent of the Wilderness Act. Managers are encouraged to explore approaches like this to protect the natural character of wilderness.

Introduction to the Strategy

Purpose of the Strategy

This Conservation Strategy has been designed as a roadmap for increasing the resilience, sustainability, and persistence of Southern California's montane forests. By identifying climate-informed implementation actions, this strategy will support planning and management efforts to enhance forest health and resilience and safeguard the local communities that live in and benefit from these forests. The strategy is also intended to build a community of practice by promoting collaborative action and fostering the development of partnerships to improve forest resilience.

Guiding Principles

We provide a foundation of guiding principles to support practitioners as they consider questions about implementation of the conservation strategy. These guiding principles speak to the intent of the conservation strategy to support ecological function through strategic management.

Principle 1. Promote and restore ecological processes that support key ecosystem services for the benefit of local communities and ecosystems.

This conservation strategy supports both the natural and the cultural benefits that forests provide. These forests are broadly valued for a rich suite of ecosystem services including recreational opportunities, cultural uses, provision of water and habitat, carbon storage, and biodiversity, among others. Supporting the ecological requirements of culturally important species is another aspect of this strategy, for the purpose of enabling sustained (or increased) levels of gathering and utilization.

Principle 2. Build ecological and community resilience and adapt to agents of change, including climate and associated disturbances.

Integrating climate adaptation strategies into forest management planning and practice is critical for successfully responding to changing conditions (Stein et al. 2013). Adaptation is intended to reduce the vulnerability of systems to the effects of climate change by altering behaviors, actions, and decisions in response to observed impacts or in preparation for projected future change (Smit et al. 2000). This approach has demonstrated effectiveness in reducing risk and vulnerability levels and building resilience into both natural resources and management systems (Owen 2020).

The process of incorporating climate adaptation into forest management is not a separate activity from standard practices. Instead, it is best accomplished by considering climate impacts throughout the planning, implementation, and evaluation cycle, so that both decision-making processes and management actions may be adjusted along the way.

Principle 3. Maintain habitat quality and connectivity through acquisitions and management activities, prioritizing connections that cross land ownership boundaries and support species' movement and adaptation to dynamic conditions (i.e., seasonal to interannual changes in habitat).

Fluxes of resources within ecosystems are dynamic through both space and time, as ecosystems experience seasonal cycles and disturbance processes. As the communities in ecosystems undergo

directional changes in climate, management to maintain existing relationships can be strengthened by considering how to create or maintain spatial connections, such as corridors for dispersal, as well as temporal connections, such as matching the phenology of resource provision and utilization.

Principle 4. Use reference forest conditions to guide management, but recognize that changing conditions may produce novel forest composition, structure, and functions.

Climate-adapted management responds to observed impacts or prepares for projected future change, rather than responding to previous conditions that no longer exist or are not likely to persist. Integrating a clear understanding of how factors such as land use and fire suppression altered forest structure will help to adjust management goals appropriately. Integrating climate considerations also helps to ensure effective use of management staff and funding.

How to use the Conservation Strategy

Leaning into the diversity of these lands and wide range of ownerships, the Southern Montane Forest Project focuses on supporting the processes of planning and implementation rather than attempting to apply a uniform set of prescriptive management strategies to all lands. This approach supports region-wide efforts to increase the pace and scale of forest treatments and prioritizes key portions of the landscape. This Conservation Strategy recommends, supports, and facilitates the use of three processes by managers.

1. Prioritize Forest Resilience Projects at Landscape-Scale. The first component of the conservation strategy is a customized decision framework for supporting landscape-scale project delineation and prioritization. Prioritization is a major component of both Federal and State efforts to increase the pace and scale of treatments. The Southern Montane Forests Framework is climate-adapted and aligned with the best-available science in Southern California. Conducting landscape-scale prioritization planning will help managers to maintain flexibility and enable rapid management response during unpredictable funding cycles.

2. Adapt for Climate Stressors at Project Level. This strategy recommends increased use of the Adaptation Workbook approach for project-scale planning (Janowiak et al. 2022). The Adaptation Workbook leads users through a process to evaluate management goals and objectives relative to anticipated climate impacts. It addresses both challenges and opportunities posed by climate change, and asks managers to consider how management tactics should be modified to address climate impacts. Strategy section 2 outlines the steps of the Adaptation Workbook process and provides a case study. A regionally relevant Adaptation Menu (based on the CA Climate Hub's Forest Adaptation Strategies Menu) is also provided to guide managers through their options for forest management after project delineation and prioritization (Appendix B). This Menu summarizes the best management tactics for Southern California's forests. In many cases the most important types of treatments for resilience to stressors will not be unfamiliar. Reintroducing fire and managing the understory will frequently be the most recommended management approaches. However, the menu should also be used to consider more transformative alternatives (e.g. assisted migration) in locations experiencing high levels of exposure to climate and disturbances.

3. Consider Context in Reforestation. The third component of the strategy is focused on post-fire landscapes. After fire, the Postfire Restoration Framework (Meyer et al, 2021) can assist in the identification of a portfolio of priority sites and restoration projects. The framework can be applied to any postfire landscape of interest and allows flexibility with respect to management priorities and goals. The framework emphasizes analysis of the burned area within both climate and habitat contexts. The context of anticipated future climate conditions puts necessary sideboards on reforestation projects. Often, the best approach will be to prioritize planting in locations of climate refugia and slower warming over more exposed locations. The habitat-focused context includes consideration of ecological attributes such as regional native biodiversity and habitat connectivity. This approach prioritizes the reforestation of mature native forest stands, with their higher species and structural diversity, over simpler and younger plantation stands.

The postfire reforestation framework also emphasizes long-term ecosystem integrity and function through incorporation of natural range of variability (NRV) into the analysis flow. In fire-adapted forests, where the process of fire plays a central role in maintaining forest condition, locations where fire effects are positive should be considered separately from the locations where fire effects were outside the natural range of variability.

Case Studies. In the sections that follow, each of the three processes is described in detail. Each process is then illustrated through a regional case study example of regional practitioners applying the process to a specific project. The case studies highlight lessons learned and features of each process that practitioners found to be particularly useful.

1. Prioritize Forest Resilience Projects at Landscape-Scale

The first component of the strategy is a customized decision framework that supports landscape-wide project prioritization. The Southern Montane Forests Framework informs landscape-scale prioritization based on exposure to climate change and other key mappable factors. In montane forest, the framework has three layers of input, utilizing data layers that represent exposure to threats, priority assets, and vulnerabilities (Figure 4). The exposure layer is a data product covering the full extent of montane forest across Southern California. The data for priority assets and vulnerabilities are identified by manager input via an interactive workshop format. Priority assets and vulnerabilities are evaluated at subregional scale, for example by county.

Three key processes

FIGURE 4. Three key processes are quantified in the prioritization framework to produce scores for the entire landscape.

Step 1. Refugia

The first layer evaluates exposure to stressors that we have little ability to change in the short term. This framework has a foundation in the domains of refugia concept developed for coastal Southern California, a landscape-scale approach to identify areas with lower exposure to multiple stressors (Rojas et al. 2021). Refugia are defined as portions of the landscape with lower levels of exposure to multiple stressors, including climate (Morelli et al. 2020). In the context of rapid climate change, these are locations that are likely to change more slowly, providing time and space for both species' persistence and adaptation. Refugia can allow some species to resist change farther into the future and supports increased resilience for others. Here, the approach is extended to montane forests, with a focus on enabling prioritization planning.

Three domains define montane forest refugia. The first domain is climate, represented as the exposure resulting from extreme events, and takes both the frequency and the intensity of extreme events into account. The two factors that are modeled are change in aridity, which is represented by Climate Water Deficit (CWD), and increase in frequency of prolonged drought. The second domain is wildfire, which is represented by fire intensity resulting from interaction of topographic landscape position, aspect, and Santa Ana winds. The final domain is human pressure, which is modeled as the proximity and abundance of impervious surface. This acts as a proxy for human disturbance. These three domains (climate, wildfire, human pressure) are overlaid to identify areas where exposure is low relative to the region as a whole. This first layer (yellow arrow, Figure 4) has already been developed, and is meant to be used in the framework as a fixed input across the entire modeled area of montane forest extent (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5. The refugia layer developed for Southern California montane forests. The extent is based on ecoregions developed by U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, and includes the Level III Southern California Mountains ecoregion plus level IV ecoregions for the Tehachapi and Santa Ana Mountains.

Step 2: Vulnerabilities

The second layer (blue arrow, Figure 4) represents vulnerabilities, which is defined as a weakness in the protection of an asset. The weakness creates a vulnerability to threats, the disturbances or stressors that could destroy valued assets. Common forest threats include uncharacteristic high severity wildfire, prolonged severe drought, and outbreaks of forest insects/diseases. Vulnerabilities have the potential to be changed or improved in the short term through management action, delineating a key difference from the stressors represented in the fixed refugia layer. Examples of common vulnerabilities include:

- High forest stand density
- Abundant surface fuels
- Ignition hotspots such as roadways.
- Departure from historical fire regime
- Stand composition
- High levels of human access and use
- Sources of pests, pathogens, or non-native species
- Existing management direction

This layer has not been developed for the entire region, but rather requires workshop-based input from managers and practitioners at a sub-regional scale. The sub-regional approach recognizes the size and diversity of the region, and allows managers the ability to choose vulnerability and priority factors that matter the most for their lands. Currently the prioritization framework has been conducted twice, for the San Bernardino Mtns and the mountain ranges of San Diego County. Future engagements will conduct the process for the San Gabriel Mtns and for the northwestern mountain ranges.

In the analytical flow, the composite vulnerability data is overlaid on the climate refugia map to identify portions of the landscape where climate refugial capacity is high, but where some aspects of condition leave the forest vulnerable to threats and stressors. Since vulnerability is defined as having the potential to be improved through management action, this analysis identifies those portions of the forest where prioritizing and implementing management action now should enable the retention of forest cover into the future. All of the areas identified as having this combination of refugial capacity and vulnerability should be prioritized for management.

Step 3: Priority Values

The third layer (orange arrow, Figure 4) also requires workshop-based input from managers and practitioners at a sub-regional scale. It represents priority assets, further defined as areas of ecological, cultural, or ecosystem service values. The priority assets can include natural and human values such as:

- Habitat connectivity
- Protected areas
- Culturally important sites or resources
- Ecosystem service values (water provision, carbon storage, biodiversity, etc.)
- Wildland Urban Interface
- Transportation corridors
- Community preparedness
- Scenic values
- Priority species/habitats
- Utility infrastructure

The act of prioritization requires the localized identification of top priority assets and vulnerabilities rather than the creation of exhaustive sets of inputs. Both priority assets and vulnerabilities must be mappable and supported by accurate existing data in order to create a landscape-level map product.

Overlaying the priority values with the locations identified in Step 2 will enable the creation of a phasing plan. While all of the acres identified in step 2 should be prioritized for management, some areas should be treated in the short-term, while other areas may be addressed over longer time frames.

Turning back to the questionnaire for practitioners, we asked managers and practitioners for their insights into what types of data layers they find most useful for prioritizing locations or designing forest management projects in Southern California's montane forests (Figure 6). Managers identified vulnerabilities as key. For example, 67% of respondents identified existing stand density as a critical data input, the highest level of agreement measured for any factor. Managers asked for data that identifies areas with the greatest vulnerability to multiple threats, and areas of high exposure to climate impacts.

Data indicating current degree of departure in fire return interval and forest pest/pathogen risk also rated highly in practitioner responses.

FIGURE 6. Top data needs for prioritizing management locations or designing forest projects, identified by practitioners. Respondents were able to select up to four answers.

In line with these responses, the design of the framework is intended to assist managers in focusing on a select set of the most informative factors across project areas, and to effectively leverage information to guide management direction. Narrowing the set of modeled factors (priority assets and vulnerabilities) to a short list supports the development of a robust yet accessible map that can guide landscape and project planning. Conducting the selection exercise as a collaborative workshop ensures that local values, concerns, and knowledge are represented. To this end, the Southern Montane Forests Project is supporting an interactive series of workshops with managers representing subregions of Southern California. The structure is designed to recognize the need to balance multiple values across the landscape, and to adjust the prioritization based on the specific part of the landscape.

The output is a customized prioritization map at region to sub-region scale that shows 1) areas with the greatest need for management implementation and 2) locations that support similar conditions and should be considered together during management planning. This is the product that the partnership takes away from the workshop, and can be used to support both priority planning and implementation. See Figures 8 and 9 in the case study for example map products.

The spatial data layers were composited using simple arithmetic expressions on rescaled raster data. Variables were put through a linear transformation based on the existing distribution for the geographic extent of interest.

FIGURE 7. Decision framework products can be linked to climate-adapted management strategies in the Adaptation Menu.

The map can also be linked to the management recommendations in the Adaptation Menu provided in Appendix B (Figure 7). The selection of appropriate management tactics will vary across sites. For example, in a site with good refugial capacity and high priority values and relatively low vulnerability, but perhaps not enough fire, the management focus could be on maintenance prescribed burns to resist future change.

In sites projected to undergo further warming and increased drought, with higher levels of vulnerability and moderate priority level, management could instead focus on accommodating some change, for example encouraging growth of well-adapted species but seeking to maintain forest cover. By contrast, in a site with low refugial capacity, high vulnerability and moderate priority level, it could be best to facilitate a more significant species transition.

Case study of the Decision Framework in Practice: Headwaters Resiliency Partnership Workshop

The Headwaters Resiliency Partnership is a collaborative in San Bernardino County, including major land managers (U.S. Forest Service), regional agencies (San Bernardino Valley Municipal Water District, Inland Empire Resource Conservation District), research institutions (CSU San Bernardino), and other interested entities. The HRP area of interest includes watersheds in both the San Bernardino and San Jacinto mountain ranges, as these are major water sources for the large urban population at lower elevations. The goals of the workshop, which was held in April 2023, were to:

1. Advance forest planning by focusing on montane forest area across the HRP area

2. Strategically narrow the list of vulnerabilities and priority assets in montane forest areas of the HRP through collaborative discussions.
3. Pilot use of the structured decision framework developed by Southern Montane Forests Project

Facilitators from the Southern Montane Forest Project guided group discussion and linked the discussions to the Southern Montane Forests Framework. After reviewing definitions for threats, vulnerabilities, and priority assets, the group began by focusing on place-based concerns and priority assets. They were prompted to consider the factors behind their place-based concerns, and what threats/vulnerabilities or assets come to mind first when deciding what areas should be prioritized for treatment. The group shared out regional places and assets and articulated their reasons for concern.

The group then moved to two stations where they brainstormed a list of 1) critical threats/vulnerabilities and 2) priority assets across the partnership area. Both stations focused on identifying mappable factors. During a break, the facilitators summarized the ideas from the prior exercise into a list of approximately 15 high-level factors for each of the two stations (threats/vulnerabilities and assets). The group then reconvened to consider the summarized list with an opportunity to ask questions and provide comments. To further highlight the most important threats/vulnerabilities and assets, participants were asked to select their top three factors in each category. The voting identified the factors for inclusion in the spatial analysis, as shown in Table 2. This consensus-based approach allowed the group to collectively identify the factors that “rose to the top” for the most participants, illustrating where there was common ground from which to move forward as a community of practice.

TABLE 2. Factors for inclusion in the spatial prioritization product for the Headwaters Resiliency Partnership

Vulnerability	Variable(s)
Fuels	Total down wood in tons/acre
Stand density	Live trees per acre (>6" DBH); Stand Density Index
Fire return interval departure	pFRID (% departure from fire return interval since 1907)
Ignitions	Ignitions (1992-2020)
Human pressure	trail density
Priority Asset	Variable(s)
Watershed/water supply	Runoff and recharge
Human communities	Wildland Urban Interface
Sensitive species	TE occurrences and TE critical habitat (including CA Spotted Owl)
Recreation facilities/uses	Recreation areas, open space, special recreation areas, recreation sites

The final session focused on a group discussion of the projects, activities, and partnerships needed to be initiated or developed further. The group was also asked to summarize any missing data still needed to make decisions or support prioritization and project design.

After the workshop, the facilitators identified high-quality data products to represent the priority assets and vulnerabilities identified by HRP partners, and developed workshop products, including a landscape-scale prioritization map of ranked treatment areas in montane forest. This mapped product was provided back to the participants to support their needs to justify projects and funding with quantitative evidence (Figure 8).

FIGURE 8. The analytical results for the Headwaters Resiliency Partnership focus on locations with high refugial capacity, where the future capacity to support forest is relatively high plus relatively high vulnerability scores. A boundary line for National Forest lands (San Bernardino NF, or BDF) is provided for reference.

A 2-page written summary compiled the methods and results of the analysis, focusing on locations with high refugial capacity, where the future capacity to support forest is relatively high AND with relatively high vulnerability scores. These locations were considered to be treatable, where forest has a relatively high likelihood of persisting into the future as long as risk factors are reduced and managed successfully. This approach identified approximately 20% of the landscape extent (~250,000 acres) in this case study as meeting both refugial and vulnerability criteria. These acres were subsequently ranked for priority treatment in a future project with four phases (Phases 1-4) according to the composited value of all of the selected priority asset layers (Figure 9). This phasing approach is meant to emphasize that all of the areas in the mapping product are important to include in eventual treatment, but that some of the areas should be treated on a shorter, more immediate time frame. This approach should fit intuitively with management cycles focused on the availability of current year funding versus future year funding.

FIGURE 9. The final product mapped the potential locations for prioritized treatment in a future project with four phases (Phases 1-4). A boundary line for National Forest lands (San Bernardino NF, or BDF) is provided for reference.

2. Adapt for Climate Stressors at Project Level

By considering the potential impacts, challenges, and opportunities from a changing climate on a project-by-project basis, managers can identify specific management options for climate adaptation that are compatible with project objectives. Implementing these actions will produce improved project outcomes that meet management objectives while enabling the managed ecosystem to cope with stressors and adapt to changing conditions with greater resilience. Given the undeniable links between drought, disease, and fire in this region, project-level integration of climate adaptation into project design is necessary to support forest resilience into the future.

To this end, we recommend routine use of “A Quick Guide to Adaptation Planning for Natural Resource Professionals” developed by the Northern Institute of Applied Climate Science (Janowiak et al., 2022). The Quick Guide is a 5-step user-guided workbook through an adaptive management process designed to enable integration of climate adaptation into management (Swanston et al. 2016). It can be applied to a range of projects including both pre- and postfire forest health, hazard reduction, and reforestation projects. Appendix A provides links to and excerpts from the Quick Guide. The appendix contains direction for each of the five steps, examples for each step, and worksheets to guide a streamlined workflow. It is a decision support tool that generates focused, specific climate considerations and potential adaptation actions for integration into broader planning and decision making. While this process can be applied at a range of spatial scales, we recommend project-scale use for this specific application.

The Quick Guide can be implemented in a workshop format. This Conservation Strategy provides supporting materials needed to conduct a streamlined workshop while avoiding adding an unreasonable burden on existing staff workloads. With some beforehand preparation, a collaborative engagement could occur in 2-3 sessions of one hour apiece. Step 1 is carried out before the workshop, through defining the project extent, management goals and objectives, and time frames. In addition to a facilitator, assigning a specialist contributor such as an ecologist to the workshop will ensure that relevant climate and ecological context is incorporated beginning in Step 2. In addition, attendees would also benefit from hearing from the social science perspective, a point of view that is often inadvertently omitted from adaptation planning efforts.

Considerations for formal environmental planning processes

In the context of compliance with Federal and State laws (National Environmental Policy Act and California Environmental Quality Act [NEPA/CEQA]), the Quick Guide can best be considered a “first stop” during the initial steps of the formal planning process. While it’s true that conducting an adaptation

workshop adds time upfront to the planning process, many managers recognize downstream efficiencies from explicit inclusion of climate considerations. These efficiencies can include:

- The outputs of the workbook process provide documentation that climate was explicitly considered as a factor in the cause/effect relationships surrounding relevant issues (points of potential disagreement).
- The outputs of the workbook analysis can be incorporated into NEPA/CEQA analysis, either in sections or as an appendix.
- Full consideration of interactions between climate factors and natural resources can provide justification for a higher degree of management intervention when appropriate and needed.
- The process generates information for addressing third party and public comments.

Taken together, these materials can strengthen the planning process and ideally, reduce the time required for potential objections.

The Adaptation Menu for Southern California Montane Forests

Key to the application of the Adaptation Workbook (AW) is the development of an Adaptation Menu (AM) focused on key strategies and tactics for implementation on-the-ground. For purposes of supporting the Montane Forest Conservation Strategy, the supporting materials include a newly developed adaptation menu for Southern California Montane Forest Ecosystems. The menu was developed through collaborative engagements with subject matter experts, Indigenous stewards, and other project advisors. The menu springboards off the California Climate Hub's statewide adaptation menu for forest ecosystems (California Climate Hub, 2020) and guides managers through their options for climate adaptation. The adaptation menu describes adaptation strategies, approaches and tactics that are specific to Southern California montane forests; the menus are intended to be used in conjunction with the Adaptation Workbook to help users design specific on-the-ground management actions, and link these to their broader adaptation intent. In many cases the most important types of treatments for restoring and maintaining forest health will not be unfamiliar. As noted by managers and practitioners, reintroducing fire and managing the understory will frequently be the most important management needed to achieve and maintain healthy and sustainable montane forests (Figure 10). However, the tactics will vary across sites, and the menu should also be used to consider more transformative alternatives in locations experiencing high levels of exposure to climate and disturbances.

FIGURE 10. Responses to a question asking practitioners to rank management activities needed to achieve healthy and sustainable montane forests in Southern California.

The Adaptation Menu (Appendix B) takes a deep dive into the strategies, approaches, and tactics that managers may consider using. Before users move into that text, we suggest two overarching themes for users to keep in mind throughout the adaptation process. The first theme is the concept that management should be driven explicitly by objectives, and the second is that managers should consider accommodating change and enabling transformation.

Objective-driven management

Throughout this conservation strategy, a consistent theme is to use objective-driven management. Linking objectives to ecosystem functioning and resilience to disturbance is one way to value and prioritize the benefits provided by forests. This approach helps to balance the risks of interacting threats to forests and human communities against the uncertainties from management in times of change. The valuing and prioritization of ecosystem functioning should occur early in the project planning process, and ideally should be co-produced by managers and their partners, including Indigenous stewards and forest users.

Unlike the more productive forests elsewhere in the state, the dry forests of Southern California are not timber producing. Rather, these forests are broadly valued for a rich suite of benefits including recreational opportunities, cultural uses, provision of water and habitat, carbon storage, and biodiversity, among others. The Adaptation Menu reflects these values in providing management recommendations

that are consistent with conserving forest structure, and explicitly includes management approaches focused on hydrology, carbon storage, biodiversity, and habitat provision.

Across the landscape, the prioritization of ecosystem functions at the level of individual management units or projects will shift from site to site. One key step for managers will be to specify which parts of the landscape will be valued as forest for forest-derived services and managed as such through changing conditions. Linking specific locations with key services creates sideboards for the planning process, and narrows the management options that need to be evaluated. If a forest stand is valued for carbon storage and habitat provision, then under objective-driven management, the objectives provide managers with the leverage they need to select and implement tactics that preserve forest structure, including more deterministic tactics such as actively reducing shrub competition.

Accommodating change and enabling transformation

The most common current approach when defining objectives focuses on resisting change and preventing any plant community conversion. Under changing conditions, though, this type of objective can be maladaptive, and lead to ineffective and inefficient management, such as reforestation projects in sites with poor conditions for tree seedling survival. At the current time, many forest conversions are proceeding anyway, as widespread stressors and disturbance impact far more areas than can be managed with available resources and staff capacity. Therefore, in addition to supporting objective-driven management that focuses on maintaining the integrity of current forests, this menu also provides guidance for accommodating moderate change in some locations and enabling transformation in other locations. The menu strategies fall under three broad directions:

Resist: Maintaining current forest structure, composition, and function.

Accommodate: Allowing and facilitating moderate changes to current forest structure, composition, and function, with an emphasis on maintaining tree cover.

Transform: Enabling significant forest conversion to a new state with a goal of retaining similar ecological functions in the system.

Tactics for accommodating moderate change, such as allowing shifts from current composition and structure, are found throughout strategies 1-7 (Figure 11). The topic of transformation is centered in strategies 8 (Expand efforts with native species) and 9 (Plan for further change), along with additional guidance and examples for using this section of the menu.

Revisiting the [guiding principles](#) can provide additional direction. Whether accommodating change or enabling transformation, managers should choose objectives and tactics that promote ecological processes that support key ecosystem services (principle 1), that build resilience to agents of change (principle 2) and that maintain connectivity across dynamic conditions (principle 3). Principle 4 is especially significant for many of the tactics in this adaptation menu: reference forest conditions can be used to guide management, but changing conditions are likely to produce novel forest composition, structure, and function, and managers will need to adjust their objectives in response.

FIGURE 11. Strategies included in the Adaptation Menu. Tactics for accommodating moderate change are found throughout strategies 1-6. Strategy 7 encompasses management for sustaining fundamental ecological functions. The topic of transformation is centered in strategies 8 (Expand efforts with native species) and 9 (Plan for further change).

Both moderate and transformational change can also be supported with objective-driven management. For example, if a disturbed stand of conifers occurs in a highly exposed part of the landscape that has been defined as a potential site for transformation, then managers are empowered to choose from a set of options that do not necessarily demand reforestation to the pre-disturbance conditions. In this case, managers will have leverage for selecting from options that support establishment of other conifer, hardwood and/or shrub species. These two components— objective-driven management and the accommodation of change— may represent a departure from current practice, but both are necessary in order to move the needle in forest management.

Managers were consulted at numerous points during the development of this menu. Sources of manager input included interviews with specialists, and a series of four workshops focused on project advisors, forest practitioners, a focal group of specialists in refugia and rarity, and Indigenous stewards. Information was also drawn from the EcoAdapt Adaptation Synthesis for Conifer and Subalpine Habitats (2017) and Climate-Informed Forest Management for the San Bernardino Mountains (American Forests, 2021). Finally, this effort was kicked off at an Adaptation workshop sponsored by NIACS, CA Climate Hub, and the USFS Region 5 Ecosystem Services and Climate Change Program to apply the Adaptation Workbook to a forest health project on the Cleveland National Forest (Cleveland National Forest, 2021).

Case study of the Adaptation Menu in Action: Mount Laguna Healthy Forest Restoration Expansion project

A team of approximately 20 resource specialists from the Cleveland National Forest (CNF) along with partners from USFS Region 5 (R5) used the Adaptation Workbook to consider the effects of climate change on the Laguna Mountains Healthy Forest Restoration Expansion project area, and to design actions to help respond to these effects while meeting management goals and objectives. The workshop was conducted in two separate meetings in October 2021.

Step 1. Define: The project was defined as a forest health project focused on montane conifer, mixed conifer-hardwood, and California black oak stands, with components focused on improving habitat conditions for California spotted owl (CASPO) and managing the reintroduction of low severity fire. The project area had already been impacted by extensive loss of mature black oak to GSOB as well as two high-severity fires (2003 and 2013), and a prior reforestation effort had been unsuccessful. The project was designed to manage both pre- and postfire forest conditions. Primary tactics included mechanical thinning, prescribed fire, and reforestation.

Step 2. Assess: After considering anticipated climate impacts, the group ranked the impacts from greatest to least. Increasing severe drought topped the list, followed by more frequent and severe wildfire and then drought-enhanced pest and disease outbreaks. Areas of vulnerability included ecotone areas where forest adjoins chaparral or grassland, recent wildfire sites and forest stands with south-facing aspects or high stand densities. Wet meadows and riparian areas were also identified as highly important but potentially vulnerable. The group also discussed vulnerability to key invasive plant and pest insect species.

Step 3. Evaluate: After discussion, the following revisions were made to management goals and objectives to support more accommodation to expected climate and disturbance:

- Emphasis on favoring Jeffrey pine as a dominant conifer species was revised to enable inclusion of Coulter pine and incense cedar. These two species are somewhat shade intolerant, compatible with the reintroduction of more frequent understory fires, and show adaptability to future fire conditions.
- The management objectives for California spotted owl habitat call for meeting or moving towards habitat thresholds for dense canopy cover established in the Conservation Strategy for California spotted owl. While areas of high canopy cover are crucial for CASPO, the likelihood of broadly retaining cover levels in face of drought, fires, and insects is low, and high canopy cover can increase fire risk. To address this concern, the management objective for California spotted owl habitat was re-focused on leveraging refugial features such as riparian areas, drainages, and northeast-facing slopes for maintaining the cover and thermal thresholds for this focal species.
- A separate management objective was created to cover the need to manage invasive plant species that might benefit from increasing temperature and frequent fire (cheatgrass, mustard spp.).
- The target for the maintenance fire rotation was also revised from a single estimated year (13 years) to a range of years (10-15 years). The natural range of variation for this forest type has been estimated as 8-13 years. These values were adjusted to a range to account for projected reductions in the frequency of wet winters. Prescribed fire is more likely to be conducted in years with sufficient winter precipitation.

Step 4. Identify: Identifying tactics from the menu led to discussion about constraints and alternatives. Consideration of tactics from the Fire Menu produced a discussion about the need to write burn plans with increased flexibility around burn intervals. Both the need to increase burning during wetter years (through surge staffing to take advantage of narrow windows) and to limit negative resource impacts during drought years (needing development of a decision structure, a “prescribed fire Go/No Go process” for drought years) were covered. The group also raised the need to accept a greater range of prescribed fire effects. Currently most prescribed fire occurs at very low severity levels during narrow windows of greatest condition favorability, and it is difficult to take advantage of prescription windows during fall months. Accepting a greater range of effects may be necessary to continue to reintroduce fire at meaningful levels across the landscape, and to utilize the fall period that is the best suited for treating bark beetle impacts and California spotted owl nesting habitat.

An intensive discussion occurred around the approaches for conducting revegetation promptly after disturbance. While some tactics for increasing the success of restoration projects remained within the ability of staff to control (use of seed lot selection tools, optimizing seasonal timing, use of microsites and other best practices, building reliable relationships with nurseries and seed sources), others fell outside the ability of staff to control (funding models for post-disturbance restoration).

Step 5. Monitor: The project team identified several monitoring variables to track the success of adaptation actions over time, such as forest structure and reforestation survival rates. These ideas need to be further refined to help determine what specific criteria or thresholds are most meaningful for tracking adaptation success, and how monitoring can be implemented.

3. Consider Context in Reforestation

Following large and potentially damaging wildfires there is often a need to conduct a post-fire restoration assessment to identify opportunities and prioritize areas for restoration. The effects of fire may either improve or damage forest structure and function, and needed management actions could include reforestation, actions to limit the risk of severe reburn events, or (in locations where fire has improved forest condition) subsequent steps towards reintroduction of maintenance fire.

The Montane Forest Conservation Strategy supports use of the Postfire Restoration Framework for National Forests in California for forest, woodlands, and shrublands (Meyer et al. 2021, also known as GTR 270). The framework is founded on a set of guiding ecological and restoration principles and uses a five-step process to develop a restoration portfolio for project planning and postfire monitoring. The framework was developed by the USFS Region 5 Ecology Program but is designed to apply to any postfire landscape of interest and allows flexibility with respect to management priorities and goals. As with other parts of the Montane Forest Conservation Strategy, this framework is designed to be implemented in a team setting with facilitation.

The framework emphasizes analysis of the burned area within both climate and habitat contexts. The context of anticipated future climate conditions puts necessary sideboards on reforestation projects. The current degree of forest dieback indicates that many trees are already close to their physiological limits, while a significant degree of additional warming is anticipated across montane sky islands in Southern California. For trees, the seedling and sapling life-stages are the most vulnerable to mortality, and survival levels during reforestation projects in Southern California are already low (~30% survival). The monetary

costs of restoration underscore that these efforts require a strong degree of judgment when deciding where and how to reforest. Often, the best approach will be to prioritize planting in locations of climate refugia and slower warming over more exposed locations. The refugia layer in Figure 5 can be used for analyses such as this.

The habitat-focused context includes consideration of ecological attributes such as regional native biodiversity and habitat connectivity. Including landscape context ensures a connection between resulting restoration projects and landscape restoration goals. This approach prioritizes the reforestation of mature native forest stands, with their higher species and structural diversity, over simpler and younger plantation stands. The final set of questions in the analysis flow focuses on feasibility, to provide a pragmatic and balanced approach to restoring and sustaining ecosystem services.

The framework emphasizes long-term ecosystem integrity and function through incorporation of natural range of variability (NRV) into the analysis flow. The first step in the framework asks where fire has improved or maintained ecological conditions, as defined by NRV (Figure 12). In fire-adapted forests, where the process of fire plays a central role in maintaining forest condition, locations where fire effects are positive should be considered separately from the locations where fire effects were outside the natural range of variability.

A detailed introduction to each of the five steps in the framework is provided in GTR 270. The postfire restoration framework was applied in 2022 to the Bobcat Fire footprint on the Angeles National Forest, and details are provided below as a case study.

FIGURE 12. Analytical workflow of the Postfire Restoration Framework (Meyer et al. 2021).

Case study in Post-fire Restoration Planning: Bobcat Fire, San Gabriel Mountains National Monument

The Bobcat Fire occurred during the 2020 California wildfire season. It burned 115,796 acres (46,861 ha) in the central San Gabriel Mountains, in and around the Angeles National Forest. In the initial days of the fire, steep and difficult terrain, low humidity, high temperatures, and a Santa Ana wind event hindered fire suppression efforts. The Bobcat was the second-largest wildfire recorded in modern times in Los Angeles County, behind the 2009 Station Fire, and it burned across the entire elevational gradient (843-8,389 feet) in the mountain belt from south to north. Given the size of the fire and the montane forest values within the fire area, managers for the San Gabriel Mountains National Monument reached out for assistance with postfire restoration planning.

Step 1. Identify a Team and Identify Priority Resources, Desired Conditions, and Restoration Goals

The team for this effort included Southern Province ecologists from the Region 5 Ecology Program and natural resource specialists from the San Gabriel Mountains National Monument of the Angeles National Forest. Forest staff requested analysis focused on upper montane mixed conifer forest and chaparral at lower elevations. Habitat for sensitive species was also considered a priority resource, and due to soil erosion concerns, emphasis was placed on aquatic species reliant on stream water quality (Arroyo Toad, Mountain Yellow-Legged Frog, and Santa Ana Sucker). Bigcone Douglas-fir is included as an important endemic species and as a priority habitat for California Spotted Owl.

We reviewed desired conditions for these key resources based on information provided in land management and resource planning documents, and then developed specific restoration goals for the analysis area: (1) maintain and restore mixed-conifer forest ecosystem integrity, diversity, and resilience, (2) maintain sufficient sensitive species habitat suitability and connectivity, and (3) maintain native shrubland types and reduce the abundance of non-native species.

Step 2. Gather and Analyze Relevant Spatial Data

The team gathered map layers to represent vegetation communities and sensitive species, including a Forestwide mapping layer for Bigcone Douglas-fir. The available postfire data included both RAVG (Rapid Assessment of Vegetation Condition after Wildfire, produced within 45 days after fire containment) and MTBS (Monitoring Trends in Burn Severity, produced 1 year postfire) condition classifications. MTBS often reflects a more accurate estimate of forest mortality by detecting new growth 1 year following the fire event. The Postfire Conifer Reforestation Planning Tool (PostCRPT) was also used to predict the probability of natural post-fire conifer regeneration under varying postfire precipitation and seed production scenarios (Shive et al. 2018).

Step 3. Use the Postfire Flowchart to Identify Restoration Opportunities

Question 1: Where did fire improve or maintain ecological conditions and are fire effects within desired conditions or NRV?

Mixed conifer: The answer focused both on the distribution of large and very large patches of high severity fire, as well as the overall percentage of high severity fire. The resilience of coniferous forest ecosystems to fire depends on forest regeneration factors such as tree survival and seed dispersal. Both of these are negatively influenced as the size of high severity patches increases. If a large proportion of

the forest area is affected by high severity fire effects, the surviving trees may not maintain dominance in the recovering plant community, and also may not be able to generate the quantity of viable seed needed to support robust regeneration. Most conifer species produce heavy seeds with limited potential for dispersal. If high severity patches are limited to a relatively small proportion of the forest matrix, the distance between high severity patches to live seed-producing trees remains small. While the postfire imagery detected large, high severity patches from the Bobcat at lower elevations with chaparral cover, upper montane conifer forest fared better. Within the fire perimeter, the MTBS assessed that 23% of areas classified as yellow pine - mixed conifer burned at moderate severity and 8% burned at high severity (Figure 13). These values fall within the natural range of variation, suggesting that the forest should be able to respond to the fire with resilience (Safford & Stevens 2017, Nigro & Molinari 2024). The mapping also shows that in mixed conifer areas, most patches of high severity effects have good connectivity to a matrix of less severely burned forest. Generally, across the upper montane forest belt, fire improved or maintained ecological effects, suggesting the mixed conifer stands within the burned area do not require active restoration at this time.

Bigcone: We also examined the distribution of fire severity effects on Bigcone Douglas-fir, which is a significant component of the forest within the project area. Within the perimeter of the Bobcat Fire, the MTBS assessment was that 29% of areas classified as Bigcone Douglas-fir burned at moderate severity and 14% burned at high severity. Both moderate- and high-severity areas should be focused on for potential restoration. Previous regional restoration experience suggests that natural regeneration is unlikely in areas that burned at moderate severity or greater, so these areas could benefit from replanting. The postfire mapping indicates that 56% of the areas defined as having Bigcone Douglas-fir remained unburned or experienced low fire severity, and these areas will not require restoration.

Question A: Where do other factors threaten ecological resilience and sustainability?

Undesirable conditions that could threaten ecological resilience in the Bobcat fire include climate change, stand isolation, regeneration failure, and erosion risk, with a primary focus on the larger patches of potential high burn severity. Potential for future high tree mortality from drought or insect outbreaks, as well as excessive fuel accumulation that might increase the risk of reburn could also be included as potential concerns.

The refugia layer developed for this conservation strategy identifies areas likely to experience relatively slow directional change (refugia) compared to exposed areas likely to experience more rapid change. The POSCRPT tool was used to predict regeneration, with the caveat that the tool is not yet fully developed for Southern California and does not include Bigcone Douglas-fir or Coulter pine. Predictions for 5-year postfire erosion rates were generally low across the upper montane burn area.

Question B. Where are management approaches feasible for the restoration of desired conditions given current and anticipated future conditions?

The climate exposure layer reflected a broad pattern of slower change and higher refugia potential on north-facing slopes, especially north of the montane crest and conversely, of greater climate exposure on south-facing slopes and south of the montane crest. With these anticipated future conditions in mind, replanting of mixed conifer forest and Bigcone Douglas-fir should be focused on north-facing slopes.

The feasibility of restoration is based on land use, topographic, and road proximity constraints. The burn area included portions of two roadless wilderness areas, where restoration plantings rarely occur. Planting is also more feasible if slope is less than 30%, but the topography within the fire footprint generally exceeds this threshold, and restoration plans will need to accommodate steep slopes.

FIGURE 13. MTBS burn severity mapping for the Bobcat Fire indicated that much of the montane forest belt burned at low severity, while chaparral on lower slopes burned at high severity.

Step 4. Develop and Integrate Restoration Opportunities into Potential Restoration Actions

This step defines three restoration opportunities. The first is to maintain or promote desired conditions in locations that burned primarily at low to moderate severity. This would also include high-severity patches that burned within NRV for patch size. In these places, the primary management activities would be to

monitor tree mortality, fuel loading, and natural regeneration. Montane forest stands would start to be ready for prescribed fire in 5-10 years, depending on forest type.

The second opportunity is to restore desired conditions in locations where fire effects fell outside the NRV. Management actions would include reducing excessive fuels loading in large patches of severe fire effects and high tree mortality. Replanting could also occur to address postfire regeneration failure, especially for Bigcone Douglas-fir. These actions would likely be constrained to areas where restoration is feasible, and field validation would be required to verify the spatial analysis.

The third opportunity is to reevaluate desired conditions considering climate change and other stressors. Fortunately in this case, fire severity in mixed conifer forest was not greatly departed from NRV over most of the landscape, and traditional management approaches can be used. However, given the likelihood of increasing drought stress through time, some parts of the landscape, such as south-facing slopes, could require the reevaluation of desired conditions. For example, two large patches with high severity fire effects fall on south-facing slopes with high predicted climate exposure. These patches are in roadless wilderness, where restoration is not highly feasible. Management should anticipate continued disturbances, such as increased frequency and severity of fire, in these locations.

TABLE 3. Summary of restoration opportunities, target areas, and management actions in the Bobcat Fire case study

Restoration Opportunity	Target Areas	Management Actions
Maintain or promote desired conditions	Areas with natural regeneration of mixed conifers Burned areas with fine litter ground cover	Protect seedlings through continued fire exclusion or pile burning, until sapling stage is reached Conduct prescribed fire
Take actions to restore desired conditions	Areas with no natural regeneration of mixed conifers Areas with no natural regeneration of Bigcone Douglas-fir Areas with Spanish Broom invasion	Conduct restoration plantings of conifers Conduct restoration plantings of Bigcone Douglas-fir Consider helicopter access to targeted ridgetops Treat Spanish Broom to eradicate
Reevaluate desired conditions considering interacting stressors	Large high-severity patches on south-facing slopes	Avoid planting on south-facing slopes and reforestation plantations

Step 5. Build a Restoration Portfolio by Prioritizing Actions

The portfolio for this project will include a range of projects that address the three opportunities in the previous step. Project locations are drawn from the spatial analysis- in this system, projects will be focused on large patches of high-severity fire effects. The prioritization will incorporate timing, feasibility, and the opportunity cost of inaction, which is currently a major factor in many locations. This framework

will support the management team in focusing restoration investments in areas with higher potential for success and lower risk of interacting stressors, including anticipated climate stressors.

Operationalizing the Plan: Moving from Strategy to Action

Project design

To the extent possible, projects should be designed at the scales in which ecological processes occur. This may be a landscape- or watershed-scale, and should consider where bridging ownership and management boundaries by leveraging partnerships can advance landscape scale adaptation by treating ecological systems as contiguous, connected units. However, it is also important to ensure that the purpose and need of a project and the proposed action are not excessively broad either in geographic extent or scope of activities.

In particular, the management approaches needed in landscapes dominated by montane forest as compared to those that are predominantly shrublands are different enough to warrant separate projects for forest and shrublands. Treating each separately will allow project intent and design to target conservation and adaptation actions that are clear and specific for planners and managers as well as project partners and stakeholders. In forest health projects, maintaining a focus on both community safety and ecological resilience is also important for creating projects that support forest persistence.

Environmental review

The time, funding, and staffing needed to complete environmental review processes (i.e., NEPA and CEQA) were identified by many forest management practitioners as a major challenge to increasing the pace and scale of forest treatments (Figure 14). Although these processes are most often undertaken on an organizational basis to meet agency missions and goals, partnerships have the potential to greatly enhance the region's collective capacity to complete environmental review. Where project designs span multiple land ownerships or management organizations, conducting coordinated processes to meet all environmental review requirements at once can be effective and efficient. Although sometimes challenging to navigate, partnerships can bring a wider range of funds, increased personnel capacity, particularly where there is high demand for specialist input, and the opportunity for partners to keep momentum going on a project when capacity becomes limiting for one of the collaborating partners.

FIGURE 14. Top Challenges for Forest Project Planning. Respondents were asked to select up to three issues that pose the biggest challenges to completing the planning for forest management projects in Southern California.

The set of tools recommended for use in this conservation strategy will provide documentation and support through the environmental review process. Use of these tools can inform prioritization and identify appropriate management targets. They provide robust information about the anticipated effects of climate change across the landscape, and will help managers summarize and leverage the available scientific knowledge.

Project implementation

Similar to the environmental review process, partnerships can also help overcome the impacts of funding, workforce, and time limitations in the project implementation phase (Figure 15). Forming a multi-organizational workforce can speed the completion of site preparation prior to a project (e.g., unit flagging), in-house project work (e.g., cutting, piling, and burning), and contracting. For example, letting joint contracts and having cross-organizational support for contract oversight can allow contracts to be executed and completed more quickly where environmental conditions allow. Increasing the pace and scale of contract work, and in fact the entire project pipeline, can allow for further economic development in the private forest and fuels treatment sector, with clear pathways and workloads that prospective contractors can plan for over longer time periods. Biomass utilization also needs development that relies on predictable supply. Any increase in contractor and biomass utilization capacity will further expand our capacity to accelerate the implementation of forest resilience projects.

FIGURE 15. Top Challenges for Forest Project Implementation Respondents were asked to select up to three issues that pose the biggest challenges to completing implementation of forest management projects in Southern California.

Pathway to progress

We are working with practitioners across the region to identify needs and opportunities to facilitate implementation of forest management projects. We are also working to align with regional prioritization efforts and the working groups of block-grant recipients established through the CA Regional Forest and Fire Capacity Program. Continued progress and coordination with these partners will greatly enhance our capacity for forest management.

The challenges of increasing the pace and scale of forest treatments under intensifying disturbance cycles drove the format of this conservation strategy. It quickly became clear that narrower and more prescriptive strategic approaches would not sufficiently support the full range of land managers or answer to the diversity of forest conditions across the region. Recognizing that there is no one-size-fits-all answer for climate-adapted forest management, this conservation strategy instead focuses on creating pathways for managers to follow in planning and implementation, and on connecting managers with existing science and information to reduce uncertainty.

The conservation strategy also recognizes the benefit to managers that comes from facilitated engagement with these pathways. The processes and tools recommended by this conservation strategy are largely well-documented with manuals and case studies. However, the intent is not to ask managers to “start from scratch” using unfamiliar protocols and processes. The authors of this conservation strategy

are experienced in using these processes through workshop engagements with a variety of audiences, including collaborative partnership groups. In many cases, the authors of this strategy will be available to guide use of the Southern Montane Forests Framework, the adaptation workbook and menu, and the postfire restoration strategy.

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Appendix A. The Adaptation Menu in Action: Mount Laguna Healthy Forest Restoration Expansion Project

Excerpted from [“A Quick Guide to Adaptation Planning for Natural Resource Professionals”](#) (Janowiak et al, 2022).

Step 1. DEFINE project goals and objectives

Clearly stated goals and objectives are important for helping you and your partners and collaborators describe exactly what you want to do. As you set up a new project, you will want to answer two fundamental questions:

Where is your project located? The project could focus on one nature area or a single small parcel, which may be a good fit for the format of this Quick Guide. Larger and more complex projects could include a large property with diverse habitats or multiple parcels scattered across a community or landscape; these are better suited to the full Adaptation Workbook. Visit forestadaptation.org/workbook for more details.

What are you trying to achieve? The project should articulate clear management goals and objectives to describe the intent of the project and the desired outcomes.

- Management goals describe the broad outcomes you are trying to accomplish. Goals outline the big picture and set the long-term vision for where you want to go.
- Management objectives are more specific actions that support the completion of a goal. Using the house analogy, your goals form the foundation that you build on, while the objectives are the walls and roof that form the shell of the house. As much as possible, objectives should be SMART: specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time bound.

Step 1 should occur before the first group meeting, and meeting participants should have an opportunity to review the project goals and objectives.

Step 1. Examples of pre- and postfire forest management goals and objectives (from Laguna Expansion Project case study). To accommodate both recently burned and unburned areas, the management goals covered both site conditions. Anticipated timeframes ranged from 10-30 years.

Condition	Management Goal	Management Objective
Pre-fire	Improve the health of montane conifer, conifer-hardwood, and hardwood stands	<p>a. Encourage growth of shade intolerant species (e.g. black oak, Jeffrey pine, Coulter pine, incense cedar) by reducing competition with thinning in stands with SDI>100.</p> <p>b. Promote native understory species with low severity understory prescribed fire on average every 10 - 15 years.</p>

	Restore portion of stands previously occupied by large California black oak	c. Accelerate growth of sapling to pole size black oaks adjacent to recent mortality by thinning like size conifer and hardwood trees.
	Improve habitat conditions for California spotted owl (CSO) in drainages, riparian areas, and northeast slopes	e. Design uneven-age management prescriptions to meet or move towards habitat thresholds established in the Conservation Strategy for California spotted owl.
	Reintroduce low severity fire into montane conifer forest ecosystems	f. For forest stands which have missed 1 or more fire return intervals, utilize low severity understory prescribed fire as an initial final treatment and for regular maintenance of forested stands on average every 10 - 15 years.
Postfire	Restore montane conifer forest deforested from wildfires.	<p>a. Prepare planting site by reducing competing vegetation and existing surface fuels through prescribed fire or herbicide</p> <p>b. Plant conifer nursery stock from lower elevation band seed or from southerly latitudes</p> <p>c. Manage competing vegetation until desired tree stocking levels are reached</p>
	In portions of stands or whole stands where tree canopy was not entirely lost, improve resiliency to a future wildland fire event.	<p>d. Lower severity of future wildfire events and release existing natural regeneration by reducing shrub cover, coarse woody debris, and snag levels with mechanical thinning and regular prescribed fire on average every 10-15 years.</p> <p>f. Promote germination of desired conifer and hardwood species through creation of patches of bare mineral soil.</p>

Step 2. ASSESS climate change impacts and vulnerabilities

Climate change will affect our natural landscapes and the human communities that depend upon them in many ways. Although we have a wealth of information about climate change impacts nationally and regionally, climate change will affect each area differently based on the local characteristics that are unique to that place.

In this step, you will identify the local factors that may increase or reduce the potential effects of climate change in your project area. Some examples of these factors are:

- Site conditions, such as topographic position, soils, or hydrology.
- Past and current management that has affected the condition of the land.

- Ecosystem composition and structure.
- Susceptibility to pests, diseases, or other stressors that may become more frequent and severe. You can consult vulnerability assessments for information on the anticipated effects of climate change on ecosystems for a particular region. Visit forestadaptation.org/learn/resource-finder for focused resources.

After describing local climate change impacts, you can rate your level of vulnerability:

- **Low Vulnerability** – Ecosystems are expected to readily cope with potential climate change impacts. Climate change is more beneficial to ecosystems than disruptive.
- **Moderate Vulnerability** – Climate change impacts are expected to alter ecosystems, but ecosystems will be able to cope with some impacts.
- **High Vulnerability** – Climate change impacts are expected to exceed the ability of the ecosystem to cope with impacts. Ecosystems may undergo changes that will disrupt important ecosystem functions and key environmental benefits

Step 2 should be led by a natural resource specialist such as an ecologist or hydrologist, and consist of a presentation. If needed, a written summary may also be provided beforehand. The presentation serves to establish baseline climate information for the rest of the workshop.

Step 2. Regional climate impacts were prioritized (in order of the strongest impacts first) by the group in an interactive Mentimeter exercise. The group then identified locations in the project area most vulnerable to each type of impact.

Regional climate impacts	Local and Project-level vulnerabilities
1. Increasing severe drought	Forested sites with characteristics such as south-facing aspects or high stand densities are more vulnerable to drought effects.
2. More frequent and extensive wildfire	Ecotone areas where forest adjoins chaparral or grassland are vulnerable to overly frequent or high-intensity fire. Postfire sites may experience repeat high intensity fire. Natural forest regeneration may fail.
3. Increases in existing or novel insect pests and disease – for example Gold spotted oak borer, bark beetles, and fungal agents.	Sites with characteristics such as south-facing aspects or high stand densities are more vulnerable to pests and diseases.
4. Increasingly variable year-to-year precipitation	Wet meadows and riparian areas, particularly peripheral areas of meadows are vulnerable to increased drying
5. Increased mean and maximum temperatures	Forested sites with characteristics such as south-facing aspects or high stand densities are more vulnerable to heat effects.

Step 3. EVALUATE goals and objectives

Once you have identified the climate change impacts on your project area, consider how these impacts could influence the goals and objectives that you identified in the first step.

Four questions can be useful to help you evaluate your project goals and objectives in the context of climate change:

- What new or different challenges need to be addressed as a result of climate change and related stressors?
- What new opportunities might be available as a result of anticipated changes?
- Are your current management practices enough to overcome the challenges and meet your management goals and objectives?
- Do any of your goals or objectives need to change?

Once you have thought about how climate change may create challenges to, or opportunities for, your project, you may realize that there may be conditions where it may no longer be feasible to meet some of the goals and objectives that you identified in Step 1. If this is the case, this is an appropriate time to revise your goals or objectives before moving onto the next step.

- **Example of a revised objective.** Given all the risks and vulnerabilities outlined in Step 2 you may decide to revise an objective if the objective was not found to be feasible. For example, you may decide that feasibility is higher if you construct a new trail network, rather than maintain an existing trail network heavily impacted by severe storms and flooding.

Challenges to meeting project goals and objectives	Opportunities for project meeting goals and objectives
Jeffrey pine is susceptible to many climate stressors (e.g. pests and fire), and may not persist or regenerate well.	Species present on the project site like Coulter pine and incense cedar show some adaptability to future conditions. Incense cedar appears to be very fire tolerant.
Gold spotted oak borer combined with drought stress present challenges for the survival of large black oak trees.	Black oaks are regenerating on the project site, with many sapling and pole-sized trees present. Multi-age stands may be more resilient to stressors.
High canopy cover is crucial for the California Spotted Owl but the likelihood of retaining cover levels in face of drought/fires/insects is low. In addition, maintaining high canopy cover can increase fire risk and other stressors.	Leveraging refugial features such as riparian areas, drainages, and northeast-facing slopes for maintaining the cover and thermal thresholds for CA Spotted Owl.
Prescribed fire season is shortening and wildfire season is lengthening; increasing challenges to implementing prescribed fire on a regular schedule.	Accepting a wider range of prescribed fire effects may stimulate increased resin development in conifers, which could increase resistance to bark beetle attacks.

Increasing heat and drought stress on seedlings may decrease survival rates. These conditions may also cause delays in planning efforts & contracts.	Winters with abundant precipitation may be infrequent but provide opportunities for rapid establishment of seedlings.
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Step 4. IDENTIFY and implement adaptation actions

You may need to alter your management practices to address new or increased challenges associated with a changing climate and environmental conditions. Identifying potential challenges and opportunities will position you to take action and adapt practices that will maximize your ability to achieve your goals for your property of interest.

Start by brainstorming and outlining specific actions or tactics that you want to evaluate for your project, and then consider:

- Time Frames – When would this action be implemented? Some actions may occur in the short term, while others may not occur for a long time or will occur only in certain situations (such as after a large disturbance).
- Benefits – What benefits does the action provide? For example, note if a tactic addresses your biggest challenge, addresses multiple challenges, or has co-benefits such as improving carbon mitigation and visitor experiences.
- Drawbacks and Barriers – What drawbacks are associated with this action? Note any negative effects or potential barriers (e.g., legal, financial, infrastructural, social) that are likely to arise.
- Effectiveness – Does the action meet the desired intent?
- Feasibility – Can the action be implemented?

After considering the above items, you will be better able to select the specific actions or tactics that are a good fit for your situation. The preferred actions will likely be those that overcome the greatest challenges, have major benefits, and can be implemented given your available resources.

TABLE 4: Proposed adaptation actions identified for the Laguna Mountains Healthy Forest Restoration Expansion project from the California Forests and draft Fire menus.

Menu	Adaptation Approach	Potential Adaptation Tactics	Benefits or Drawbacks/Barriers
PRE-BURN CONDITIONS			
California Forests	1.4. Reduce vegetation competition for moisture, nutrients, and light	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce tree density to help increase survivorship in older trees and favor individuals that are healthy. • In areas at high risk from drought/beetle attacks (e.g. south & southwest aspects), thin and follow with pile burning to reduce stand densities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These are current management practices. • Stand densities of 100 SDI may disfavor certain wildlife species and favor ceanothus.
California Forests	5.1. Promote forest age- and size-class diversity and spatial heterogeneity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create gaps using individual tree and group selection to encourage regeneration of lower diameter classes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May be difficult to get the gap size right for certain species (e.g. Jeffrey pine).
California Forests	2.1. Maintain or improve the ability of forests to resist pathogens and insect pests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leave large black oaks that have survived GSOB on the landscape to regenerate - potentially decrease encroachment or conifers around them to give them a leg up. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This action is already occurring (some survival of large oaks, currently producing acorns).
California Forests	4.2. Prioritize and maintain sensitive or at-risk species or communities 5.1. Promote forest age- and size-class diversity and spatial heterogeneity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjust objectives to be more specific about where to maintain higher canopy cover & tree densities. For example, maintain those conditions in places w/landscape features (e.g., drainages and NE facing slopes) that are most beneficial to California Spotted Owls. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This would increase areas that can be treated while still protecting CSO habitat.

Fire Menu	7.3. Consider using fire as a tool to align existing vegetation communities with changing climate regimes 9.1: Develop adaptive staffing and budgeting strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapt the burn plan to increase flexibility with burn intervals. Increase burning during wetter years and develop a Go/No Go process, particularly during drought years. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workforce availability can affect flexibility (e.g. personnel may be tasked with fire suppression)
Fire Menu	9.1: Develop adaptive staffing and budgeting strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement surge hiring to increase workforce that's dedicated staff for burning. Create an implementation pre-burn team. Add a fuels person to the NEPA team. 	

Menu	Adaptation Approach	Potential Adaptation Tactics	Benefits or Drawbacks/Barriers
POST-BURN CONDITIONS			
California Forests	3.4. Promptly revegetate after disturbance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use silvicultural prescriptions to regenerate on-site forest based on stand characteristics and tree species currently present. Favor native species adapted to future conditions if possible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Using trees present on site would be easier than finding nursery stock. However may be missing an opportunity to increase genetic or species diversity.
California Forests	1.4. Reduce vegetation competition for moisture, nutrients, and light. 2.2. Minimize the risk of the introduction and establishment of invasive plants and remove existing invasive species.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use mechanical or herbicidal removal of encroaching woody competitors and invasive species to create suitable conditions for regeneration and enhance the survivorship and growth of desired species. Use fire for maintenance (broadcast burns). Use cattle grazing to manage competing vegetation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cattle permits are on site already. This tactic requires collaboration with knowledgeable ranchers.

<p>California Forests</p>	<p>10.1. Promptly revegetate sites after disturbance.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct planting site preparation to reduce competing vegetation and existing surface fuels. • Prescribed burn before planting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timing adds complexity – it can be difficult to be ready with site prep post-fire.
<p>California Forests</p>	<p>9.2. Establish or encourage new mixes of native species 10.3. Realign significantly disrupted ecosystems to meet expected future conditions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant species that may be better able to cope with future conditions such as trees that can come to maturity in a warmer climate (60 yrs out). • Increase the diversity & selection of planted species (e.g. Coulter pine, diversity of oak spp. e.g. canyon live oaks). • Make more efficient use of microsites by selecting species better suited to site characteristics. • Use seedlot selection tools to help select future-adapted tree species; consult with other forests/regions tackling this issue. • Form relationships with nurseries to ensure future availability of seeds & seedling stock. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge in getting seedlings delivered in the appropriate planting window. • Identifying funding that can be used over 5-year periods is important – needs to cover both planting and maintenance.

Step 5. MONITOR and evaluate effectiveness

Monitoring is about asking the right questions that will help you ensure desired outcomes over time. There are different types of monitoring that you'll encounter in science and management. In scientific research, we may have a question and a hypothesis, and with quality replication we can judge deviation through time. But, most of us will find this methodology difficult to implement because of the financial costs, and time and effort involved. Instead, the focus here can be on evaluating whether you are achieving the goals and objectives that you identified at the outset of the project and to what extent your actions were effective in helping you meet those goals and objectives.

Monitoring allows you to practice adaptive management. It has always been impossible to predict the future, and climate change makes that uncertainty even more apparent. Adaptive management supports decision-making in the face of uncertain future conditions by adopting a flexible approach that allows you to adjust your management as new information becomes available.

Objective or Adaptation Tactic	Monitoring item
Thin stand densities (i.e. 100 SDI or under) to protect against drought and beetle attacks.	Post-treatment stand density monitoring
Design uneven-age management prescriptions to meet or move towards habitat thresholds established in the Conservation Strategy for California spotted owl in drainages, riparian areas, and northeastern slopes.	Track canopy cover over time across owl activity areas and landscape management units
Increase burn interval flexibility to enable burning more in wetter years and in the fall (to avoid CSO nesting in spring); implementation of a "prescribed fire Go/No Go" process for drought years and burn windows.	Pre and post burn monitoring across drought categories (e.g. moderate, exceptional, extreme) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Tree survival ● Current year leaf dieback
Plant conifer nursery stock using lower elevation band seed or seed from southerly latitudes	Monitoring plant germination, survival, health, and height. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● compare across elevations/seed zones ● against control or baseline stock

Appendix B. Adaptation Menu

[Strategy 1. Support community engagement in montane forest conservation](#)

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
<p>1.1 Consider mindful practices of reciprocity.</p>	<p>1.1.1 Provide gifts or compensation when seeking guidance or knowledge from elders or community members</p> <p>1.1.2 Share data and results of climate change assessments and adaptation projects with the local community.</p> <p>1.1.3 Ensure that all who share knowledge, such as teachers, elders, and all contributors are credited in presentations, public documents, and materials.</p> <p>1.1.4 Teach harvesting in a good way, such as taking only what you need and leaving enough to sustain the population.</p>
<p>1.2 Consult cultural leaders, key community members, and elders.</p>	<p>1.2.1 Events and access to engage in stewardship of ancestral lands can help to change existing adversarial relationships with Indigenous communities.</p> <p>1.2.2 Work with Tribal leaders and members to identify knowledgeable individuals in the community, such as elders, and ask for guidance for how to consult with them in a good way.</p> <p>1.2.3 Conduct community engagement workshops to learn about past environmental (especially climate-related) changes using specific local examples or important resources as discussion points.</p> <p>1.2.4 Work with Indigenous stewards to understand observed impacts to non-human relatives (plants and animals) from storm events, drought, or other aspects of changing climate.</p>
<p>1.3 Understand the human and landscape history of the local communities.</p>	<p>1.3.1 Identify and meet with Tribal Historic Preservation Officers in order to understand the history of the local community.</p> <p>1.3.2 Work in a good way with Tribes to make connections with traditional stories and teaching and to forge insights focused on climate change.</p>
<p>1.4 Maintain and revitalize traditional relationships and resource uses.</p>	<p>1.4.1 Support educational programs for engaging youth. Educational programs should use outdoor classrooms as much as possible and be guided by Tribal communities.</p> <p>1.4.2 Create opportunities for intergenerational teaching and guidance.</p> <p>1.4.3 Create opportunities for cross-cultural learning, experiences, and partnerships to help non-Tribal forest management practitioners better understand and incorporate</p>

	<p>Indigenous relationships with the land and non-human relatives as well as traditional stewardship practices into their efforts.</p> <p>1.4.4 Preserve threatened resources to ensure that traditional crafts, medicines, and relationships can continue in a changing environment</p>
<p>1.5 Participate in local- and landscape-level management decisions with partner agencies</p>	<p>1.5.1 Fully utilize existing funded and non-funded agreements or develop new agreements as part of advancing co-stewardship of ancestral lands.</p> <p>1.5.2 Forest management practitioners should engage Tribes at the outset of the decision-making process, when project development is in early stages.</p> <p>1.5.3 Tribes can request or utilize a Tribal liaison to increase communication with partner agencies on climate change planning.</p>

Strategy 2. Reduce the risk and long-term impacts of severe disturbances

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
<p>2.1 Reduce risk or severity of wildfire.</p>	<p>2.1.1 Reduce fuel continuity and ladder fuels (e.g. reduce surface fuels, increase canopy base height, reduce canopy bulk density).</p> <p>2.1.2 Prioritize management treatments in strategic areas of highest risk of uncharacteristic fire effects, such as stand-replacing fire.</p> <p>2.1.3 Prioritize fuels treatments in strategic areas of highest community risk. Maintain defensible space around structures up to 100 ft depending on slope and vegetation.</p> <p>2.1.4 Implement fire-conscious planning and home hardening measures for structures</p> <p>2.1.5 Coordinate with utility companies to reduce likelihood of ignition from their infrastructure</p> <p>2.1.6 Engage with the public about community exposure and susceptibility and the hazards associated with the current ecosystem condition.</p>
<p>2.2 Reduce the risk of severe reburns in existing high severity fire footprints</p>	<p>2.2.1 Manage shrub cover, coarse woody debris, and snag density in ecologically sound ways within recovering forest stands</p> <p>2.2.2 Conduct public awareness engagements and campaigns to address common ignition sources</p>

<p>2.3 Alter forest structure to reduce severity or extent of extreme weather events (drought, flooding, erosion)</p>	<p>2.3.1 Enhance structural heterogeneity and reduce inter-tree competition through use of variable density thinning 2.3.2 Identify locations where the alignment of topography and structures put communities at risk from flooding and erosion</p>
<p>2.4 Care for cultural sites after a severe disturbance</p>	<p>2.4.1 Coordinate with Tribal communities to determine what their priorities and preferences are for addressing areas of concern. 2.4.2 Remove hazardous trees and debris from cultural sites after fires, storms, or high wind events. 2.4.3 Evaluate and restore eroded or damaged areas after a flood.</p>
<p>2.5 Establish and maintain strategic fuelbreaks to minimize the risk of uncharacteristic, high-severity fire in montane forests</p>	<p>2.5.1 Prioritize fuelbreaks in montane forest based on the criteria given for strategic fuelbreaks 2.5.2 Create shaded fuelbreaks in strategic places in montane forests by reducing surface fuels, increasing base to crown height and opening the canopy through tree removal 2.5.3 Utilize strategic fuelbreaks to protect specially designated (e.g. wilderness) or high value (e.g. refugia) areas where forest health activities are not permissible 2.5.4 Ensure fuel breaks are not located within key biodiversity areas, important plant areas, or other sensitive habitats. 2.5.5 Reduce ignition potential in fuelbreaks through regular maintenance, including invasive species management 2.5.6 Consider ways to reduce the opportunity for illegal trespass and undesirable recreation in fuelbreaks.</p>
<p>2.6 Promptly revegetate after disturbance to support forest regeneration and to mitigate postfire conditions, in order to promote soil retention and reduce erosion risk</p>	<p>2.6.1 Initiate replanting within original forest footprint within 1-3 years of disturbance. 2.6.2 Support natural regeneration by protecting surviving trees as conifer seed sources 2.6.3 Prioritize reforestation where natural regeneration is at risk due to large areas of high severity fire effects. 2.6.4 Design of restoration plantings should always be informed by climate projections to match species tolerances to expected future conditions and to ensure effective and efficient use of project resources. 2.6.5 Use climate-adapted seed tools to identify appropriate seed lots based on climate conditions rather than geography 2.6.6 Plan for and secure funding to support multi-year planting to increase chances of intercepting high rainfall years 2.6.7 Tactics to improve seedling survival include: correct seedling handling, taking advantage of rain events, site preparation and mechanical treatments</p>

	<p>2.6.8 Adjust seasonal planting schedules and other aspects of management according to current drought conditions.</p> <p>2.6.9 Designate certain locations for managing tree competition with aggressive shrubs such as <i>Ceanothus</i></p> <p>2.6.10 Consider utilizing mesic microsites to enhance reforestation success. These microsites may take the form of natural features like rocks, shallow depressions or downed wood, and use of nurse plants.</p> <p>2.6.11 Prioritize replanting in natural forests before investing in plantations, especially in areas where plantations were established within chaparral and the chaparral is recovering following disturbance.</p>
<p>2.7 Consider multiple options for biomass disposal.</p>	<p>2.7.1 Avoid chip accumulation during chipping.</p> <p>2.7.2 Seek opportunities for long-term carbon storage from biomass removal.</p> <p>2.7.3 During pile-and-burn operations, avoid leaving unburned piles for extended periods.</p>

Strategy 3. Reduce establishment, spread, impact of biological stressors

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
<p>3.1 Maintain or improve the ability of forests to resist insect pests</p>	<p>3.1.1 Consult with local experts for updated information on current local risk before planning and implementation.</p> <p>3.1.2 To increase tree resilience, reduce density targets from current levels to support ability to sustain insect damage.</p> <p>3.1.3 Incorporate sanitation practices into projects to resist the spread of insect pests through cut wood</p> <p>3.1.4 Conduct or participate in programs for early detection and treatment of invasive pests such as GSOB and invasive shothole borer</p> <p>3.1.5 In locations where GSOB infestation is advanced, with a low probability of reducing overall infestation levels through management, managers may choose to focus on maintaining genetic diversity through promoting resprouting (coppicing).</p> <p>3.1.6 Increase education efforts on the role of firewood movement in the establishment of destructive invasive pests.</p>
<p>3.2 Minimize the risk of the introduction and establishment of invasive plants and remove existing invasive species</p>	<p>3.2.1 Before planned disturbances: implement weed reduction activities within project areas prior to undertaking ground-disturbing activities</p> <p>3.2.2 Understanding the biology and phenology of nonnative species can help with effective management.</p>

	<p>3.2.3 If understory is currently invaded: high intensity broadcast burns could be used to reduce nonnative propagules.</p> <p>3.2.4 If currently no nonnatives present at the site: emphasize precautions to reduce nonnative introduction (clean equipment, minimize surface disturbance, reduce vehicle access, etc)</p> <p>3.2.5 After disturbance events: conduct invasive species monitoring and control treatments</p> <p>3.2.6 Consider potential of adjacent developed areas and recreation access to introduce invasive species.</p> <p>3.2.7 In areas where invasives are managed with annual treatment, strengthen funding and capacity to ensure uninterrupted annual treatments</p> <p>3.2.8 Include perennial understory species in restoration projects to resist new invasive establishment</p>
<p>3.3 Manage herbivory to promote regeneration of desired species</p>	<p>3.3.1 In areas where grazing is utilized, minimize spread of nonnative species and support perennial native species by following forage utilization standards on a consistent, annual basis.</p> <p>3.3.2 Goat grazing may be a useful alternative to livestock in some locations</p> <p>3.3.3 In areas with dense populations of nonnative species, shift grazing earlier, during the peak growth season of annual nonnatives and remove before peak perennial growth.</p>
<p>3.4 Manage pathogen spread</p>	<p>3.4.1 Use a certified clean nursery to source planting material for projects to avoid introduction of fungal species.</p> <p>3.4.2 Reforestation projects should mix pine and fir seedlings within planting units to limit the spread of Annosus root rot.</p> <p>3.4.3 Incorporate sanitation practices into projects to resist the spread of infection through cut wood.</p> <p>3.4.4 Look for opportunities to use prescribed fire to control alternate host species</p>

Strategy 4. Maintain and enhance species diversity and forest structural heterogeneity

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
<p>4.1 Promote tree age- and size-class diversity and spatial heterogeneity in forests.</p>	<p>4.1.1 Prioritize thinning in even-aged and/or single species forest stands to create structural diversity.</p> <p>4.1.2 Utilize variable density tree thinning to increase adaptability by maximizing the potential for a variety of survivorship pathways.</p>

	<p>4.1.3 Retain or recruit shade-intolerant tree species into lower diameter classes through individual tree and group (clump) selection.</p> <p>4.1.4 Create gaps/openings appropriate for the forest type</p>
4.2 Maintain and restore diversity of native species	<p>4.2.1 Plant greater variety of conifers along with yellow pines (Coulter, Incense Cedar)</p> <p>4.2.2 Plant oaks to supplement natural regeneration</p> <p>4.2.3 Conduct monitoring and control for understory invasive species in new canopy openings.</p> <p>4.2.4 Engage with tribes in conservation of culturally significant species</p>
4.3 Retain biological and cultural legacies	<p>4.3.1 Protect GSOB-free legacy oaks and high-value sites.</p> <p>4.3.2 Preferentially retain snags and trees with morphological old growth characteristics instead of relying on diameter caps</p> <p>4.3.3 Support mycorrhizal networks by maintaining large and old-growth trees.</p> <p>4.3.4 Support and protect natural regeneration for both shade-intolerant conifers and oaks.</p> <p>4.3.5 Thin surrounding vegetation around legacy trees</p> <p>4.3.6 Develop strategies for protecting legacy trees during prescribed fire operations.</p>
4.4 Special management designations protect and call attention to the unique biological resources in montane forests	<p>4.4.1 Protect lands and reserves with special designations by prioritizing management that maintains ecosystem and cultural diversity</p> <p>4.4.2 Coordinate with State and Federal 30x30 programs</p> <p>4.4.3 Coordinate with land conservancies that seek to acquire and protect Native American ancestral lands</p>
4.5 Consider multiple options for biomass utilization taking into account the beneficial links between woody biomass, heterogeneity and species diversity	<p>4.5.1 Use chipping only where there is a positive ecological benefit.</p> <p>4.5.2 Maintain patches of downed woody debris.</p> <p>4.5.3 Use woody material to recover and repair disturbed areas where vegetation has recently been cleared.</p>

Strategy 5. Maintain or create opportunities for sites or communities of concern to withstand stressors in refugia

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
5.1 Identify stressors on refugial areas, and address them through active management	5.1.1 Use available species and climate models to define refugia where target species should be proactively maintained.

	<p>5.1.2 Reduce heavy recreation activity and road access in refugia areas</p> <p>5.1.3 Within climate refugia, especially where there are existing values at risk due to current condition, consider prioritizing management in areas that are prone to high intensity fire</p> <p>5.1.4 Within refugia, reduce drought stress where possible by modifying landscapes to retain water or promote infiltration.</p>
5.2 Prioritize and maintain sensitive or at-risk species or communities	<p>5.2.1 Treat operable canyons and slopes with Bigcone Douglas-fir to create refugia from fire.</p> <p>5.2.2 Identify GSOB-free Black Oak stands and commit funds for monitoring and suppression treatments</p> <p>5.2.3 Include wet meadows in prescribed fires as possible to remove encroaching woody species</p> <p>5.2.4 Include riparian forest in prescribed fires to protect mature forest from crown fire</p> <p>5.2.5 Restore and maintain riparian corridors for high vegetation moisture levels</p> <p>5.2.6 Collaborate with Indigenous communities to identify, protect, and maintain access to important gathering areas and sacred sites through management that recognizes and incorporates Indigenous stewardship practices</p> <p>5.2.7 Establish fuel breaks around at-risk species and stands (example: a postfire stand where regeneration of a rare cypress species is at seedling stage).</p> <p>5.2.8 Manage mesic microsites as refugia for sensitive species</p>
5.3 Bank genetic material for at-risk or sensitive species	<p>5.3.1 Develop ex-situ plantings and seed farms.</p> <p>5.3.2 Develop collections of seeds or genetic material for long-term storage</p>

Strategy 6. Use redundancy and connectivity to maintain dynamic relationships in a changing landscape

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
6.1 Ensure redundancy of uncommon ecosystems or rare species assemblages	<p>6.1.1 Identify uncommon ecosystems and rare assemblages, such as high-elevation limber pine, aspen, rare cypress stands, patches of big-cone Douglas fir, and pebble plains.</p> <p>6.1.2 Evaluate and manage the potential risks to uncommon ecosystems and rare assemblages with landscape-scale management plans</p> <p>6.1.3 Prioritize management of rare or protected species such as the California Spotted Owl</p>

	<p>6.1.4 Partner with neighbors to develop landscape-scale management plans that establish management goals for uncommon ecosystems or rare species assemblages that can be carried out across redundant locations under management by different organizations.</p>
<p>6.2 Establish and enhance connectivity among rare assemblages where connectivity would allow for recolonization after disturbance events or migration to adapt to changing climatic conditions</p>	<p>6.2.1 Consider management actions such as restoration that will enhance connectivity among habitats that host unique ecosystems or rare species assemblages to support recolonization and/or adaptation as conditions change.</p> <p>6.2.2 Maintain gene flow using assisted migration tools if necessary.</p> <p>6.2.3 Where there are specific threats to unique ecosystems or rare species assemblages from stressors such as wildfire, pests, or disease that can be spread through connected landscapes, consider management actions that could limit the connectivity of those stressors across the landscape (such as stand thinning).</p>
<p>6.3 Support structural and functional redundancy at a landscape scale by restoring heterogeneity in similar patches and in patches that contribute to critical ecosystem processes such as hydrologic functioning.</p>	<p>6.3.1 Prioritize treatments to reduce the risk of stand replacing fire using similar management targets for multiple sites across the landscape with similar species or communities.</p> <p>6.3.2 Consider replicating management actions across areas that contribute to critical ecosystem functioning such as springs, the headwaters of major waterways, or landscapes surrounding these hydrologic systems to reduce the impacts of stressors and to enhance recovery from disturbance across the landscape.</p> <p>6.3.3 Create management units focused on landscape features that have been shown to provide some degree of buffering from the impacts of climate change or can support adaptation to those changing conditions</p> <p>6.3.4 Restore heterogeneous forest structure by creating clusters and gaps of trees.</p> <p>6.3.5 Restore disturbance regimes to multiple redundant systems across the landscape, particularly for systems that are at risk from widespread stressors.</p> <p>6.3.6 Where there is uncertainty about optimal treatment types or approaches that may best maintain ecosystem functioning, consider testing strategies in a subset of redundant systems to allow for comparison and adaptive management.</p>
<p>6.4 Consider landscape dynamics in planning management actions for redundancy and connectivity</p>	<p>6.4.1 Incorporate flexibility into management plans to allow for adjustments to scheduling and treatment type to adapt to dynamic conditions</p>

	<p>6.4.2 Evaluate the landscape of proposed or completed treatments through the lens of seasonal and interannual dynamics to ensure there is redundancy and connectivity among areas at risk that are planned for treatment so they can best accommodate changing conditions</p> <p>6.4.3 Consider how landscape dynamics may affect proposed management actions to avoid maladaptation and negative impacts, being mindful of how connectivity to adjacent areas may affect risk and recovery</p> <p>6.4.4 Evaluate the potential impacts of changing climatic conditions on habitat quality and ecosystem function, prioritizing management of at-risk redundant areas and connectivity to buffer dynamic conditions</p> <p>6.4.5 Consider seasonal closures to intermittent streams that provide sensitive species habitat when running but also have a conflict with human use patterns</p> <p>6.4.6 Seek out traditional and/or cultural knowledge regarding movement of beings</p> <p>6.4.7 During reforestation plantings, select stock that maintains genetic diversity and gene flow at landscape scale to allow for a greater degree of adaptive capacity to landscape dynamics over both the short- and long-term</p>
<p>6.5 Plan for redundancy and connectivity among refugia to ensure a single refugium does not result in a dead end for any species or community</p>	<p>6.5.1 Prioritize protection and management of mesic pockets to maintain relict species</p> <p>6.5.2 Map and assess connectivity and redundancy of refugia to ensure prioritization of refugia areas that are hubs of connectivity or unique in character</p>

Strategy 7. Sustain fundamental ecological and cultural functions

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
<p>7.1 Restore/maintain fire in fire adapted systems.</p>	<p>7.1.1 Focus on reduction of hazardous fuel loading in order to enable reintroduction of fire.</p> <p>7.1.2 Accept a greater range of fire effects from prescribed burns. If prescribed fire is too cool, it does not produce desired ecological effects.</p> <p>7.1.3 Seek opportunities to experiment with prescribed fire within the historical burn season</p> <p>7.1.4 Avoid accumulation of chipped material to avoid excessive soil heating and residence time and expedite even distribution of follow-up treatments.</p>

	<p>7.1.5 Incorporate drought consideration into prescribed burn planning, such as creating a Go/No Go process based on an index such as Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI).</p> <p>7.1.6 Rake around tree bases during drought years.</p> <p>7.1.7 Develop a maintenance plan that guides repeated rounds of mechanical and fire treatments.</p> <p>7.1.8 Revitalize and maintain cultural use of fire as a stewardship practice</p>
7.2 Build resilience to drought stress	<p>7.2.1 Provide density targets for conifers and oaks that are based on NRV by forest community type</p> <p>7.2.2 Incorporate stand heterogeneity by adjusting density targets by aspect and slope positioning into project design</p> <p>7.2.3 Provide targets for shrub cover to encourage conifer and oak recruitment</p> <p>7.2.4 Collaborate with Tribal communities to incorporate traditional stewardship practices that restore hydrologic function and increase moisture availability to forest stands during periods of drought.</p>
7.3 Restore/maintain carbon sinks	<p>7.3.1 Retain large trees as important carbon sinks</p> <p>7.3.2 Reduce likelihood of complete carbon loss by prioritizing mechanical thinning in areas of important carbon stocks</p> <p>7.3.3 Prioritize reforestation in areas where woody biomass has been severely reduced (e.g. type-converted to shrub or grass) and natural regeneration is likely to fail.</p> <p>7.3.4 Where possible, design forest treatments to promote natural regeneration for future carbon uptake</p> <p>7.3.5 In areas where plantations have been lost to fire or drought, consider letting them naturally convert to shrub dominance and invest in reforestation in areas with a higher likelihood of tree survival</p>
7.4 Retain and enhance genetic diversity	<p>7.4.1 Work collaboratively to develop robust seed sources and banks for the region</p> <p>7.4.2 Develop seed collections from a wide geographic range, from not just lower-elevation bands but a range of topographic positions and distances from the coast.</p> <p>7.4.3 Collect and store genetic material from a diversity of tree species within the region</p> <p>7.4.4 Explore the limits of drought-tolerance in genotypically similar seed sources for Ponderosa across the Southwest</p> <p>7.4.5 Identify individuals that are resistant to known diseases and pests and create seed collections from them.</p>

	<p>7.4.6 Work with Tribal communities to identify genetic lineages of important plants used for food, fiber, and medicine that should be collected and stored for conservation purposes.</p>
<p>7.5 Maintain or restore hydrology</p>	<p>7.5.1 During project planning, identify whether projects are likely to increase or decrease surface flows and have indirect effects on groundwater recharge.</p> <p>7.5.2 Managers need to fully participate in CA Groundwater Sustainability Act planning processes in order to balance beneficial human uses of source water areas.</p> <p>7.5.3 Managers should engage with the CA Water Board and Army Corps of Engineers to maintain permits and water quality regulatory compliance</p> <p>7.5.4 Natural resource specialists and project/contract managers should manage Best Management Practices in partnership</p> <p>7.5.5 Seek opportunities for floodplain, meadow, and wetland restoration to build natural resilience to a range of surface water flows and support groundwater infiltration</p> <p>7.5.6 Built infrastructure— including road-stream crossings, check dams, and culverts— needs to accommodate projected high and low flows and permit aquatic and terrestrial beings to pass between upstream and downstream water sources</p> <p>7.5.7 With warming temperatures, maintaining the right type and amount of canopy cover in riparian areas will become increasingly important for aquatic species</p> <p>7.5.8 Engage in discussions with Tribal communities about the hydrologic issues they face, beneficial uses they are working to maintain, and traditional approaches to managing surface water and groundwater</p>
<p>7.6 Reduce impacts to soils and nutrient cycling</p>	<p>7.6.1 Plan for seasonal adjustments to ground disturbing activities in response to storms or drought</p> <p>7.6.2 Follow best management practices to minimize soil compaction and ground disturbance impacts during forest management activities</p> <p>7.6.3 Retain topsoil</p> <p>7.6.4 Minimize postfire impacts by addressing suppression damages and damages or new threats created by the fire itself</p> <p>7.6.5 Avoid excessive nutrient inputs</p>
<p>7.7 Maintain and revitalize cultural approaches to harvesting and caretaking.</p>	<p>7.7.1 Promote sustainable harvest techniques informed by traditional practices with guidance from local native practitioners</p> <p>7.7.2 Remove weak or sick trees during forest management activities to leave the stronger, healthier individuals behind</p>

	<p>7.7.3 Use honorable harvest practices when gathering non-timber forest products to give back from what is taken, for example to gather and re-plant seeds or propagules for the next harvest</p> <p>7.7.4 Support co-stewardship and harvesting in a good way, following guidance from Tribal practitioners and culture bearers, such as taking only what you need and leaving enough to sustain a population</p>
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Strategy 8. Expand efforts with native species in existing habitats

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics, with regional considerations
<p>8.1 Prioritize restoration for transformation with culturally important species, engaging in co-management with local Tribes and Indigenous communities</p>	<p>8.1.1 Collaborate with Tribes to identify potential species and sites that would achieve multiple benefits</p> <p>8.1.2 Be open to intensive management strategies that may be required to establish sustainable populations.</p> <p>8.1.3 Provide funding and frequent, authentic opportunities to co-manage prioritized culturally important species and habitats</p> <p>8.1.4 Enable and support traditional practices of tending, gathering, and cultural burning</p>
<p>8.2 Favor or restore native species that are expected to be adapted to future conditions and disfavor maladapted species</p>	<p>8.2.1 Expand research-based efforts to identify genotypes of native tree species better adapted to drier and warmer climatic conditions.</p> <p>8.2.2 Treat high elevation Bigcone Douglas-fir and disfavor isolated low-elevation occurrences.</p> <p>8.2.3 Establish and encourage closed-cone pines for future higher severity fire regimes.</p> <p>8.2.4 Expand the capacity for restoration plantings of Engelmann Oak, Canyon Live Oak, and other oaks that are resistant or less susceptible to GSOB.</p>
<p>8.3 Establish or encourage new mixes of native species with current ranges within close proximity</p>	<p>8.3.1 Experiment with species native to Southern California</p> <p>8.3.2 Remain open to novel combinations of species.</p>
<p>8.4 Protect seedlings and saplings through vulnerable early life stages</p>	<p>8.4.1 Protect oak regeneration.</p> <p>8.4.2 Plant to take advantage of precipitation events and reduce drought mortality.</p> <p>8.4.3 Stronger focus on utilizing microsites (deep soils, cooler, wetter, dead stumps).</p>

	8.4.4 Protect restoration efforts by leveraging barriers between plantings and ignition sources
8.5 Prioritize establishing populations of at-risk species in locations determined to be climate refugia, where species may be buffered from the impacts of climate change	8.5.1 Consider establishing rare understory species in sites with a higher probability of providing longer-term refuge

Strategy 9. Plan for further change

Adaptation Menu Approach	Tactics
9.1 Identify goals, objectives, and tactics using co-production.	<p>9.1.1 Develop management goals and objectives that include both social and ecological components</p> <p>9.1.2 Focus on co-production of goals and objectives with partners.</p> <p>9.1.3 When designing tactics, also focus on co-production of tactics with partners.</p>
9.2 Include indigenous knowledge as a primary consideration from early in the decision-making process	<p>9.2.1 Collaborate with Tribal natural resources managers and elders to identify acceptable ecosystem futures</p> <p>9.2.2 Support reciprocity by providing financial compensation.</p>
9.3 Identify opportunities to pilot new strategies for both conifer and hardwood species	<p>9.3.1 Identify locations for deliberate and careful experimentation</p> <p>9.3.2 Document trials, conduct follow-up monitoring, and provide reporting</p> <p>9.3.3 Examine analogous Mediterranean landscapes that are further into warming and drying (i.e. Baja Mexico, oak woodlands in Spain) for experimental management strategies</p>
9.4 Introduce species that are expected to be adapted to future conditions.	<p>9.4.1 Pinyon pine-juniper</p> <p>9.4.2 Gray pine</p> <p>9.4.3 Southwestern oaks.</p>

Strategy 1. Support community engagement in montane forest conservation

Given that the threats currently facing southern California's montane forests are largely the result of past management and human intervention, the inclusion of diverse community perspectives is critical for the success of conservation planning and action for these systems. Therefore, the first strategy focuses on building and maintaining a community of practice focused on montane forest conservation, with a particular emphasis on Tribal engagement. These approaches and tactics were developed using the NIACS Tribal Climate Adaptation Menu as a starting point and have been further developed with local input through Tribal-focused workshops.

Approach 1.1 Consider mindful practices of reciprocity.

Meaningful and long-lasting relationships with communities require a commitment to establishing a strong foundation built on respect, reciprocity, and responsibility. Meaningful inclusion of Tribal points of view can assist with creating pathways forward for collaboration and potential management approaches should be evaluated in part by what Tribes will gain from them. Showing appreciation for reciprocal exchanges in culturally informed ways should always be built into the relationship.

Tactics:

1.1.1 Provide gifts or compensation when seeking guidance or knowledge from elders or community members. The knowledge shared has important value to successful conservation and should be compensated accordingly. Gifts need to be culturally informed, so that gifts are offered and received in a good way. When entering into new relationships, individuals with less experience and knowledge in culturally informed relationship-building should consult first with individuals with more experience.

1.1.2 Share data and results of climate change assessments and adaptation projects with the local community. Sharing results is important for all communities. For Tribal communities, data sovereignty is paramount and requires early and frequent conversations during collaborations and project development. Discussions should consider what information will be shared and how, including data formats and storage, usage, and sharing. Tribal communities should also be asked about ways in which they do not want data used.

1.1.3 Ensure that all who share knowledge, such as teachers, elders, and all contributors are credited in presentations, public documents, and materials. This tactic is a simple and necessary way to acknowledge collaborative relationships and exchanges of knowledge. Overlooking it, even by accident, has a lasting negative impact.

1.1.4 Teach harvesting in a good way, such as taking only what you need and leaving enough to sustain the population. Most guidelines limit sampling to no more than 5% of the current season seed either from a population or on a per-plant basis. This is an example of how land management should incorporate reciprocity with non-human beings.

Approach 1.2 Consult cultural leaders, key community members, and elders.

Local, cultural, and historical knowledges and practices are valuable in guiding stewardship and informing climate adaptation efforts. However, these types of knowledge have not always been sought out or

valued in the ways that western science is valued. In particular, when working to incorporate knowledges and perspectives from Tribal communities, it is imperative to be mindful of the history of broken trust, and it will be important to invest time into relationship- and trust-building. The benefits resulting from taking the time to consult with the community will be more informed decisions and greater community support for management actions.

Tactics:

1.2.1 Events and access to engage in stewardship of ancestral lands can help to change existing adversarial relationships with Indigenous communities. Approach Tribes individually and ask which types of engagement they would prefer, whether conducting site field trips, gatherings, structured visits, or other types of meetings. Offer to provide community meeting support such as note-taking and methods of increasing accessibility. Listen to Tribal priorities.

1.2.2 Work with Tribal leaders and members to identify knowledgeable individuals in the community, such as elders, and ask for guidance for how to consult with them in a good way. First impressions have lasting power.

1.2.3 Conduct community engagement workshops to learn about past environmental (especially climate-related) changes using specific local examples or important resources as discussion points.

1.2.4 Work with Indigenous stewards to understand observed impacts to non-human relatives (plants and animals) from storm events, drought, or other aspects of changing climate. When considering management decisions that would impact aspects of stewardship and gathering such as timing or processes, the community should be involved through the entire decision-making process.

Approach 1.3 Understand the human and landscape history of local communities. Ask for guidance about the context and stories for places that are being considered for active management. The Tribal Climate Adaptation Menu puts it well: “The history of the community and the land can inform land management decisions, and it is worth investing time and attention to cultivate a deeper understanding... before making management decisions.”

Tactics:

1.3.1 Identify and meet with Tribal Historic Preservation Officers in order to understand the history of the local community.

1.3.2 Work in a good way with Tribes to make connections with traditional stories and teaching and to forge insights focused on climate change.

Approach 1.4 Maintain and revitalize traditional relationships and resource uses. These are an important entry point for individuals and are pathways for enabling more engagement with both nature and culture.

Tactics:

1.4.1 Support educational programs for engaging youth. Educational programs should use outdoor classrooms as much as possible and be guided by Tribal communities. Educational

topics may include bringing awareness to cultural burning, ethnobotany practices, and the importance of soil health, among other potential topics, and should include a climate change component. Themes can include, in addition to caretaking the lands, how to be respectful, responsible, and reciprocal in relationship with the lands and nonhuman beings.

1.4.2 Create opportunities for intergenerational teaching and guidance. These can include involving youth in traditional harvesting activities, such as gathering materials for basketry, and the harvest of acorns or prickly pear fruits. It could also include cultural burning practices, such as maintenance burning in acorn harvest sites.

1.4.3 Create opportunities for cross-cultural learning, experiences, and partnerships to help non-Tribal forest management practitioners better understand and incorporate Indigenous relationships with the land and non-human relatives as well as traditional stewardship practices into their efforts.

1.4.4 Preserve threatened resources to ensure that traditional crafts, medicines, and relationships can continue in a changing environment.

Approach 1.5 Participate in local- and landscape-level management decisions with partner agencies, with the intention of advancing co-stewardship and/or co-management.

Tactics:

1.5.1 Fully utilize existing funded and non-funded agreements (such as Memoranda of Understanding, MOU), or develop new agreements as part of advancing co-stewardship of ancestral lands. Agencies are encouraged to push boundaries to develop more meaningful instruments and models for co-management.

1.5.2 Forest management practitioners should engage Tribes at the outset of the decision-making process, when project development is in early stages. Management organizations should also ensure that the right connections are being made and that the best communication methods (email, written letters) are being used.

1.5.3 Tribes can request or utilize a Tribal liaison to increase communication with partner agencies on climate change planning.

Strategy 2. Reduce the risk and long-term impacts of severe disturbances

Severe disturbances such as wildfire, drought, and flooding are currently driving forest management in forests. As this dynamic is unlikely to change in the foreseeable future, the adaptation menu prioritizes approaches for reducing the risk and impacts of these disturbances. Irreversible impacts are of great concern. For example, during menu workshops for Tribal participants, there were concerns about impacts such as the loss of gathering areas, increased barriers to resource use, type conversion, and species extinctions. In response, this strategy includes both pre- and post-disturbance management approaches. As with other sections of the menu, using an objective-oriented process will provide managers with some

of the guidance needed to select among different management approaches. None of these disturbances observe management boundaries, and management needs to be coordinated across land ownerships.

Approach 2.1 Reduce the risk or severity of wildfire. Recent widespread observations of larger and more severe fire events and well-founded concerns of long-term forest loss have confronted managers with an urgent need for more effective management strategies and approaches. While federal and state entities work to create and fund the organizational structures needed to increase overall pace and scale of efforts to increase forest resilience, all managers can contribute by implementing fuels management on the forestlands they manage. In locations where the reintroduction of fire is a feasible goal, this will often require multiple initial entries in forest stands (e.g. thinning followed by pile burning and broadcast burning). After the initial entries, maintenance activities should be anticipated and implemented. This approach also considers tactics for managing both forest and built environments. In the wildland-urban interface, neither the forest nor the built environment can be managed in isolation.

Tactics:

2.1.1 Reduce fuel continuity and ladder fuels (e.g. reduce surface fuels, increase canopy base height, reduce canopy bulk density, Valliant et al 2009). Forest treatments that include a combination of thinning and prescribed fire are the most effective at reducing subsequent fire severity, tree mortality, and the likelihood of passive crown fire (Kalies et al. 2016, Safford et al. 2012, Stephens et al. 2009). There is a high degree of scientific consensus that the combined effects of thinning plus prescribed burning consistently reduce the potential for severe wildfire across a broad range of forest types and conditions (Prichard et al. 2021). In contrast, thinning or prescribed fire alone tend to have less of an effect or none at all depending on conditions at the time of wildfire. In areas where conditions are not yet safe for broadcast burning, pile burning should be emphasized to remove surface fuels after thinning and to support future broadcast burning. Management targets can be derived from studies of natural range of variation and take into account local biotic and abiotic factors (e.g. slope, aspect, elevation).

2.1.2. Prioritize management treatments in strategic areas of highest risk of uncharacteristic fire effects, such as stand-replacing fire. These may include areas of high tree density and fuel accumulation resulting from fire suppression. Risk reduction may also be a priority in forested areas abutting chaparral or subalpine forest. Determining factors include vegetation type and condition, site productivity and management history.

2.1.3 Prioritize fuels treatments in strategic areas of highest community risk. Determining factors include proximity to forested land, travel time for fire response, and community vulnerability. Maintain defensible space around structures up to 100 ft depending on slope and vegetation. Studies indicate that distances greater than 100 ft do not convey increased protection benefit (Syphard et al 2013).

2.1.4 Implement fire-conscious planning and home hardening measures for structures. The University of California Agricultural and Natural Resources Cooperative Extension is a good source of information. For example, SAFE Landscapes is a project of the Natural Resources Program based in Los Angeles and Ventura County Cooperative Extension that [provides information for making structures more resistant to fire](#).

2.1.5 Coordinate with utility companies to reduce the likelihood of ignition from their infrastructure. One of the vulnerabilities associated with powerline fuelbreaks is increased hazard from flashy fuels such as nonnative annual grasses.

2.1.6 Engage with the public about community exposure and susceptibility and the hazards associated with the current ecosystem condition. Develop outreach materials that describe the dual benefit of fuels reduction for community protection and forest health/persistence.

Approach 2.2 Reduce the risk of severe reburns in existing high severity fire footprints.

This approach includes tactics for management of both ignition sources and fuel types. It focuses on strategically reducing high-severity fire risk in areas affected by recent burns.

Tactics:

2.2.1 Manage shrub cover, coarse woody debris, and snag density in ecologically sound ways within recovering forest stands. Management targets can be derived from studies of natural range of variation and take into account local biotic and abiotic factors (e.g. slope, aspect, elevation) as well as potential ignition sources and fire spread patterns. Areas burned once at moderate to high severity have been found to support fuel types (thick shrub cover, many standing snags) that reburn at high severity in subsequent climate-driven fires, which sets back recovery and increases probability of long-term forest loss (Lydersen et al. 2019). NRV-based reductions in understory shrub cover and increased heterogeneity in the subcanopy (between 2-8 m in height) are recommended (Steel et al. 2021) within fire footprints.

2.2.2 Conduct public awareness engagements and campaigns to address common ignition sources. Ongoing public awareness campaigns will benefit from reinforcing efforts.

Approach 2.3 Alter forest structure to reduce severity or extent of extreme weather events (e.g. drought, flooding, erosion). This approach is relevant to pre- and postfire situations. High stand densities resulting from fire exclusion put stands at risk of drought mortality and also put natural and human resources at risk from flooding and erosion after severe fire. This is especially of concern where topography and infrastructure placement put communities at risk.

Tactics:

2.3.1 Enhance structural heterogeneity and reduce inter-tree competition through use of variable density thinning. At high stand densities, trees compete for resources, resulting in reduced vigor and increased tree mortality from insufficient space, moisture, or nutrients. Reduction in stand densities is needed to increase the resilience of the stand to extreme weather events. Variable density thinning is an effective tactic for re-creating both stand densities and heterogeneity characteristic of pre-settlement stand conditions, including clumps, widely spaced individual trees, and canopy gaps. Structural heterogeneity not only increases forest resiliency by reducing competition but maintains the multiple age classes needed to replace trees lost to mortality.

2.3.2 Identify locations where the alignment of topography and structures put communities at risk from flooding and erosion. Prioritize management in locations where community risk overlaps with forest vulnerability to uncharacteristic fire effects in order to reduce potential effects to human dominated communities.

Approach 2.4 Care for cultural sites after a severe disturbance. This approach focuses on appropriately caring for and protecting cultural sites and uses after severe disturbances. A range of disturbance events, such as fires, storms, wind events, or floods can damage cultural sites. Land managers will be focused on implementing response efforts after the event, and there is a risk that those efforts may occur without recognition of cultural sites and special places. Ensuring that cultural sites are recognized during post-disturbance planning and implementation will maintain the values and relationships within cultural sites.

Tactics:

2.4.1 Coordinate with Tribal communities to determine what their priorities and preferences are for addressing areas of concern.

2.4.2 Remove hazardous trees and debris from cultural sites after fires, storms, or high wind events. The use of soil-disturbing equipment should be evaluated beforehand to protect cultural sites.

2.4.3 Evaluate and restore eroded or damaged areas after a flood. Restoration may include revegetation.

Approach 2.5 Establish and maintain strategic fuelbreaks to minimize the risk of uncharacteristic, high-severity fire in montane forests. Fuelbreaks are typically linear strips of vegetation where fuel volume has been reduced. They are not designed to stop fire; rather, they provide fire crews access and relative safety when implementing wildfire suppression activities. This approach focuses on fuelbreaks in montane forest, not on fuelbreaks in lower-elevation chaparral.

Strategic fuelbreaks are defined in terms of:

- Location: they should be on pathways between known ignition sources and values at risk
- Firefighter safety: avoid placing fuelbreaks in areas where deployment of ground-based firefighting resources is infeasible or dangerous (e.g. midslope, canyons)
- Proximity to fire resources: Travel distances for firefighters should be short
- Regular maintenance occurs: without regular maintenance, fuel breaks become wicks of flashy fuels

When fuelbreaks are strategically placed and maintained, they can help prevent catastrophic losses of at-risk values. Creation and maintenance of fuel breaks comes with the trade-off of net ecological loss, though, and unless each of the criteria above is met, the likelihood that the fuelbreak will be effective is low. Ineffective or extraneous fuelbreaks are unnecessarily destructive (especially to chaparral) and can promote invasion by undesirable plant species, increasing the potential for ignitions. Unmaintained fuelbreaks are also ineffective. Therefore, fuelbreak creation and use should be deployed to a limited extent with careful evaluation of whether the criteria above have been met. If forests are maintained within the natural range of variation for density, they likely will not require additional fuelbreaks.

Tactics:

2.5.1 Prioritize fuelbreaks in montane forest areas based on the criteria given above for strategic fuelbreaks. Work with fire staff to identify strategic locations that will be utilized during fire suppression operations.

2.5.2 Create shaded fuelbreaks in strategic places in montane forests by reducing surface fuels, increasing base-to-crown height and opening the canopy through tree removal (Agee et al 2000). Monitoring the need for maintenance could be especially useful in years of high precipitation and rapid plant growth.

2.5.3 Utilize strategic fuelbreaks to protect specially designated (e.g. wilderness) or high value (e.g. refugia) areas where forest health activities are restricted. Areas with management restrictions can be vulnerable to wildfire, and strategic fuelbreaks may be a useful tool.

2.5.4 Ensure fuel breaks are not located within key biodiversity areas, important plant areas, or other sensitive habitats. By definition, fuelbreaks require regular maintenance and have inherent impacts to vegetation. Regular mechanical disturbance is likely to be incompatible with the ecological needs of sensitive habitats.

2.5.5 Reduce ignition potential in fuelbreaks through regular maintenance, including invasive species management. The fuel loads of unmaintained fuelbreaks are too high to be effective. Many annual non-natives produce flashy fuel loads, and both monitoring for invasives and invasives management should be required as part of regular fuelbreak maintenance.

2.5.6 Fuelbreak creation and the removal of vegetation can enhance opportunities for trespass and undesirable recreation. Consider the effect of these disturbances during planning (e.g. weed spread, ignitions) and develop appropriate measures (e.g. placement of boulders or other natural barriers near access points) to reduce the opportunity for illegal trespass.

Approach 2.6 Promptly revegetate after severe disturbance to support forest regeneration and to mitigate postfire conditions to promote soil retention and reduce erosion risk. Restoration plans will differ greatly depending on whether the intent is to resist change, accommodate change, or enable transformation. Design of revegetation and restoration efforts requires many decision points, and utilizing a process driven by specific goals and objectives will serve to narrow down the options. Allowing management to be driven by goals and objectives can also provide the justification needed for more deterministic management actions. For example, if severe disturbance resets mature forest to an earlier successional stage, such as shrubland, having established goals for preserving forest structure in place will help manage challenges such as strong shrub competition.

Tactics:

2.6.1 Initiate replanting within the original forest footprint within 1-3 years. It can be logistically challenging to fund and plan work on this timeline, but rapid response will likely be met with greater success. Timing is key for successful restoration implementation—the window of opportunity will close as unmanaged vegetation recovery proceeds in disturbed areas. If chaparral has been recovering with a strong regeneration response, after several years the window of opportunity will close, and reforestation should not be attempted. Consistent with 2.6.8,

restoration postponements due to drought status may still need to occur and take precedence in scheduling.

2.6.2 Support natural regeneration by protecting surviving trees as conifer seed sources. Most conifer species produce heavy seeds with limited potential for dispersal (Bonnet et al 2005, Welch et al 2016). Mature seed-producing trees should be a highly valued component of postfire forest resilience. In postfire conditions of high loads of dead and down fuels, surviving trees are also frequently vulnerable to high-severity reburn. The risk of losing existing seed sources can be reduced by reducing tree density through methods such as thinning and pile burning of subdominant trees to NRV levels.

2.6.3 Prioritize reforestation where natural regeneration is at risk due to large areas of high severity fire effects. When patches of high severity fire are greater than 100 acres, the forest can be considered moderately departed from the natural range of variation and extremely departed when patches of high severity burn are greater than 250 acres (Estes et al. 2021). Plant a mosaic of sites to serve as centers of future seed dispersal (i.e. founder stand planting patterns). Reforestation tools like Postfire Conifer Reforestation Planning Tool (PostCRPT) can also be used to identify areas where natural recruitment is unlikely and active reforestation is necessary.

2.6.4 Design of restoration plantings should consider the potential impacts of changing climatic conditions, matching available information about species tolerances to expected future conditions ([from sources such as Cal-Adapt](#)) and to ensure effective and efficient use of project resources. Generally, south-facing slopes, especially at lower elevations, impose greater environmental stress on plantings, and are likely areas of future maximum climate exposure. Even if some of these slopes previously supported mature forest, the seedling and sapling growth stages require more mesic conditions for survival. While presettlement forests were stable enough to rely on natural regeneration when forest openings aligned with adequate rainfall, restoration projects require a greater likelihood of success. Accordingly, practitioners in the region are already limiting investments in attempted restoration of lower-elevation south-facing slopes relative to other sites.

2.6.5 Use climate-adapted seed tools, such as the [USFS Seedlot Selection Tool](#) or [Climate Adapted Seed Tool \(CAST\)](#) to identify appropriate seed lots based on climate conditions rather than geography.

2.6.6 Plan for and secure funding to support multi-year planting to increase chances of intercepting high rainfall years. Southern California already experiences the highest interannual variability in precipitation in the United States, and further increases in variability are likely under climate change scenarios.

2.6.7 Within the reforestation workflow, there are several critical tactics for improving seedling survival. These include correct seedling handling, conducting site preparation, or mechanical grubbing (i.e. removal of competing vegetation; [Stewart 2020](#)). Thinning (reducing the number of competing saplings) can also be done but is often not necessary in this region due to low survival.

2.6.8 Adjust seasonal planting schedules and other aspects of management according to current drought conditions. This tactic includes both scheduling planting to take advantage of rain events, as well as postponing planting by up to a year when drought conditions are unfavorable to planting survival. Seasonal timing is key to planting success.

2.6.9 Designate certain locations for managing tree competition with aggressive shrubs such as *Ceanothus*. In certain sites, *Ceanothus* and other shrubs may respond to severe disturbance with a strong regeneration response that outcompetes conifer regeneration and resets the forest to an earlier successional stage. Having established goals for preserving forest structure in place will provide the needed justification for localized management challenges such as strong shrub competition.

2.6.10 Consider utilizing mesic microsites to enhance reforestation success. These microsites may take the form of natural features like rocks, shallow depressions, or downed wood. Utilizing sporadically growing shrubs as nurse plants to moderate solar radiation and evaporative loss from the soil may also be effective in drier environments like south-facing slopes.

2.6.11 Prioritize replanting in natural forests before investing in plantations, especially in areas where plantations were established within chaparral and the chaparral is recovering following disturbance. Reforestation success is likely to be low in areas that were historically dominated by shrubs.

Approach 2.7 Consider multiple options for biomass disposal. Efforts to increase the pace and scale of forest treatments are producing woody biomass, both coarse woody debris and more fine-scale material. There are a range of uses and disposal options for this material. Woody biomass can be utilized both on- and off-site, with the primary options being chipping, pile-and-burn, biochar, firewood, and trucking to offsite facilities (usually for combustion). These tactics explore the current options for biomass while avoiding negative consequences such as adding deep, homogeneous layers of fuels to the soil surface.

Tactics:

2.7.1 During chipping, avoid chip accumulation. Chips accumulate quickly in the immediate vicinity of the chipper. However, chip beds should not be continuous over large areas, and should not exceed a depth of 3 inches (7.5 cm). The creation of deep and/or continuous chip beds can have negative consequences. The timely reintroduction of prescribed fire can be delayed or complicated by the risks created by deep chips. If a wildfire passes through the site before prescribed fire can be implemented, the severity of fire effects to the soil surface and seedbank will be increased.

2.7.2 Seek opportunities for long-term carbon storage from biomass removal. Burning biomass releases carbon emissions to the atmosphere, contributing to climate warming. Prioritizing the local use and disposal of biomass in ways that minimize carbon emissions should be a consideration in projects that generate biomass. This includes options such as biochar production, with deposition of the biochar product on- or offsite. Because biochar is a new product, there are knowledge gaps associated with its use that should be a priority for deliberate and careful experimentation. Southern California montane forests are characterized by dry, low-productivity soils and vegetation adapted to those conditions, and the effects of applying a nutrient amendment such as biochar need to be fully examined before wide scale application is recommended.

2.7.3 During pile-and-burn operations, avoid leaving unburned piles for extended periods. Fuels left in the forest will contribute to fire intensity in the event of a wildfire, undoing the original

purpose of treatments and projects. In addition, woody debris left for more than a season will be used and occupied by wildlife, potentially including species with protected status.

Strategy 3. Reduce establishment, spread, impact of biological stressors

Climate-enhanced biological stressors such as invasive species and pest and pathogen outbreaks follow severe disturbance in their urgency for management. Managers are concerned about the potential for impacts from interactions with fire and climate, especially the potential for enhanced rates of tree loss and subsequent losses in habitat and biodiversity. As temperatures warm and drought increases, concerns about severe bark beetle and other forest pest outbreaks and tree loss will be heightened.

With the introduction and spread of nonnative species, consistent treatments and early detection monitoring will be required more frequently to reduce the likelihood of impact to forest ecosystems. Efforts to increase the stability and reliability of annual treatments should focus on strengthening the mechanisms for funding and staff capacity. Where biological stressors are concerned, even one year of missed monitoring or treatment can lead to missed opportunities, increased spread of invasives, and reduced biological control. The creation of invasive pest management plans can help develop management responses that are in accordance with the values and objectives of the land owners.

Approach 3.1 Maintain or improve the ability of forests to resist insect pests. This approach is focused on tactics for supporting forest resilience and addressing known threats.

Tactics:

3.1.1 Consult with local experts (e.g. University of California Agriculture and Natural Resources, County Extension, Resource Conservation Districts and agency staff) for updated information on current local risk before planning and implementation. Local conditions may change rapidly, and projects should be planned with recent and reliable information. Species that may soon become an issue include: emerald ash borer, Mediterranean ash borer, redbay ambrosia beetle, spongy moth, spotted lantern fly, and Asian longhorn beetle.

3.1.2 To increase tree resilience, reduce density targets from current levels to support ability to sustain insect damage. For example, one current recommendation is to reduce stand densities to a Stand Density Index (SDI) value of 100 on south & southwest aspects (Egan. 2020, unpublished data). SDI accounts for the degree of competitive stress within a stand, depending on both stand density and mean tree size. Alternative metrics, such as drawing density targets from the lower end of NRV could also be used.

3.1.3 Incorporate sanitation practices into projects to resist the spread of insect pests through cut wood. For GSOB, sanitation [management practices](#) for tree removal include cutting tree stumps flush to the ground, then stump grinding or debarking, and chipping to < 3 in. (including bark that falls off the tree during felling). Cut stems and branches 4" diameter is recommended to be chipped to prevent insect emergence. Field trials indicate that pile burning can effectively treat large woody debris. Field experiments with prescribed pile burns that peaked at 600 degrees C and had direct flame for 8 minutes with 20 minutes of smoldering resulted in 97% reduction in GSOB emergence (J. Tamm, unpublished data). Pile-burning infested wood to 95% consumption

eliminates the potential for GSOB emergence. No GSOB emergence was detected when temperatures were maintained above 140° F (60° C) for 60 minutes (J. Tamm, personal communication).

3.1.4 Conduct or participate in programs for early detection and treatment of invasive pests such as gold-spotted oak borer and invasive shothole borer. In some locations across the region, invasion is still at an early stage and treatment could be effective. For both GSOB and shothole borer, ground surveys and insect trapping are used to detect insect presence, and chemical treatments can be effective in preventing the mortality of individual high value trees. Where trees are managed with annual treatment, strengthen funding and capacity mechanisms to ensure uninterrupted annual treatments. Utilizing community scientists for early detection monitoring can reduce losses from insect pests while simultaneously raising community awareness of the problem.

3.1.5 In locations where GSOB infestation is advanced, with a low probability of reducing overall infestation levels through management, managers may choose to focus on maintaining genetic diversity through promoting resprouting (coppicing). Promoting resprouting involves cutting dying trees to within 10-18" of the ground to promote regeneration and soil retention. Insecticide also needs to be applied to reduce infestation. This strategy is more effective on trees with moderate canopy mortality (<50%) and is less effective on trees with >50% canopy mortality. Resprouts can quickly grow to the height of a ten year old oak (M. Puzzo, unpublished data).

3.1.6 Increase education efforts on the role of firewood movement in the establishment of destructive invasive pests. Limit firewood movement and engage in GSOB and invasive shothole borer awareness programs. Public awareness campaigns are established at both national and state levels, but their visibility and effectiveness are variable. Organizations with the opportunity to reinforce and refresh existing messaging to the public should do so. Managers should consider connecting with the [California Firewood Task Force](#) to keep up to date on outreach materials and current threats.

Approach 3.2 Minimize the risk of the introduction and establishment of invasive nonnative plants and remove existing invasive species. Climate change is expected to intensify the disturbances that create opportunities for species invasions. As described in the statewide menu [California Forest Adaptation Strategies and Approaches](#), state-level efforts are focused on early detection and rapid response to new invasive species. This focus applies at more localized scales as well. One major area of focus is on slowing the spread of understory species such as cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*), and mustard (*Sisymbrium sp.*) into montane areas with intact understory communities. Occurrences of ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*) at higher elevations than expected have also been observed anecdotally, potentially due to climate warming. Invasive species management and removal approaches can be informed by many communities, including Tribes. Management activities should include communication and outreach to build understanding and support for a wide range of tactics to reduce the establishment, spread, and impact of invasive nonnative species.

Tactics:

3.2.1 Before planned disturbances: implement weed reduction activities within project areas prior to undertaking ground-disturbing activities. This tactic may be used across a range of cover levels

of invasive species and may be applied where intermediate cover levels of invasives have reduced the applicability of the other recommended tactics.

3.2.2 Understanding the biology and phenology of nonnative species can help with effective management. Implementing weed abatement strategies (e.g. mowing, herbicide application, prescribed fire) that match the susceptible life stage for the nonnative will increase success. For many species, targeted removal before seed production is key to reducing abundance and likelihood for seed spread.

3.2.3 If the understory is currently invaded, especially with cheatgrass, hot high intensity broadcast burns could be used to reduce nonnative propagules.

Fire intensity can be increased by delaying burning until later in the season, conducting the burn in the late afternoon, using backing fires to increase residence time. In areas with grazing, deferring grazing operations for a year may help with fuel build up resulting in higher burn intensity. The most effective burn period for many nonnative annual grasses is when the seeds are still attached to the plant and have not yet dispersed.

This tactic is used in locations where dense cheatgrass cover has already been established, and management needs to reduce propagules in the seedbank as well as aboveground cover. This tactic is not recommended for locations with moderate levels of invasive cover, however, as it may create an opportunity for increased invasive cover. In areas with moderate levels of invasion, a layer of wood chips (<3 in. deep) may be used to suppress non-native growth.

3.2.4 If there are currently no nonnatives present at a site: emphasize precautions to reduce nonnative introduction (clean equipment, minimize surface disturbance, reduce vehicle access, etc) and conduct post treatment monitoring. These best management practices are critical for protecting understory species diversity. Invasive propagules carried on management equipment is a common introduction pathway.

3.2.5 After disturbance events: conduct invasive species monitoring and control treatments. Areas that maintained relatively intact understory communities of native species before disturbance should be a priority for monitoring in order to detect new species introductions or significant changes in the existing cover levels of invasives as a result of the disturbance. Types of disturbance events that require follow-up monitoring include management activities such as mechanical thinning and prescribed fire treatments.

3.2.6 Consider the potential of adjacent developed areas and recreation access to introduce invasive species, and provide education materials, signage, or weed check stations for people to inspect their shoes, belongings, and pets prior to entering weed-free areas. Locations adjacent to an established invasive population receive higher propagule pressure than sites buffered by distance to the nearest propagule source and are at higher risk of establishment.

3.2.7 In areas where invasives are managed with annual treatment, strengthen funding and capacity to ensure uninterrupted annual treatments. Efforts to increase the stability and reliability of annual treatments should focus on strengthening the mechanisms for funding and staff capacity. Where biological stressors are concerned, even one year of missed monitoring or

treatment can lead to missed opportunities, increased spread of invasives, and reduced biological control.

3.2.8 Include perennial understory species in restoration projects to resist new invasive establishment. Once established, areas with native perennial species cover can resist invasion. Coordinated treatment of invasive species during the first three years will increase the likelihood of a competitive balance that favors native species (Keeley et al. 1981, Franklin et al. 2006).

Approach 3.3 Manage herbivory to promote regeneration of desired native species.

This approach is focused on maintaining rangeland health by meeting the standards of livestock grazing management.

Tactics:

3.3.1 In areas where livestock grazing is utilized, minimize spread of nonnative species and support perennial native species by following forage utilization standards on a consistent, annual basis. For example, the National Forests in Southern California follow guidelines established in the [Land Management Plan \(Table 3.2\)](#), which include limits on residual dry matter (an indicator of rangeland condition, RDM), as well as percentage-based guidelines for how much woody browse matter and perennial grasses must remain by vegetation type. A quarantine requirement can also be included in contracts to hold animals in one restricted, easily monitored site for a period of a few days before moving on to another location.

3.3.2 Goat grazing may be a useful alternative to livestock in some locations. Goats are frequently used for fuel management in the wildland-urban interface, particularly for fuelbreak maintenance. They are able to reach inaccessible slopes where other forms of weed management would be difficult and are perceived favorably by the public. Goats can target ladder fuels, and don't leave biomass behind that requires further disposal. The downsides are that goats are not as effective in removing annual grass thatch as cattle, there is less published evidence to draw on for guidance, and it can be relatively expensive to lease goats.

3.3.3 In areas with dense populations of nonnative species (such as brome, wildrye, and mustard), shift grazing earlier. Grazing should occur during the peak growth season of annual nonnatives and grazers should be removed before peak native perennial growth. This tactic may be difficult to implement correctly at higher elevations, due to unpredictable montane weather patterns. In areas with a more persistent snowpack, it may be difficult to predict the timing of early growth by annual nonnatives. Having resources available and ready to implement at the right time will be important for success.

Approach 3.4 Manage pathogen spread. This approach draws on established management tactics for the control of fungal pathogens, such as *Heterobasidion annosum*, the fungus that causes Annosus root disease, and white pine blister rust, that weaken trees and increase baseline mortality levels.

Tactics:

3.4.1 Use a certified clean nursery to source planting material for projects to avoid introduction of fungal species. This tactic also applies to *Phytophthora spp.*, which are not true fungi but are readily introduced into native plant communities through restoration plantings.

3.4.2 Reforestation projects should mix pine and fir seedlings within planting units to limit the spread of Annosus root rot. *Heterobasidion annosum* is the pathogen that causes Annosus root disease, the most significant fungal pathogen in the American West. It spreads over short distances through belowground root contacts. Separate fungal strains affect pines vs. firs, so that mixing pines and firs during planting will increase inter-tree distances and decrease the potential for root connections.

3.4.3 Incorporate sanitation practices into projects to resist the spread of infection through cut wood. For fungal diseases such as Annosus root rot (*Heterobasidion annosum*), treatment of cut surfaces with fungicides should be considered. During mechanical thinning projects, minimize tree wounding on trees intended for retention to limit potential for pathogen spread. This tactic focuses on pathogens such as Heterobasidion, which can spread through wounds in the roots and basal portion of the bole.

3.4.4 Look for opportunities to use prescribed fire to control alternate host species. For example, *Ribes spp.* are alternate hosts of white pine blister rust.

Strategy 4. Maintain and enhance species diversity and forest structural heterogeneity

Both species diversity and structural heterogeneity are key to supporting forest resilience to disturbance and providing multiple pathways for forest response to future amplified stressors. They also provide the foundation for more diverse forest understory plant, wildlife, invertebrate, and soil communities. Both diversity and structural heterogeneity support the resilience of important cultural resources, such as plants that are important food, fiber, and medicine for Indigenous communities. Maintaining and supporting cultural uses of a range of species helps to maintain management focus on the diversity and heterogeneity of a forest in balance.

Approach 4.1 Promote tree age- and size-class diversity and spatial heterogeneity in forests. Resilient forests should include clusters of trees, widely spaced individual trees, and canopy gaps to create a diversity of microsite conditions and open spaces for forest regeneration. After a century of fire suppression and concomitant forest densification, existing canopy gaps have filled in, reducing the amount of sunlight that reaches the forest floor and the amount of high-value edge habitat between forest and small openings. Variations in forest structure provide diverse conditions for both understory plant communities and wildlife habitat within forest stands.

Tactics:

4.1.1 Prioritize thinning in even-aged and/or single species forest stands to create structural diversity. Yellow-pine mixed conifer forest stands that provide uniform habitat conditions support less diverse understory communities and are generally of lower habitat quality for wildlife. Forests that lack structural diversity are more uniform in their response to disturbances (drought, pest/disease outbreaks, and wildfire) and are therefore less resilient and at greater risk of losses. Thinning can be used to create structural diversity, increasing spacing among individual trees and establishing canopy gaps. Fire is the preferred method for creating structural diversity, but mechanical methods may be necessary in many locations before fire can be reintroduced due to existing stand densities. To adequately protect trees from drought stress and competition, it may

be necessary to thin using the low end of the NRV for stand density as a target. Forest treatments that include a combination of thinning and prescribed fire are the most effective at reducing subsequent fire severity, tree mortality, and the likelihood of passive crown fire (Kalies et al. 2016, Safford et al. 2012, Stephens et al. 2009). There is a high degree of scientific consensus that the combined effects of thinning plus prescribed burning consistently reduce the potential for severe wildfire across a broad range of forest types and conditions (Prichard et al. 2021).

4.1.2 Utilize variable density tree thinning to increase adaptability by maximizing the potential for a variety of survivorship pathways. Standard thinning prescriptions may focus on preferential removal of some tree species and sizes. Variable density thinning purposefully retains a selection of all species in a variety of age classes.

4.1.3 Retain or recruit shade-intolerant tree species into lower diameter classes through individual tree and group (clump) selection. Fire exclusion practices and concomitant forest densification have negatively impacted the shade-intolerant tree species such as yellow pines that are the most adapted to low-intensity frequent fire regimes. Retention and recruitment of these species are valued because they preserve an opportunity for restoring a predominately low-intensity fire regime in locations that are currently at risk of uncharacteristically severe wildfire.

4.1.4 Create gaps/openings appropriate for the forest type (Safford and Stevens 2017). Canopy gaps are also an essential element of frequent-fire forests across the US (Bigelow et al 2017). Canopy gaps create a wider range of both crown and surface fire behavior at small scales by maintaining differences in the type and density of fuels. Diversity in fire effects within a predominant surface fire regime allows forests to return to fire and regeneration dynamics that have greater resilience and less reliance on future active management.

Approach 4.2 Maintain and restore diversity of native species. This approach represents another opportunity for maximizing the potential for a variety of survivorship pathways. Before the arrival of GSOB in Southern California, a widely held view was that conifer losses could be offset with increases in oak species. The composition of the future forest is now less predictable. This approach focuses on preserving potential pathways for forest stand development and succession through retention of a diverse suite of native tree species.

Tactics:

4.2.1 Plant greater variety of conifers (e.g. Coulter pine, Incense Cedar) along with yellow pines. Coulter pine is a facultatively serotinous conifer associate of most forest communities in Southern California, but seedling recruitment is not limited to the postfire period. Existing Coulter stands that are advanced in age produce less vigorous postfire regeneration (Safford, personal communication). Incense cedar has shown resilience to recent climatic and biotic disturbances in mesic sites and can provide forest structure where other species are being lost to mortality. The species is not strongly drought-tolerant, however.

4.2.2 Plant oaks to supplement natural regeneration. Oaks provide an important hardwood component to stand diversity, but in many locations low oak recruitment has been observed. Planting sites that provide beneficial microclimate or protection from browsers can boost establishment. Interspersing oaks and conifers has multiple benefits, including breaking up

canopy fuel continuity and providing a barrier to biological stressors in conifers. Consult with Tribes to ensure that important aspects of oak regeneration are included.

4.2.3 Conduct monitoring and control for understory invasive species in new canopy openings. Native understory communities include guilds of species that respond favorably to characteristic fire conditions. Fire often produces a stronger growth and reproduction response than those observed during undisturbed periods. However, newly created openings and bare mineral soil are also favorable to invasion by undesired species. Monitoring and control for invasive species such as cheatgrass, other species of brome, and mustard spp. should be conducted after wildfire, prescribed fire, thinning and other disturbances that create new forest openings, especially at lower elevations/lower slopes. In some cases, restoration of native understory plants may be necessary to resist reinvasion by invasive species.

4.2.4 Engage with tribes in conservation of culturally significant species such as oaks. Tribes have an inherent role in informing and influencing the maintenance and restoration of culturally significant tree, shrub, forb, and grass species. Many species that are important food, fiber, and medicine to Tribal communities are not prioritized in western management practices. Building rapport with Tribal people is essential to being able to discuss culturally sensitive information about focal species and traditional restoration approaches. It is at the discretion of individuals on a case-by-case basis whether to share culturally sensitive information. The California Native American Heritage Commission's [Digital Atlas](#) is a recommended resource for contacting Tribes.

Approach 4.3 Retain biological and cultural legacies. This approach focuses on retaining biological resources whose inherent value stems from advanced age and culturally important species that cannot be easily replaced. Identifying valued biological and cultural legacies benefits from conversations across disciplines to identify species and develop criteria for target individuals.

Tactics:

4.3.1 Protect GSOB-free legacy oaks and high-value sites. Moderately- and severely-infested trees can be felled. Individual high-value, large-diameter oaks may be protected by applying [preventive insecticide by tree](#) (as long as infestation level of the tree is low, <10 emergence holes). Coordinate with Tribal communities about proposed pesticide treatments and consider the potential applications of prescribed and cultural fire for managing the fuels created by GSOB-related mortality. Additional research related to cultural fire and management of GSOB infestations is underway. Manage removed wood with methods such as grinding (most effective), covering, or debarking.

4.3.2 Preferentially retain snags and trees with morphological old growth characteristics instead of relying on diameter limits. Morphological old growth features include deep furrowed bark, large limbs, and full crowns. Old growth provides high-value habitat for a variety of wildlife species, and supports complex, diverse understory communities. Management emphasis should be in retaining these biological legacies during thinning projects and other management.

4.3.3 Support mycorrhizal networks by maintaining large and old-growth trees. Little work has been done with mycorrhizal networks in this region, but inferences can be made from research conducted elsewhere. Mycorrhizal networks support forest health, enabling inter-forest signaling as well as resource acquisition and sharing between trees of different species and age classes.

4.3.4 Support and protect natural regeneration for both shade-intolerant conifers and oaks. Yellow pine establishment is episodic in California, but fire exclusion and increasing drought decreases the likelihood of favorable conditions for establishment. There have been observations of low regeneration rates in montane oaks (i.e. black oak) in Southern Californian sites (Muick & Bartolome, 1987). Natural oak regeneration should be protected with measures such as grazing enclosures and targeted fire exclusion.

4.3.5 Thin surrounding vegetation around legacy trees (both conifers and oaks). Old growth may be resistant to low- to moderate-intensity fire but is still vulnerable to climate-driven high-severity fire. Surrounding vegetation should be thinned to create a buffer by removing surface and ladder fuels. To protect large trees from drought stress and competition, it may be necessary to thin to a lower stand density than current standard prescriptions allow for.

4.3.6 Develop strategies for protecting legacy trees during prescribed fire operations. This may include tactics such as limbing, ladder fuel removal, raking around tree bases, use of tree rings during broadcast burning, and alternative firing patterns (e.g. backing fire) to minimize exposure to extreme temperatures and maximize opportunity for survival of legacy individuals.

Approach 4.4 Special management designations such as Important Plant Areas, Research Natural Areas, and Botanical Special Interest Areas protect and call attention to the unique biological resources in montane forests. The establishment of new reserves can be complex but provide long-term benefits in the provision of ecosystem services. Lands with established designations should be managed to enhance resilience.

Tactics:

4.4.1 Protect lands and reserves with special designations by prioritizing management that maintains ecosystem and cultural diversity. Management should be designed with the specific response traits of the focal species in mind. Management objectives should focus on increasing community resilience to disturbance and reducing risk factors.

4.4.2 Coordinate with State and Federal 30x30 programs. As of 2023, the California state program offers a website with an extensive listing of potential resources and programs focused on supporting all steps in the process of identifying key lands and implementing durable protections for them ([California Nature](#)).

4.4.3 Coordinate with land conservancies that work to acquire and protect Native American ancestral lands. These organizations create opportunities for acquisition to reclaim ancestral homelands and Indigenous stewardship of those lands. Examples of organizations in Southern California include Native American Land Conservancy and Kumeyaay Diegueño Land Conservancy.

Approach 4.5 Consider multiple options for biomass utilization taking into account the beneficial links between woody biomass, heterogeneity and species diversity. Efforts to increase the pace and scale of forest treatments are producing woody biomass, both coarse woody debris and more fine-scale material. There is a range of uses for this material. Woody biomass can be utilized on-site to create forest heterogeneity, support species diversity, and repair postfire damages, with caveats and cautions about avoiding deep, homogeneous layers of fuels on the soil surface.

Tactics:

4.5.1 Where possible, use chipping only where there is a demonstrated positive ecological benefit. Chipping can have some beneficial effects on understory richness and diversity in forbs and grasses (Fornwalt et al. 2017).

4.5.2 Maintain patches of downed woody debris. Woody debris provides habitat to species such as southern rubber boa and woodrats. Smaller quantities of coarse woody debris resulting from forest treatments can be utilized on-site to purposefully create patches of habitat.

4.5.3 Use woody material to recover and repair disturbed areas where vegetation has recently been cleared. As an example, following fire suppression with heavy equipment such as bulldozers, woody material can be pulled back onto the bulldozer's fire containment lines. This tactic has the dual purpose of providing barriers to human access (reducing recreational impacts) and providing heterogeneity for post-fire plant recruitment. The distribution of material could also be designed to reduce water flow and erosion.

Strategy 5. Maintain or create opportunities for sites or communities of concern to withstand stressors in refugia

Refugia are places that are relatively buffered from the impacts of threats and stressors that occur across the landscape. They may be defined in terms of more than one type of stressor, and allow individuals, populations, or even physical, ecological, or socio-cultural resources to persist over time. For example, climate refugia are areas that are likely to be buffered from the impacts of climate change, such as coastal areas or north-facing slopes. Conversely, refugia from fire in Southern California can be defined in terms of topography and Santa Ana wind patterns. This menu considers these different forms of refugia as “domains” of refugia that influence landscape outcomes in combination (Rojas et al. 2021).

For the purposes of the conservation strategy, we are also defining refugia by the inherent characteristics of the landscape we cannot change (e.g., terrain, land-use, local and regional weather patterns) that may provide that buffering effect. For locations with a high degree of buffering from climate-associated threats, refugia can be thought of as areas where managers may be able to resist change, serving as a “slow lane” of change, providing protection to native species and ecosystems from negative effects in the short term (Morelli et al. 2020). In the longer term, refugia would be expected to support higher levels of biodiversity and ecosystem function than locations with greater exposure to climate stressors (Morelli et al. 2020). In workshops, managers also thought of refugia as places that could be utilized to support and protect iconic species, incoming species retreating from more exposed locations, ecosystem services, and both structural and genetic diversity.

This strategy focuses on identifying the portions of the landscape where climate- and other types- of exposure will be lowest, leveraging the opportunity to retain forest integrity in those locations. The benefit is that managers can focus investments of resources strategically in locations where retention of forest structure or similar management objectives will be more likely to be effective.

Approach 5.1 Identify stressors on refugial areas, and address them through active management. Even if an area provides a buffer from changes in temperature and precipitation, it is not necessarily protected from non-climate stressors without management. Within climate refugia, efforts to

identify and actively manage non-climate stressors will enhance forest persistence. The following tactics address stressors from the domains of refugia for climate, human pressure, and fire.

Tactics:

5.1.1 Use available species and climate models to define refugia where target species should be proactively maintained. This tactic applies predictive tools to identify areas of species-specific habitat stability, where critical elements of forest communities are most likely to persist under changing climatic conditions. When management is intended to conserve sensitive or at-risk species, an effort should be made to compile the best available information about the species' climate niche. For species that lack species distribution models, non-species-specific models of climate stability (i.e. slow climate velocity) can also be utilized. This tactic alone will not protect areas from non-climate stressors, and should be combined with tactics such as the ones that follow.

5.1.2 Reduce heavy recreation activity and road access in refugia areas. In forests, many anthropogenic stressors (e.g. nonnative species introduction, ignitions) are concentrated along transportation corridors such as roads and trails. Reducing disturbance levels by limiting access can be effective in protecting resources within refugia. Where longer-term options for limiting access are not practicable, aligning seasonal restrictions with either the primary climate stressors or the phenology of vulnerable biological resources can be effective.

5.1.3 Within climate refugia, especially where there are existing values at risk due to current condition, consider prioritizing management in areas that are prone to high intensity fire. Consider topography and Foehn wind patterns to determine exposure to stand replacing fire.

5.1.4 Within refugia, reduce drought stress where possible by modifying landscapes to retain water or promote infiltration. This may include protection or restoration of springs, meadows, and riparian areas and promoting groundwater recharge through stand thinning and the reintroduction of fire.

Approach 5.2 Prioritize and maintain sensitive or at-risk species or communities. This approach highlights regionally important biological resources such as Bigcone Douglas-fir, black oak, wet meadows, riparian corridors, and Indigenous gathering areas with a focus on conserving existing species and structural diversity.

Tactics:

5.2.1 Treat operable canyons and slopes with Bigcone Douglas-fir to create refugia from fire, especially when the understory consists of chaparral rather than canyon live oak (Parkinson et al, 2022). While the topographic characteristics of deep canyons and steep rocky slopes could be considered fire refugia for Bigcone Douglas-fir, many populations are still at risk of high-severity fire due to the history of fire exclusion. Fuels reduction may not be feasible in many locations as Bigcone populations associated with steep slopes are generally not considered operable. Therefore, locations that are operable should be prioritized for targeted reduction of chaparral in the lower canopy and understory. Bigcone Douglas-fir provides important habitat for California Spotted Owl. Given current fuels and fire conditions we recommend emphasizing reduction of understory fuels in order to retain forest canopy thereby lowering the risk of high-severity fire. (USDA 2004)

5.2.2 Identify GSOB-free Black Oak stands and commit funds for monitoring and suppression treatments such as removing newly infected trees and annual insecticide application to preserve individual trees. Gold spotted oak borer has now been detected across Southern California. In uninfected black oak stands, early detection and suppression tactics still have the potential to be effective. Resources for monitoring and treatment should be focused on preserving these stands. Managers may also focus on areas where the risk of introduction is high, such as uninfected stands near campgrounds and communities.

5.2.3 Include wet meadows in prescribed fires as possible to remove encroaching woody species. Establishment of tree seedlings in wet meadows occurs opportunistically during periods of drought and fire exclusion. Once established, forest stands further alter ground hydrology through their own water use, drawing down soil moisture through evapotranspiration. Consequences include forest homogenization through loss of meadow species and forest openings. Where periodic drowning of the root zone is not expected to be effective at limiting tree seedlings, a broadcast fire prescription specifically designed for wet meadows should be implemented. The prescribed fire will need to be hot enough to cause tree mortality within the wet meadow.

5.2.4 Include riparian forest in prescribed fires to protect mature forest from crown fire. Riparian forest communities benefit from fuels reduction through risk reduction, similar to other forest types, and are also often resilient to low- and moderate-severity fire. However, forest management often excludes riparian corridors due to the presence of sensitive species. Finding ways to include riparian corridors in fuels management is critical to reducing the impacts of severe fire in riparian areas as well as the risk of crown fire in adjacent forest stands. Methods could include flagging/avoidance of individual sensitive plants, or shifting the seasonal timing of the treatment to minimize impacts.

5.2.5 Restore and maintain riparian corridors for high vegetation moisture levels. Riparian corridors can function as natural firebreaks, where lower flame-lengths and slower fire spread are expected. High water tables and vegetation moisture levels are needed to maintain this dynamic. Riparian corridors and adjacent forest stands should be restored, including tree density reduction as needed, to conditions based on NRV targets.

5.2.6 Collaborate with Indigenous communities to identify, protect, and maintain access to important gathering areas and sacred sites through management that recognizes and incorporates Indigenous stewardship practices.

5.2.7 Establish fuel breaks around at-risk species and stands. This tactic is especially relevant where fire has triggered regeneration, but a reburn would cause high mortality rates in the cohort of seedlings or saplings. This scenario has occurred during large fire events in California, wiping out regeneration cohorts for fire-dependent species such as the rare cypress species that occur in Southern California.

5.2.8 Manage mesic microsites as refugia for sensitive species. More deliberate and effective utilization of microsites to support populations of focal species would promote diversity. Actions in mesic microsites could include avoidance of existing populations during anthropogenic disturbances, the return of fire at intervals beneficial to the plant community, or propagation of focal species. Mesic microsites provide an alternative to macro-scale connectivity features such as canyons and riparian corridors.

Approach 5.3 Bank genetic material for at-risk or sensitive species. This approach focuses on more intensive approaches, utilizing the full spectrum of conservation options and technology. Seed collections, seed farms and ex-situ plantings are established approaches in this region.

Tactics:

5.3.1 Develop off-site plantings and seed farms. These can be used to create “insurance” populations by holding seedlings until they are large enough to survive replanting, or to increase the supply of seed for restoration projects.

5.3.2 Develop collections of seeds or genetic material (such as tissue cultures) for long-term storage. Collections of both seed and other genetic material have successfully been utilized to preserve genetic diversity in rare plant and animal species. With the populations of many species in decline, these methods are being used for more species as a protection against extinction.

Strategy 6. Use redundancy and connectivity to maintain dynamic relationships in a changing landscape

Redundancy can be thought of in terms of groups of similar land features or habitat patches, whether they are montane meadows, forested “sky islands”, watersheds, or wetlands. Having multiple similar features can reduce the risk of species extinctions by supporting multiple separate populations. Even if a disturbance negatively impacts one or more of the features, some existing populations will escape impact. Habitat connectivity (as between patches that are spatially separated) also can have positive effects, such as supporting viable populations through gene flow and enabling the occupation of available habitat through dispersal or migration movements. Connectivity can also support negative effects of disturbances, such as the spread of non-native propagules. Maintaining redundancy and connectivity are increasingly recognized as important conservation strategies (Jennings et al. 2020). Considering temporal dynamics such as seasonal or interannual patterns in combination with patterns of connectivity and redundancy can support effective landscape management and conservation (Zeller et al. 2020).

As the communities in ecosystems undergo directional changes in climate, management to maintain spatial and temporal connections can provide more opportunities for species and ecological processes to move to more suitable habitat as environmental conditions change. Using riparian corridors as an example of an important means of connectivity, riparian terrestrial plant communities provide connectivity among habitat patches for a range of terrestrial species, including mammals and birds.

Fluxes of resources within ecosystems are dynamic through both time and space, as ecosystems experience seasonal cycles and disturbance processes. Seasonal hydrological fluctuations are especially strong in this region, as most streams run intermittently during the spring and dry up entirely by midsummer. As a result, aquatic populations may have reduced connectivity for portions of the year. Climate-adapted management tactics should take seasonality and spatial dynamics into account.

Approach 6.1 Ensure redundancy of uncommon ecosystems or rare species assemblages. For uncommon and rare species, emphasizing the maintenance of multiple populations can lower the chances of significant population losses because threats impacting some populations may not affect all of them.

Tactics:

6.1.1 Identify uncommon ecosystems and rare assemblages, such as high-elevation limber pine, aspen, rare cypress stands, patches of big-cone Douglas fir, and pebble plains. Aspen reaches the southernmost limit of its distribution in the US in the San Bernardino Mountains. Limber pine occurs in disjunct high-elevation locations, and rare cypress and big-cone Douglas fir are also found in a range of disjunct locations. Pebble plains are a glacial relict found only in the San Bernardino Mountains.

6.1.2 Evaluate and manage the potential risks to uncommon ecosystems and rare assemblages with landscape-scale management plans. Consideration at greater spatial scales will help account for metapopulation dynamics and enable management for connectivity. Management plans should take into account management actions applied to different populations and occurrences of priority communities to ensure that management is prioritizing actions to mitigate risk across an adequate representation of sites that host uncommon ecosystems or rare species assemblages.

6.1.3 Prioritize management of rare or protected species such as the California Spotted Owl (CASPO). For example, prioritize action across occupied CASPO territories, applying seasonal restrictions to limit impacts to the species. Actively manage forest structure in territories to reduce the risk of habitat loss or degradation due to high severity wildfire; forest health treatments of up to 15% of the protected activity center per year are consistent with current practices and Mexican Spotted Owl guidelines. Nest core areas should not be treated. Preserving core areas of dense cover will maintain areas of suitable nest habitat, and incense cedar in particular can provide both the preferred structural density and thermal regulation for CASPO. Treat unoccupied territories to maintain forest resiliency, preserving opportunities for future recolonization.

6.1.4 Partner with neighbors to develop landscape-scale management plans that establish management goals for uncommon ecosystems or rare species assemblages that can be carried out across redundant locations under management by different organizations. Utilize local resources (e.g., Resource Conservation Districts) to facilitate landscape planning.

Approach 6.2 Establish and enhance connectivity among rare assemblages where connectivity would allow for recolonization after disturbance events or migration to adapt to changing climatic conditions. Rare assemblages typically already have a degree of isolation, but climate change and land use can reduce existing connectivity further. However, limiting connectivity may be warranted where the risk of spread of invasive species, fire, or disease outweighs the potential benefits of connectivity.

Tactics:

6.2.1 Consider management actions such as restoration that will enhance connectivity among habitats that host unique ecosystems or rare species assemblages to support recolonization and/or adaptation as conditions change.

6.2.2 Maintain gene flow using assisted migration tools if necessary. Engage with communities, especially Tribal communities, in plans and actions to use assisted migration as a conservation tool.

6.2.3 Where there are specific threats to unique ecosystems or rare species assemblages from stressors such as wildfire, pests, or disease that can be spread through connected landscapes, consider management actions that could limit the connectivity of those stressors across the landscape such as stand thinning.

Approach 6.3 Support structural and functional redundancy at a landscape scale by restoring heterogeneity in similar patches and in patches that contribute to critical ecosystem processes such as hydrologic functioning.

Tactics:

6.3.1 Prioritize treatments to reduce the risk of stand replacing fire using similar management targets for multiple sites across the landscape with similar species or communities. Creating more redundant sites with increased structural heterogeneity is likely to increase overall landscape scale resilience to disturbance and enhance recovery after disturbance.

6.3.2 Consider replicating management actions across areas that contribute to critical ecosystem functioning such as springs, the headwaters of major waterways, or landscapes surrounding these hydrologic systems to reduce the impacts of stressors and to enhance recovery from disturbance across the landscape.

6.3.3 Create management units focused on landscape features that have been shown to provide some degree of buffering from the impacts of climate change or can support adaptation to those changing conditions. Examples include north-facing canyons and slopes, riparian corridors, and elevational gradients.

6.3.4 Restore heterogeneous forest structure by creating clusters and gaps of trees. Fine-scale heterogeneity is a characteristic structural component of yellow pine mixed conifer forest (Safford and Stevens 2017). It creates patch-type redundancy throughout that supports overall biodiversity, allowing diverse species access to a range of resource types.

6.3.5 Restore disturbance regimes to multiple redundant systems across the landscape, particularly for systems that are at risk from widespread stressors. For example, to address the loss of oaks to the gold-spotted oak borer, restore the practice of cultural burning for management of mid-elevation oak savannahs. Regular cultural burning would remove decadent and diseased woody material, limit shrub ingrowth and stimulate the regrowth of oaks.

6.3.6 Where there is uncertainty about optimal treatment types or approaches that may best maintain ecosystem functioning, consider testing strategies in a subset of redundant systems to allow for comparison and adaptive management.

Approach 6.4 Consider landscape dynamics in planning management actions for redundancy and connectivity. This would primarily entail adaptive management approaches to address variable conditions at subseasonal, seasonal, annual, and interannual timeframes. Some of the following tactics address spatial dynamics as well.

Tactics:

6.4.1 Incorporate flexibility into management plans to allow for adjustments to scheduling and treatment type to adapt to dynamic conditions. For example, reforestation efforts could be

planned with the option for implementation in multiple years in the event of a drought that may reduce survival or landscape scale planning could include a potential treatment option that would be implemented in the event a fire occurs before forest thinning can be completed.

6.4.2 Evaluate the landscape of proposed or completed management actions through the lens of seasonal and interannual dynamics to ensure there is redundancy and connectivity among areas at risk that are planned for management so they can best accommodate changing conditions. For example, in transitional zones that may be more susceptible to drought, consider prioritizing thinning to reduce competition for available water. In areas where stand replacing fire may result in increased erosion and slope failure during extremely wet periods, evaluate options for returning low intensity fire to the landscape.

6.4.3 Consider how landscape dynamics may affect proposed management actions to avoid maladaptation and negative impacts, being mindful of how connectivity to adjacent areas may affect risk and recovery. For example, if thinning or burning is planned near a community or a previously burned area, consider how drought may affect post-treatment recovery for native versus non-native species that may spread from those previously disturbed areas.

6.4.4 Evaluate the potential impacts of changing climatic conditions on habitat quality and ecosystem function, prioritizing management of at-risk redundant areas and connectivity to buffer dynamic conditions. For example, where temperature extremes or drought may reduce suitability of habitat for some species, prioritize management of elevational gradients that would allow upslope migration through either natural or assisted migration.

6.4.5 Consider seasonal closures to intermittent streams that provide sensitive species habitat when running but also have a conflict with human use patterns. The overlap of water play areas and Arroyo Toad breeding habitat is one regional example. This tactic may require staffing and enforcement at locations with higher recreational use; conversely, it may be more feasible in locations that receive lower human use and traffic.

6.4.6 Seek out traditional and/or cultural knowledge regarding movement of beings. Traditional knowledge can provide insight into landscape dynamics, in terms of both locations and timing of habitat occupancy and use.

6.4.7 During reforestation plantings, select stock that maintains genetic diversity and gene flow at landscape scale to allow for a greater degree of adaptive capacity to landscape dynamics over both the short- and long-term. Reforestation stock will provide future contributions to the genetic diversity of the forest.

Approach 6.5 Plan for redundancy and connectivity among refugia to ensure a single refugium does not result in a dead end for any species or community. While refugia can be considered a “slow-land” where species can have more time to adapt to changing climatic conditions or to withstand a disturbance event (Morelli et al. 2020), without similar refugia across the landscape and connectivity among them, they may simply serve as relictual sites where species or communities may persist but are functionally extirpated from the landscape.

Tactics:

6.5.1 Prioritize protection and management of mesic pockets to maintain relict species. Management actions may include thinning in or adjacent to mesic sites to promote conditions that would result in low intensity burning should a wildfire occur. Multiple mesic pockets can provide redundancy across the landscape.

6.5.2 Map and assess connectivity and redundancy of refugia to ensure prioritization of refugia areas that are hubs of connectivity or unique in character. For example, support and enable pools to act as refugia for aquatic species during low flow periods. An appropriate management action would be to limit water use and removals when seasonal water flows are low.

Strategy 7. Sustain fundamental ecological and cultural functions

These approaches cover fundamental forest management needs, and many of them are already frequently incorporated into ongoing management efforts. They support forest survival and resilience by maintaining ecological functioning and resource cycling. The primary ecological functions provided by montane forests include retention of biodiversity, carbon storage, and preservation and retention of hydrological function and healthy soil. Frequent fire is also considered an important function in the maintenance of healthy and resilient forested landscapes. Supporting the ecological requirements of culturally important species through traditional stewardship practices is another aspect of this strategy, for the purpose of enabling sustained or increased use by Indigenous communities.

FIGURE B-1. The word cloud represents important ecological and cultural functions identified by participants in a Tribal-focused workshop to develop this Adaptation Menu.

Approach 7.1 Restore/maintain fire in fire-adapted systems. The widespread reintroduction of fire to fire-adapted forest systems is the ultimate goal across Southern California. In particular, returning frequent-fire forest types to regular cycles of low-intensity fire would serve to lower risk to human communities, ecosystem services, and other values. However, climate change has created additional challenges for what was already a complex, landscape-scale situation.

Tactics:

7.1.1 Focus on reduction of hazardous fuel loading in order to enable reintroduction of fire. Current forest conditions are often unsuitable to receive fire given the century-long accumulation of trees and fuels. A phased approach to forest restoration is often required, with prescribed fire preceded by thinning. The efficacy of coupling thinning and prescribed fire treatments to reduce high severity fire has been described repeatedly in the literature (Safford et al. 2012). Forest treatments that include thinning plus prescribed fire are the most effective at reducing fire severity, tree mortality, and the likelihood of passive crown fire. In contrast, thinning or prescribed fire alone tend to have less of an effect or none at all depending on conditions at the time of wildfire. Prichard et al. (2021) summarize this literature, “Although thinning alone as a fuels reduction treatment is questionable and site dependent, there exists widespread agreement that combined effects of thinning plus prescribed burning consistently reduces the potential for severe wildfire across a broad range of forest types and conditions.”

7.1.2 Accept a greater range of fire effects from prescribed burns. If prescribed fire is too cool, it does not produce the desired ecological effects. The natural fire regime for YPMC is characterized by a preponderance of low to moderate fire intensities. The subsequent distribution of fire effects is characterized by an overall fine-grained heterogeneous structure of small canopy openings with occasional larger gaps in the forest canopy from pockets of high-severity fire (Safford and Stevens 2017). Moderate fire effects in particular are beneficial for maintaining a resilient forest structure.

7.1.3 Seek opportunities to experiment with prescribed fire within the historical burn season. Seasonality shifts on a geographical gradient from primarily occurring late-summer to fall in the western Transverse Range to having a significant component of spring-early summer burns in the southern Peninsular Range (Skinner et al. 2006). The San Bernardino mountains fall at an intermediate point along this gradient. While this has not been an active area of experimentation, the potential benefits include expanding the number of days available for prescribed fire and achieving a greater range of fire effects. Conducting burns as planned incidents or pilot projects would increase the operational feasibility. Tactics such as this will be necessary to increase the pace and scale of forest treatments that have positive ecological benefits.

7.1.4 Avoid accumulation of chipped material to avoid excessive soil heating and residence time and to expedite even distribution of follow-up treatments. The critical attributes are both in the depth and distribution of chips. Too much chipped material (>3 in or 7.5 cm in depth) can require multiple rounds of prescribed fire to safely consume the material, reducing the overall number of acres that receive the needed follow-up prescribed fire.

7.1.5 Incorporate drought consideration into prescribed burn planning, such as creating a Go/No Go process based on an index such as Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI). The concern is that tree mortality levels from the prescribed fire treatment will be elevated from the combination of drought stress and fire effects.

7.1.6 Rake around tree bases during drought years. In drought years, baseline levels of stress are higher, and sustained heating around tree bases is more likely to cause damage or kill stressed trees. The practice of raking depends on a “not too much and not too little” approach.

Too much raking will damage roots and surface soil structure, while not enough raking will be ineffective at reducing heat residence time.

7.1.7 Develop a maintenance plan that guides repeated rounds of mechanical and fire treatments. The maintenance plan needs to include monitoring after treatments to evaluate whether objectives are being met and to guide adaptive management decisions. Burn objectives should be quantified as much as possible, so that monitoring can be used to evaluate the outcomes.

7.1.8 Revitalize and maintain cultural use of fire as a stewardship practice. Cultural burning maintains important species for community uses as well as supporting biodiverse communities generally, and increases structural heterogeneity in forests. It supports the frequency of fire needed to maintain low-intensity fire regimes and engages community members in caretaking.

Approach 7.2 Build resilience to drought stress. At the current tree density, many stands are crowded enough that trees are competing for resources (moisture, nutrients, and light). As a result, tree growth is slowed, tree vigor is reduced, and some trees are dying from insufficient space, moisture, or nutrients. Intra-stand competition will strengthen with increasing stress from changing climate. The tactics in this section will also serve to generally lower the risk of high-severity fire.

Tactics:

7.2.1 Provide density targets for conifers and oaks that are based on NRV by forest community type. Density targets can be adjusted for anticipated climate exposure by selecting targets at the low end of the range, rather than the mean.

7.2.2 Incorporate stand heterogeneity by adjusting density targets by aspect and slope positioning into project design. The density targets should be based on NRV, and will likely recommend lower tree densities for south and southwest-facing slopes where conditions are drier relative to north and northeast-facing slopes.

7.2.3 Provide targets for shrub cover to encourage conifer and oak recruitment. At forested elevations, shrub cover under mixed conifer forest canopy is generally open and may be absent over extensive areas. Natural range of variation studies report median shrub cover values ranging from 1-7%, suggesting that in reference forests, more than half of the sampled locations supported very low shrub cover (Southern CA NRV, in draft). NRV studies also indicate that higher- and potentially extensive- shrub cover is expected on southern slopes, while being absent in extensive portions of basins/canyon bottoms and on north-facing slopes (Minnich et al. 2000). The upper end of the range of shrub cover values in both historic and recent sampling extends to 75% or higher in some plot locations. These elevational and topographical trends can be used to guide shrub management.

7.2.4 Collaborate with Tribal communities to incorporate traditional stewardship practices that restore hydrologic function and increase moisture availability to forest stands during periods of drought.

Approach 7.3 Restore/maintain carbon sinks. At the present time, California forests are considered carbon sinks. However, simulation modeling suggests that compounding climate effects,

forest mortality, and severe wildfires could cause forests to become net carbon sources instead by the middle of this century (Dass et al. 2018). Simulation modeling suggests that forests in Southern California may already be carbon sources. Preserving the ability of forests to store carbon focuses on retaining large trees and reducing the risk of extensive carbon losses during large wildfire events.

Tactics:

7.3.1 Retain large trees as important carbon sinks. In stands with an existing resource of large trees, the goal is to reduce fire hazard (i.e. by removing many smaller trees) while retaining the larger trees where most of the carbon is stored. Stand data will assist in determining the optimal tree diameter to use as a threshold between retention (carbon storage) vs. removal (hazard reduction). Removal of surface and ladder fuels around large trees should also be a focus to reduce existing hazard to large trees.

7.3.2 Reduce likelihood of complete carbon loss by prioritizing mechanical thinning in areas of important carbon stocks. The areas of greatest management need should be identified to help managers guide scarce resources to those locations first. With the conditions for large, severe climate-driven fires occurring more frequently, these projects are extremely time-sensitive. In many locations, wildfires have been burning through landscapes rapidly, far ahead of treatment implementation.

7.3.3 Prioritize reforestation in areas where woody biomass has been severely reduced (e.g. type-converted to shrub or grass) and natural regeneration is likely to fail. Integrating current and future [climate exposure mapping products](#) will help identify deforested areas where reforestation efforts are likely to be successful and persist into the future. This may include a focus on planting hardwoods or drought-tolerant conifers in more xeric areas. These projects are also time-sensitive, as the window of opportunity for reforestation will close after the first few growing seasons.

7.3.4 Where possible, design forest treatments to promote natural regeneration for future carbon uptake. The specific forest treatment will depend on the germination requirements by tree species. For example, fire-based treatments will be needed for facultative or obligate serotinous species that require burning. Shade-intolerant species will require the creation of appropriately-sized forest openings during thinning.

7.3.5 In areas where plantations have been lost to fire or drought, consider letting them naturally convert to shrub dominance and invest in reforestation in areas with a higher likelihood of tree survival. Shrubs serve as carbon stores and if they are frequently disturbed by wildfire or cleared in preparation for reforestation activities that are unsuccessful then the net result may be invasion by non-native grasses that have a low carbon storage value.

Approach 7.4 Retain and enhance genetic diversity. Genetic diversity refers to variation in traits both within populations and among populations. Genetically diverse populations maintain greater potential for successfully adapting to a wider range of future conditions, by producing diverse individuals who carry different traits. Retaining as much existing diversity as possible within populations is an important adaptive approach towards uncertainty about future conditions, since it is impossible to know which traits will support survival in the future. Maintaining gene flow between populations is also important

for avoiding the deleterious effects of inbreeding. The tactics in this approach represent an underdeveloped area of need and present a significant opportunity for collaboration and grant development.

Tactics:

7.4.1 Work collaboratively to develop robust seed sources and banks for the region. The southern U.S. border with Mexico complicates efforts to expand sources of genetic material. Seed sources from higher latitudes across California may not be adapted to local climate conditions, and sources from lower latitudes require international cooperation. There is a great need for development of new collaborations. This tactic could also include working towards collaborations for experimentation with species from outside the region that may be better adapted to future conditions in southern California.

7.4.2 Develop seed collections from a wide geographic range, from not just lower-elevation bands but a range of topographic positions and distances from the coast to test how different seed sources may increase adaptive capacity of existing forest stands. Maximizing the range of environmental gradients represented in seed collections will support the retention of genetic diversity for regional reforestation efforts. Documenting the provenance of individual seed collections should be emphasized in order to avoid maladaptive effects in plantings. Controlled experimentation and monitoring of outcomes is critical.

7.4.3 Collect and store genetic material from a diversity of tree species within the region (e.g., Coulter pine, big-cone Douglas fir). Maximizing the existing diversity that is represented in seed collections will retain a greater range of future restoration options.

7.4.4 Explore the limits of drought-tolerance in genotypically similar seed sources for Ponderosa across the Southwest. Ponderosa pine in southern California has been found to be more similar genetically to southwestern (Nevada, New Mexico) populations than Sierra Nevada populations (Potter et al 2013). These populations could potentially hold genetic material with greater heat- and drought- tolerance than current populations in Southern California. Similarly, the climate tolerances of Jeffrey pine populations in Baja California should be examined.

7.4.5 Identify individuals resistant to known diseases and pests and create seed collections from them. Specific needs include the identification of blister rust-resistant white pine individuals, and the identification of old-growth oaks that have proven resistant to GSOB-related mortality.

7.4.6 Work with Tribal communities to identify genetic lineages of important plants used for food, fiber, and medicine that should be collected and stored for conservation purposes. Support efforts by local Tribes to undertake that collection and storage.

Approach 7.5 Maintain or restore hydrology. Across multiple workshop engagements with a wide range of audiences, maintaining hydrological function has been broadly identified as a priority in the montane forests of Southern California. This menu approach has a dual focus on capturing surface flows in recognized drainage features and increasing groundwater interaction with streamflows and infiltration for water storage. In areas where forests have been lost, restoration is important for protection of hydrologic function. This includes tactics for erosion and sediment reduction and development of canopy cover for moderating temperatures and solar radiation within streams. The following tactics are

recommended due to their relevance for conserving forest habitat, riparian corridors, and ecosystem services focusing on water security.

Tactics:

7.5.1 During project planning, identify whether projects are likely to increase or decrease surface flows and have indirect effects on groundwater recharge. Integrating a hydrologist into planning at an early stage and conducting this analysis will document expected water impacts and raise the profile of hydrological health as a valued ecosystem service.

7.5.2 Managers need to fully participate in CA Sustainable Groundwater Management Act (SGMA) planning processes in order to balance beneficial human uses of source water areas. These planning processes are where holistic decisions regarding water usage are made between managers, specialists, and water users. SGMA provides delineated basin boundaries and creates a working group for each basin. Manager participation in these groups ensures that groundwater storage is valued and protected, especially at the upper edges of the basins where forest habitat and riparian corridors are more likely to be found.

7.5.3 Managers should engage with the CA Water Board and with the Army Corps of Engineers (when activities fall within the ordinary high water mark of streams and wetlands) to maintain permits and water quality regulatory compliance. At the State level, the conditions for permitting ground-disturbing activities vary by district, but these requirements are intended to maintain water quality for beneficial uses. Each district has a list of beneficial uses, and accounting for these is one way to incorporate ecosystem services into management efforts to maintain water quality and to address existing impediments to meeting water quality objectives.

7.5.4 Natural resource specialists and project/contract managers should manage [Best Management Practices](#) in partnership during ground-disturbing activities to monitor operator activities and correct deficiencies as they arise in order to meet applicable regulatory requirements. This includes ensuring that all involved managers have access to and knowledge of the requirements and conditions that have been agreed upon for the project. Often this will require field visits during the activity (not just after work has been completed) and maintaining communication between regulatory agencies, specialists, managers, and contractors through all phases of ground-disturbing projects.

7.5.5 Seek opportunities for floodplain, meadow, and wetland restoration to build natural resilience to a range of surface water flows (including flooding events) and support groundwater infiltration. Historical uses and current management result in different types of impacts, such as channel confinement, incision, dissection, or diversion. For example, artificial linear features like a road/crossing may dissect a natural feature, capturing water flow and diverting it elsewhere. Restoring resilience requires first identifying the cause of hydrological disconnection and then directly addressing it to restore connection. Where flooding is a factor, restoration projects may focus on creation or expansion of natural features that slow and hold water, such as floodplains or wetlands.

7.5.6 Built infrastructure— including road-stream crossings, check dams, and culverts— needs to accommodate projected high and low flows and permit aquatic and terrestrial beings to pass between upstream and downstream water sources. Culverts and bridges should be designed to

accommodate dynamic stream channel shape and to limit channelization. This tactic includes the removal of historic water impediments (dams, wells, diversions) and restoration projects to accelerate the recovery of impacted areas and species.

7.5.7 With warming temperatures, maintaining the right type and amount of canopy cover in riparian areas will become increasingly important for aquatic species. Tactics for achieving this could include establishing a minimum water-surface canopy cover standard ([USFS Best Management Practices Handbook](#)) on streams where the maintenance of proper water temperatures is essential for the perpetuation of fish and aquatic habitat. Following disturbance, areas where canopy cover is critical should be monitored for natural recovery and restored if recovery of the riparian canopy fails to occur.

7.5.8 Engage in discussions with Tribal communities about the hydrologic issues they face, beneficial uses they are working to maintain, and traditional approaches to managing surface water and groundwater.

Approach 7.6 Reduce impacts to soils and nutrient cycling. Impacts of concern include but are not limited to ground disturbance, excessive nutrients, pollution, soil compaction, water runoff, soil erosion, and sedimentation of water features. Many tactics for conserving soil and water can be found in handbooks of best management practices. A soils specialist or hydrologist can assist with the selection of specific tactics.

Tactics:

7.6.1 Plan for seasonal adjustments to ground disturbing activities in response to storms or drought. This recommendation could take the form of a wet weather management plan or a storm preparedness plan developed as part of a more comprehensive erosion control plan. The language can make recommendations for specific time periods when equipment can be operated (e.g. within 72 hours of a wetting rain event of 0.25 inch or greater). Subjective language can further explain: “Equipment will not be operated when ground conditions are such that damage will result,” and can also require adjustments to erosion control practices: “The kinds and intensity of control work... will be adjusted to ground and weather conditions, in order to control overland runoff, erosion, and sedimentation.”

7.6.2 Follow Best Management Practices to minimize soil compaction and ground disturbance impacts during forest management activities. These will vary based on the type of activity but should incorporate the principles of 1) minimizing impact during management activities and 2) conducting needed repairs afterwards. This may include avoiding ground equipment operation on unstable, wet or easily compacted soils unless operation can be conducted without excessive rutting, soil puddling or runoff of sediment. Provide guidance for appropriate routes for heavy equipment that includes moving in a straight line and minimizing pivot turns, focusing equipment activity in areas that have already been compacted. Flagging and clearly articulating travel routes and landings to heavy equipment operators will greatly reduce soil compaction and ground disturbing activities. Repair activities may include methods such as chip application in areas of soil disturbance to reduce erosion.

7.6.3 Retain topsoil. Topsoil has concentrations of organic matter and microorganisms. Handbooks of best management practices will include tactics for storing and protecting topsoil for

later use in reclamation or restoration. Putting topsoil back in place on the soil surface is necessary for accelerating the regrowth of vegetative cover and root systems needed to hold soil in place and prevent erosion.

7.6.4 Minimize postfire impacts by addressing suppression damages and damages or new threats created by the fire itself. Suppression damages may cause erosion and sedimentation or allow unauthorized access, and repair includes: restoring hand lines and dozer lines by installing water bars, raking material back onto bare soil, or securing and repairing gates and fences that may have been damaged during suppression action. Addressing damages or new threats within the burned area created by the fire itself includes repair of damaged infrastructure (drains, stream crossings, waterbars) as well as potential implementation of erosion control measures, such as installation of straw wattles or rip rap or application of hydromulch, to control runoff, erosion, and sedimentation. The U.S. Forest Service uses a Burned Area Emergency Response process to analyze and implement this postfire repair.

7.6.5 Avoid excessive nutrient inputs. Southern California montane forests are characterized by dry, low-productivity soils and vegetation adapted to those conditions. Nutrient-rich inputs are likely not appropriate. This tactic applies both to pollutant streams (point and non-point sources), as well as to nutrients that could be considered beneficial. More experimentation is needed to determine the siting and quantities of biochar that will support ecological functioning, while avoiding deleterious effects. The use of fertilizers and other soil amendments during revegetation or reforestation projects should be assessed carefully and avoided if possible.

Approach 7.7 Maintain and revitalize cultural approaches to harvesting and caretaking.

From the Tribal Adaptation Menu: “Using traditional harvesting and caretaking methods can be an important way to sustain ecological functions in a given area, as these methods are often holistic and respectful in a way that standard land management practices are not. Revitalizing the use of these methods can serve as a climate adaptation tool and help provide balance in an ecosystem and strengthen relationships with its native beings. For example, traditional caretaking might provide guidance on how to harvest certain plants in a good and respectful way, to not overharvest, and to allow for healthy regeneration.”

Tactics

7.7.1 Promote sustainable harvest techniques informed by traditional practices with guidance from local native practitioners.

7.7.2 Remove weak or sick trees during forest management activities to leave the stronger, healthier individuals behind.

7.7.3 Use honorable harvest practices when gathering forest products to give back from what is taken, for example to gather and re-plant seeds or propagules for the next harvest.

7.7.4 Support co-stewardship and harvesting in a good way, following guidance from Tribal practitioners and culture bearers, such as taking only what you need and leaving enough to sustain a population.

Why Transform?

Transformation is most commonly described as permanent, uni-directional change from one vegetation type to another, but it may also be more subtle where certain species or types of species are lost while others are able to persist (this process also is known as vegetation type change or conversion). Communities transform through their response to disturbances and self-reorganization. In montane forests, transformation is the likely end result of severe, climate-accelerated disturbance cycles of drought, pest/disease outbreaks, and fire. The end state of transformation in montane forests will depend on the site, and the magnitude of the transformation may be linked to the type and intensity of the disturbance. When we have limited or no control over the major abiotic and biotic drivers of change, we may focus instead on building or supporting forest resilience. Likewise, when severe disturbance overpowers resilience capacity in forests, are there ways land management activities can guide resource responses towards desired new conditions that maintain ecosystem services? This is the first of many questions posed in this section.

In California it is no longer uncommon to encounter severely burned forests with damaged soils that have massively reduced habitat quality, water-holding capacity, and carbon storage values. These areas are unlikely prospects for unassisted tree recovery. When a forest gets to the point of serious degradation, what should be done to support basic ecological functioning while the ecological community undergoes major reorganization? Consideration of this complex question can be especially challenging, because the first impulse may be to try to return the system to its original forested state. The first two thirds of the menu cover management tactics to resist or accommodate change, but these tactics may not be appropriate in all cases when vegetation conversion has either started or occurred, including during postfire restoration and recovery.

While managing to move towards a novel state can provide opportunities to retain ecological functioning, there are many challenges and well-founded concerns about the practicality and suitability of management-driven transformation. It is a difficult management decision to determine when pre-disturbance conditions are no longer tenable and how best to maintain ecological processes without risk of losing key functions like water holding capacity, soil retention, and biodiversity. Given all the evidence supporting projections of likely climate outcomes, it is apparent that if managers do not consider transformational management strategies, the transformation will happen regardless. We should anticipate likely transformation across portions of the landscape and begin to plan for management response where and when it eventually becomes necessary. Developing a plan for transformation may be guided by the intention of maintaining ecosystem services, as a stopgap against extensive losses in those critical services. Considering that transformation without intervention will result in further forest loss and degradation, and the task at hand is to work within the limits of the disturbance response and participate in the ecological re-organization. The following is a scenario of forest transformation we are likely to see in southern California, intended to guide exploration and planning for transformative management strategies.

Transformation Scenario

Imagine a site initially occupied by a mature Jeffrey pine-black oak (*P. jeffreyi-Quercus kelloggii*) forest. The details of this scenario have been taken from events that have already taken place in parts of Southern California.

Time interval: fifteen years, since 2010

Site history:

- Two-year drought
- Then burned by a severe wildfire, killing most Jeffrey pine on site.
- With most adult trees killed, seedling densities in the year after fire were low, and survival was nearly zero after two more hot summers.
- Subsequent Jeffrey pine beetle (*Dendroctonus jeffreyi*) outbreak killed many surviving adult conifers, even though prescribed fire had been employed to thin some of the stands and reduce water stress.
- Black oak appeared poised to dominate, but invasion by a boring insect (GSOB, *Agilus auroguttatus*) devastated mature oaks.
- Followed by 4 years of severe drought.

Some points about this situation to consider:

This scenario is realistic across a range of montane forest areas in southern California, and describes the conditions under which more transformative approaches could be used in management. Managers might typically assume the cascade of events would occur as drought followed by an insect outbreak, followed by wildfire through the stressed and dead trees. However, it is more realistic to anticipate that mortality factors could hit in a variety of sequences. This scenario assumes that a moderate level of active management was implemented in forest stands but was not as effective in reducing water stress as managers might have hoped.

Currently, the best case-scenario for routine management is that if mechanical thinning and prescribed fire are implemented regularly, Jeffrey pine should be able to survive at higher elevations under short- to moderate-term climate change. In terms of black oak, once GSOB hits, oak dominance will decrease, although younger trees may persist at lower abundance. Unfortunately, outcomes with marked degradation or loss in community structure and/or biodiversity have occurred (Safford 2019). Sites similar to this generalized scenario are transitioning to open shrubland with an understory of invasive grasses and accumulations of heavy loads of coarse woody fuels. In between these best- and worst-case scenarios are a range of intermediate outcomes.

Three components of transformation that are significant for managers are:

- 1) the use of objective-driven management,
- 2) the need to identify key characteristics to maintain or change, and
- 3) the ability to identify strategic intervention points.

Objective-driven management has been stressed throughout the conservation strategy as integral to decision-making in uncertain times of change (Section X). The process for identifying key characteristics is a focus of the refugia-based decision-making framework (Section Y). Therefore, the remainder of this introduction to transformative management as a response to ecosystem transformation considers the question: is identification of a threshold needed to justify greater departures from current management strategies?

Thresholds

Identifying strategic intervention points and recognizing significant turning points in the ecosystem can be difficult to do in real time, even during major mortality events. Some intervention points may be obvious, for example, after severe fire. Others are less obvious—in Southern California, managers are watching for signs that oak species sensitive to Gold-spotted oak borer have reached a transformative threshold. One approach might be to establish management triggers that are linked to monitoring a target area or species over time for undesired changes. In some cases, waiting to initiate management may cost too much time as the window of opportunity closes and vegetation degradation ensues.

Identifying observable indicators of a threshold could be useful, for example, the detection of an uncharacteristically large component of early seral vegetation in a fire footprint. Other thresholds that have been suggested for tree species include the combination of occurrence at low elevation plus the absence of a viable seed source or low recruitment. Generally, foresters are already seeking to source seed from lower-elevations for montane restoration. When trees at low elevations are lost, there are few options for sourcing climate-adapted seed as replacements (e.g.). Using climate projections to identify the portions of the landscape that are most exposed to increasing drought stress is another approach. Once a major disturbance occurs, these portions of the landscape can be examined more closely for signs of transformation.

There is a poignant financial threshold that can also be used as a communication tool with audiences that are more resistant to the concept of transformation. The message would be, with limited financial ability to conduct reforestation, where can we afford to maintain forest as the climate continues to change? This message is best communicated by the land managers who experience the daily tensions of developing, funding, and implementing critical management projects over large landscapes with limited financial resources and many competing needs.

As this section of the menu attempts to look forward into the future, keep a few guiding thought questions in mind:

- Is identification of a threshold needed to justify greater departures from current management strategies?
- Are there any indicators of potential threshold changes that can be readily tracked to allow for more proactive response?
- Are there bet-hedging management strategies that we can deploy?
- What species will help maintain forest structure in warmer temperatures and more variable precipitation?
- Which ecological processes or functions are most important to maintain in situations where existing species management has become untenable?
- Do we have pathways for maintaining a lower-intensity fire regime?

Strategy 8. Expand efforts with native species in existing habitats

In transformation workshops with managers, one recurring theme has been to exhaust options for guiding forest change through the use native species (i.e. indigenous species that are found within the assessment area) before moving to species that currently do not occur within the forest being considered. This section of the menu focuses on forest transformation within the existing ranges of native species. As with other sections of the menu, using an objective-oriented process will provide managers with some of the guidance needed to make transformational options more feasible.

Approach 8.1 Prioritize restoration for transformation with culturally important species, engaging in co-management with local Tribes and Indigenous communities.

Tactics:

- 8.1.1.** Collaborate with Tribes to identify potential species and sites that would achieve multiple benefits
- 8.1.2.** Be open to intensive management strategies that may be required to establish sustainable populations.
- 8.1.3.** Provide funding and frequent, authentic opportunities to co-manage prioritized culturally important species and habitats
- 8.1.4.** Enable and support traditional practices of tending, gathering, and cultural burning

Approach 8.2 Favor or restore native species that are expected to be adapted to future conditions and disfavor maladapted species.

As forest regeneration becomes less predictable after major disturbance events, reforestation efforts should focus on prioritizing the sites most likely to support trees into the future, and avoid investment of scarce resources into unlikely locations, even if they supported trees previously.

Tactics:

- 8.2.1** There is room to expand research-based efforts to identify genotypes of native tree species better adapted to drier and warmer climatic conditions. Currently, foresters work with seed selection tools to identify appropriate seed lots by elevation and latitude. Researchers can further improve efficacy by identifying drought, fire, and pest/disease resistant genetics of the most important species for Southern California: Jeffrey pine, Coulter pine, Bigcone Douglas fir, and black oak. This should include further genetic examination of older successful reforestation projects where genetic material was likely brought in from elsewhere.
- 8.2.2** Treat high elevation bigcone Douglas-fir and disfavor isolated low-elevation occurrences. Bigcone has a wide elevation range but is primarily found between 3,200-7,200 ft (Minnich 2007). While isolated, relict stands can be found at elevations as low as 1,000 ft, these stands are less likely to survive long-term and investment may be better placed by strategically restoring Bigcone Douglas-fir stands in areas where it is most likely to persist into the future Resources should be focused on elevations above 3,200 feet, unless the lower elevations populations are in canyon bottoms where moisture conditions may be favorable

8.2.3 Establish or encourage more closed-cone pines for future high-severity fire regimes. Coulter pine is a facultatively serotinous native species that commonly occurs across several forest types. While its smaller stature and thinner bark make it more sensitive to fire than the yellow pines, it has the advantage of a regeneration strategy that accommodates high-severity fire. Some foresters have had greater success with releasing natural regeneration rather than with planting Coulter.

8.2.4 Expand the capacity for restoration plantings of Engelmann Oak, Canyon Live Oak, and other oaks that are resistant or less susceptible to GSOB. Engelmann is a rare species that has already lost much of its habitat to urban development, and its utilization in restoration could provide a conservation benefit.

Approach 8.3 Establish or encourage new mixes of native species with current ranges within close proximity. Southern California is characterized by high diversity and high species turnover (beta diversity). This approach embraces trials of assisted migration for select species that may be from adjacent lower elevations or sky islands within the Transverse and Peninsular Ranges, but are not found within the assessment area. This approach broadens the footprint of the native species pool beyond the assessment area to neighboring forest areas for consideration in planting.

Tactics:

8.3.1 Experiment with species native to Southern California. Experimentation should be coupled with monitoring and reporting so that lessons from innovative trials are shared regionally with managers.

8.3.2 Remain open to novel combinations of species. The restoration literature recognizes that “novel” ecosystems still can provide valuable ecosystem services, although active management may be needed to maintain values such as habitat structure.

Approach 8.4 Protect seedlings and saplings through vulnerable early life stages.

Seedlings and saplings represent the future forest, and regeneration failure in some forested areas in southern California is deeply concerning. As seedlings and saplings tend to be more sensitive to drought mortality than other life stages, investment into supporting their survival and establishment is worthwhile.

Tactics:

8.4.1 Protect oak regeneration. Oaks are a potential forest dominant, but the spread of GSOB has cascading effects such as reduced acorn production. Natural oak regeneration should be protected with measures such as grazing exclosures and targeted fire exclusion, especially in areas where mature tree loss (and acorn production) has occurred.

8.4.2 Plant to take advantage of precipitation events and reduce drought mortality. The planting window opens in the fall, as soon as the chance of heat events has ended (CA Forest Manual). Fall planting allows seedlings additional access to winter moisture and maximizes time for root growth. However, the time window for fall planting is very short and logistics are complicated. In many cases it will be better to focus on conducting planting as early as possible in late winter (late February) incorporating elevational considerations when soils are 40 degrees and warming. Start planting lower sites as soon as appropriate conditions are reached, rather than waiting for

all sites to be simultaneously plantable. Be prepared for these conditions to occur sooner than in the past. Avoid planting on windy days to limit desiccation; observe guidelines for relative humidity and temperature limits. Planting should not extend past April. In terms of stature, shorter, thicker seedlings may be better able to survive summer drought.

8.4.3. Stronger focus on utilizing microsites (deep soils, cooler, wetter, dead stumps) for planting. Tree seedling survival rates in Southern California are lower than elsewhere in the state. 20-30% survival after three years is considered average, and if drought conditions dominate after planting, nearly 100% mortality has been known to occur. Reforestation planting should be focused on areas where seedlings are most likely to survive. For shade-intolerant yellow pine seedlings, deep soils and cooler/wetter topographic locations will support survival on open slopes.

8.4.4. Protect restoration efforts by leveraging barriers between plantings and ignition sources. This tactic emphasizes minimizing fire risk by intentionally locating planting sites where there are features to reduce fire risk placed between the planting site and ignition hotspots. Consider planting in areas where adjacent treatments may have reduced fire risk to restoration areas.

Approach 8.5 Prioritize establishing populations of at-risk species in locations determined to be climate refugia, where species may be buffered from the impacts of climate change.

Tactics:

8.5.1 Consider establishing rare understory species in sites with a higher probability of providing longer-term refuge. For plants, this would take the form of establishing new populations and creating redundant plantings in locations based on mapped refugia.

Strategy 9. Plan for further change

This section of the menu seeks to provide some guidance for managers considering transformative management for which there is less existing evidence. In workshops, a level of consensus has formed around using co-production and an objective-oriented process when considering transformational options. The best guidance for managers will come from collaborative sessions with partners, including the Indigenous communities on whose ancestral lands the transformation is occurring. This section also seeks to provide initial guidance for managers considering management that is not limited to native species, including specific assisted migration questions that have already arisen in Southern California.

Approach 9.1 Identify goals, objectives, and tactics using co-production. This can be done through a number of established processes, for example the Conservation Standards ([About Conservation Standards \(CS\)](#)). Nowhere in the menu is the need to move beyond one-way transfer of information more critical than when developing transformational management. Allowing information to flow in both directions through engagement will serve to build the support needed to overcome barriers.

Tactics:

9.1.1 Develop management goals and objectives that include both social and ecological components. If objectives serve one but not the other, implementation is more likely to fail. In Southern California, development of management projects is largely driven by the need to reduce

fire risk to communities and protect infrastructure. The link between management and communities should be anticipated, leveraged, and embraced. Humans have played a role in regional ecosystems since time immemorial, and future transformational change should be linked with local human needs and desires.

9.1.2 Focus on co-production of goals and objectives with partners. A collaborative, consensus-based approach may lengthen the process but is likely the only way to generate the level of agreement and cooperation necessary to overcome barriers to transformational management.

9.1.3 When designing tactics, also focus on co-production of tactics with partners. Future challenges and needs cannot be fully envisioned by existing adaptation menu products.

Approach 9.2 Include Indigenous knowledge as a primary consideration from early in the decision-making process.

Tactics:

9.2.1 Collaborate with Tribal natural resources managers and elders to identify acceptable ecosystem futures. Tribes are currently fielding numerous and diverse requests for Indigenous input, and processing these requests is challenging for leadership. In some cases, Tribes work through non-governmental organizations to consolidate and prioritize requests.

9.2.2 Support reciprocity by providing financial compensation. Tribal contributions of time, effort, and knowledge should be valued appropriately with honorariums or other financial compensation.

Approach 9.3 Identify opportunities to pilot new strategies for both conifer and hardwood species. Taking an experimental approach may be useful in locations where the historical vegetation community has become degraded and either restoration attempts have failed or managers deem that restoration is likely to fail. The questions addressed through experimentation may vary, but it is key to conduct the monitoring needed to identify successes and failures.

Tactics:

9.3.1 Identify locations for deliberate and careful experimentation. This could include locations where restoration has failed or managers deem that restoration is likely to fail.

9.3.2 Document trials, conduct follow-up monitoring, and provide reporting. Partnering with an educational institution can provide the needed expertise and staffing. Investments in experimentation need to produce learning in order to be worthwhile. The driving motivation for experimentation should be to determine the potential for application of new tactics across the region.

9.3.3 Examine analogous Mediterranean landscapes that are further into warming and drying (i.e. Baja Mexico, oak woodlands in Spain) for experimental management strategies. One focal area should be the identification of options for maintaining lower-intensity fire regimes, which are more compatible with human communities, and also support understory diversity. Many understory natives, both perennials and annuals, benefit from periodic fire at low/moderate intensities to renew growth and reproduction.

Approach 9.4 Introduce species that are expected to be adapted to future conditions.

For assisted migration, goals would need to be well defined and broadly supported by partners. There would likely need to be few other options for management with native species.

Tactics:

9.4.1 Pinyon pine-juniper. Pinyon pine and juniper species have the benefit of being adapted to dry and warm sites, and also have cultural value to Indigenous communities. However, this vegetation type is sensitive to fire, and is adapted to long fire-free intervals. When fire occurs, fire severity is often high. In this region, restoration success to date has been low. Pinyon pine-juniper is more appropriate for sites with long-term barriers between the intended forestland and sources of high ignition risk, as well as having low connectivity to shrublands that might serve to carry fire into the trees. The paleo record shows that pinyon pine-juniper migrates around the landscape at long time intervals. One form of experimentation could be to allow pinyon pine-juniper to establish in locations where it is naturally colonizing and where its presence would be consistent with management objectives.

9.4.2 Gray pine. Introduction of gray pine (*Pinus sabiniana*) is most feasible in the northwestern strategy area. Some planting has already occurred, but the level of success and benefits from these plantings are unclear. Gray pine is not serotinous and is sensitive to fire. In addition, utilizing this species would constitute a southward range shift.

9.4.3 Southwestern oak species. Introducing species or genetics from southwestern oak species, especially those from southeastern Arizona, has been suggested as one way to adapt to the presence of GSOB, which is native to southeastern AZ. One example of a potential opportunity for assisted migration comes from the association of Pacific Emory oak (*Quercus peninsularis*) with Coulter pine and canyon live oak in the Sierra San Pedro Martir. This species is a close relative to Emory oak (*Q. emoryi*) of southern Arizona and northwestern Mexico, suggesting that *Q. emoryi* could be a useful species for introduction.

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